

200th anniversary of Nicolas Pike's birth 2018 – some associated papers

Nicolas Pike, American consul in Mauritius (and thus also Seychelles) from 1867 to 1873, is most famous for his book on the culture, history and wildlife of Mauritius, published in 1873, entitled *Subtropical rambles in the land of Aphanapteryx*. Less well-known is a briefer account of the granitic Seychelles in the same vein. Pike was also an inveterate collector of all manner of natural history taxa, most of which ended up in museums in the United States.

In October 2018 the Royal Society of Arts & Sciences of Mauritius organised a symposium to celebrate the 200th anniversary of his birth, which took place over two weekends. October 13th saw presentations in the lecture hall of the futuristic building of the Mauritius Commercial Bank in St. Jean, while some further talks, and an amusing acted sketch, followed on October 20th at the old plantation house of St. Antoine in the north of Mauritius, a place Pike himself visited and discussed in his book.

The Society's original intention was to publish these papers in the next issue of their published proceedings, now renamed the *Journal of the Royal Society of Arts & Sciences*. However contributors were informed without prior discussion in June 2019 that "Unfortunately now that the bicentenary of Pike's birth is past history, the Society's Executive Committee, after discussing the matter fully, has decided that unfortunately there was not enough interest locally to carry on with this plan [to publish]". Although they were prepared to accept papers for a future issue of the journal, this would result in the loss of coherence of the Pike event, and in any case the interval between their publications was generally several years, so any immediacy would be lost.

Having failed to persuade them to change their minds, some of us decided to look elsewhere, and Justin Gerlach accepted the proposal to publish in *Phelsuma*. I then offered this option to all contributors, but some, notably those also contributing to the Society's tercentenary events commemorating Pierre Poivre in October 2019, declined. The remaining papers from the 2018 Pike symposium are presented here, together with an annotated version of Pike's 'Visit to the Seychelles Islands' and a brief essay contextualising the tradition of 'rambles' in Mauritius.

Anthony Cheke, October 2019

Touring Mauritius on foot or horse, a brief history of ‘rambles’ in the island

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While science may praise his museum collections and fish paintings, Nicholas Pike is best known in Mauritius and elsewhere for his book *Subtropical rambles* (Pike 1873). Much of the book is taken up with Pike’s descriptions of his excursions on foot in and around the island, including a tour more or less around the coast. Such tours have quite a long pedigree, and indeed Pike appears to have borrowed his title from a predecessor in the genre, George Clark’s anonymously published *A ramble round Mauritius* of just over a decade earlier (Clark 1859). ‘Rambles’ were generally undertaken by outsiders, French or English, though there is one example by a returned expatriate Mauritian, Alfred Erny. A ‘ramble’ in English is more-or-less a *balade* in French¹, though Bernardin’s tough journey (below) was certainly no mere *balade*!

The first published tour of Mauritius was by Abbé Nicolas-Louis de la Caille (1758) while mapping the island, but this astronomer-surveyor wrote only a very terse account of where he had been, without any accompanying description, so the first true ‘ramble’, i.e. in this context a descriptive tour, is that of military engineer Jacques-Henri Bernardin de Saint-Pierre (1773) in 1769. In Bernardin’s day much of the island was devoid of paths, let alone roads, and even with a supportive slave, he had to work hard to complete the task he had set himself. Starting anti-clockwise from Port Louis, in the south and east he had to ford rivers on the shoulders of his slave, suffer sunstroke, scramble up steep sides of deep gorges (Rivière des Anguilles etc.). By the time he reached the Plaine des Roches he decided to accept a horse to take him back to the capital, as ahead were ‘four leagues of uninhabited country where no water was to be had’ [my translation], and he already knew the coast from Pointe aux Canonnières to Port Louis. Bernardin’s account includes no illustrations.

There are several other descriptions of Mauritius in the later eighteenth century and early nineteenth, including the reports from the Baudin, Freycinet & Duperrey expeditions, and Matthew Flinders’s tale of captivity², but the next ‘ramble’ is from Jacques Milbert (1812). He was an expedition artist who abandoned the Baudin expedition to explore Mauritius instead (e.g. Ly-Tio-Fane 2003); his rambles are not dated, but he was on the island between 1801 and 1804. Mauritian infrastructure had come on a lot since Bernardin’s time, and Milbert could travel partly on horseback, though he had to dismount in coastal areas where the abundant burrows of *tourlouroux*³ (land crabs *Cardisoma* spp.) risked causing the horse to stumble and fall. He made several trips inland on foot, but also more or less repeated Bernardin’s coastal odyssey, adding in a dangerous climb of Le Morne *en route*. More observant of the minutiae of nature and geology than Bernardin, Milbert’s temperament lends his descriptions a certain amount of ‘artistic licence’, and lots of digression into generalities. His illustrations, engraved from his drawings⁴, collected into a separate *atlas* volume, provide important visual testimony to Mauritius in the first years of the 19th century. He was, like Bernardin, generally accompanied by a black slave, though at times also by Franco-Mauritian companions.

Our next Rambler, James Holman (1835, Barnwell 1948) was unusual in that he had been struck blind after a naval career, yet continued very actively to travel around the world. His very comprehensive ramble in 1829-30, the first to complete the entire coastline, was performed, not always on foot, accompanied by sighted companions who described the sights and landscape to him as he travelled; from his writing one would be hard put to guess he couldn’t see the scenes he described. He made ample use of his military contacts and generally stayed with British officers or officials as he travelled round the island. His style is very matter-of-fact, recalling Bernardin, but he had little contact outside the British, apart from a few Franco-Mauritian friends of Charles Telfair. Holman’s is the first ramble to include illustrations in appropriate places in the text, albeit very few in the entire 4-volume opus (and only one of Mauritius), as he presumably had to borrow from others as he saw none of it himself.

The mid 19th century was not short of visitors writing accounts of their stays in Mauritius, but few qualify as ‘rambles’. Frederick Mouat’s (1852) book was the first to illustrate his visit with several evocative in-text engravings, albeit nowhere near as detailed as Pike’s two decades later. There are more statistics than travel in Mouat’s account, and Ida Pfeiffer’s visit (1861) was fairly short, but her acerbic comments on Franco-Mauritian society in 1857 led to Alfred Erny (1863, Lalouette 2006) being commissioned to write a specifically favourable riposte for the French periodical *Le Tour du Monde*, which took the form of a ramble in 1860-61; he did not reveal his means of transport. Erny, later a well-known psychological researcher, was a Mauritian settled in France, who came back specifically for this tour; unfortunately his style is informative but pedestrian, and almost all he sees or meets is nice or attractive. Furthermore, he was not above a little plagiarism here and there – compare for example these two passages with those published the year before his visit by George Clark (1859; see next ramble):

¹ *balade/balader* is closer to ‘stroll’ than ‘ramble’, the latter tending to be longer with more exertion, having no exact equivalent in French

² The published account (Flinders 1814) is not a ‘ramble’, but his manuscript diary including his time in Mauritius, despite the restrictions on his movements, would almost qualify – it has recently been published in facsimile (Brown & Dooley 2008).

³ more often, nowadays, *trouloulou* / *trululu*

⁴ some of his original drawings are reproduced by Ly-Tio-Fane (2003).

[Clark] Proceeding along the coast ... we reach St. Antoine⁵, the estate of Mr Edmond de Chazal, a gentleman whose mansion has not only received the most distinguished strangers who have visited our shores, and charmed them with his princely hospitality, *but has given refuge to many a shipwrecked mariner and passenger, and generously supplied their wants* [my italics]

[Erny] ... Je vis d'abord Saint Antoine, l'habitation de M. de Chazal, qui a souvent donné abri aux naufragés et généreusement subvenu à leurs besoins / ... I first saw Saint-Antoine, the estate of M. de Chazal, *who has often given shelter to those shipwrecked and generously supplied their wants* [my translation & italics]

[Clark] In returning towards Port Louis, by *taking a road to the right of that by which the traveller came from Pamplemousses*, he will be led by a substantial stone building formed by a strong wall. *This establishment, now used a district prison is known by the name of Powder Mills, and a manufactory of gunpowder on a large scale was carried on there, and in 1774 an explosion took place which caused the death of many of the persons employed therein*

[Erny] Une route à droite de celle des Pamplemousses conduit par un pont en pierre à l'établissement appelé les Moulins à Poudre. Ver l'année 1774, il y existait une manufacture de poudre, mais à cette époque une terrible explosion détruisit une partie de l'édifice qui sert maintenant de prison / *A road to the right of the one to/from Pamplemousses leads by a stone bridge to the establishment called the Powder Mills. Around the year 1774 gunpowder was manufactured there, but at that time a terrible explosion destroyed part of the building that nowadays serves as a prison* [my translation & italics; what about the employees ?]

Erny was a competent watercolourist, and his ramble is illustrated by engravings by Karl Girardet from his paintings, which provide a better understanding of ordinary life, buildings and scenery than is seen in the more celebrated but idealised prints of Bradshaw (1832), Thuillier or Kelsey (Pitot & Lenoir 1980). Erny wasn't the only plagiarist, Boyle (1867), in a book more descriptive than rambling, added a chapter on fauna 'borrowed largely' from Clark's *Ramble*, albeit this time with acknowledgement.

The year before Erny arrived, the *Mauritius register* published an un-illustrated 132-page supplement as a sort of preface to its normal statistical compendium, paginated in lower-case Roman numerals, and without fanfare. Although there was no credit on the text, the introduction to the issue noted that 'to Mr. G. Clark the Editors' best thanks are especially due, for the contribution of his "Rambles round Mauritius, &c.'" George Clark (1859) was a schoolmaster in Mahébourg, who not only made and described an extensive tour of the island but also added a very detailed natural history of the island's animals, in many ways not matched since in one document⁶. His *Ramble round Mauritius* has Milbert's eye for detail, Bernardin's sober but engaging style, with the useful addition of historical asides not recorded elsewhere, and remarks comparing the island in the late 1850s with how it had been when he arrived in about 1836. On the downside, his long digression in the context of Pamplemousses gardens on the coco-de-mer palm *Lodoicea maldivica* was uncharacteristically over the top. Curiously Clark never mentioned whether he was walking or on horseback as he travelled the island's roads. This is the only ramble that has never appeared in book form, and as copies of the *Mauritius register* are very rare, and although the text of this little masterpiece is now available on the internet⁷, it would be well worth a Mauritian publisher reprinting it. Clark of course became much better known in 1866 for his discovery of Dodo bones in the Mare aux Songes (e.g. Clark 1866, Hume *et al.* 2014).

Finally we come to Pike himself, whose ramble (1873) is closest in character to Milbert's wanderings - a vivid picture of the island, details seen but not always accurately recorded (e.g. Summers 2020, this issue); scenes and events hyped a bit for effect. Yet as he proceeds he also digresses into the geological features, plants and animals he finds, often using Latin names his likely readers would not know, making some pages heavy going, although valuable to the naturalist. He didn't stint himself, going down caves, taking byways to waterfalls, visiting offshore islets etc. - in all he covered more ground even than Milbert. He always travelled on foot, but with a team of servants using ponies to carry provisions, photographic and camping equipment, and his ever growing collections. Pike was a pioneer in Mauritius as a photographer, and his book is generously embellished throughout with detailed illustrations, engraved on wood by S. Cooper from his photos. In 1871 Pike (1872) also visited the granitic Seychelles, and wrote up his 'ramble' there, this time unfortunately without illustrations.

After a century of 'rambles', Pike's is the last, and possibly the most widely read and most travelled: my copy was formerly in the garrison library in Gibraltar! After Pike the *genre* seems to have died out, bar a half-hearted attempt by Verschuur (1899) - what a different story a modern Rambler would tell.

Acknowledgements

I thank Geoff Summers for discovering Clark's *Ramble* on the internet.

References (NB: many out-of-copyright old books and journals have been digitised and can be read online at archive.org or gallica.bnf.fr, or bought as print-on-demand paper copies)

⁵ Pike (1873) also visited Saint Antoine, and this estate, still in the same family, hosted the Royal Society of Arts & Sciences and participants for the second Saturday of the Pike celebrations in October 2018.

⁶ The nearest equivalent is France Staub's *Fauna of Mauritius and associated flora* (1993).

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⁷ <https://ia800301.us.archive.org/6/items/mauritiusregist00clargoog/mauritiusregist00clargoog.pdf>

A Jolly Day Out: Colonel Nicolas Pike's account of the Mahébourg Bay and Ile de la Passe: colonial adventures of an American Consul at Mauritius.

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Abstract: Pike's descriptions of the Mahébourg bay geology and the military remains on Ile de la Passe are compared with observations in the field and found wanting in certain respects. Structures, graffiti and war graves that he mentioned have been recognized in spite of additional WW2 defensive constructions and modifications. Pike's description of one inscribed grave stone led to its rediscovery and relocation to a museum.

Introduction

Nicholas Pike's *Subtropical Rambles in the Land of the Aphanapteryx* is undoubtedly the finest natural history of Mauritius penned in the last quarter of the 19th century (Fig. 1), unsurpassed until Anthony Cheke and Julian Hume's *Lost land of the Dodo*.² While Pike's book contains a wealth of observations, it was not strictly a work of science, or a natural history, as the subtitle, *Personal experiences, Adventures, & Wanderings in and around the Island of Mauritius*, presages. At the start of chapter 23 we find the only account of Ile de la Passe from the second half of the 19th century. Potentially, therefore, this is of considerable importance for any study of the islet. The aims of this paper are twofold: firstly, to determine what can be gleaned from Pike's account of his visit with regard to natural and cultural heritage and, secondly, to test the astuteness and accuracy of his observations as a way of assessing the credibility of his reputation as a scientist.

Pike (1817-1905) himself was a fascinating, larger than life, character; military man, consul and self-taught naturalist. His official responsibilities as American consul in Mauritius were mostly concerned with the passage of American whalers,³ but he perhaps wore these duties lightly as he spent much time travelling around the island observing and collecting (Fig. 2), and enjoying hospitality⁴.

Ile de la Passe is the last in a chain of islets on the fringing reef that forms the south-eastern side of the Mahébourg Bay (Figs 3 and 4). Situated on the edge of the pass it is the closest point to the first human settlement on Mauritius, the Dutch Fort Frederik Hendrik,⁵ on the ruins of which the first French capital was built before the move to Port Louis in 1735.⁶ Today named Vieux Grand Port, it remained the seat of French administration in the south until Decaen made the move to Mahébourg in 1805. Ile de la Passe, as its name implies, controlled entry and egress through the pass. In 1759, or thereabouts, the first defences were constructed on what was essentially a static ship, entirely dependent on the mainland for everything from drinking water to manpower. Famously captured by Captain Nesbit Josiah Willoughby, who became popularly known as 'Willoughby the Immortal',⁷ in August 1810, in the prelude to the Battle of Grand Port. Through these

¹ Fellow of the British Institute at Ankara and Associate, The Oriental Institute, Chicago University. A shorter version of this paper was presented at a conference in Mauritius organised by the Royal Society of Arts and Sciences (RSAS) bicentenary commemorations for Colonel Nicolas Pike on the 13th October 2018. I am most grateful to Anthony Cheke for commenting on a draft and assiduous editing.

² Pike (1873), Cheke & Hume (2008). Pike's name was spelt with an 'h' ('Nicholas') on the title page of the British edition of his book.

³ Michel Eric Perrier, Master Mariner, presented a fascinating paper entitled "*Nicolas Pike, Whales and Whaling Ships*" at the RSAS Pike bicentenary event *Sur les Traces de Pike à la Demeure de Saint Antoine*, 20th Oct. 2018.

⁴ For background see: <https://rsasmauritius.org/fr/nicolas-pike>. Pike has not yet had the book-length biography that he deserves; for a short account see the laudatory overview by Job Dittberner (2014). Recent overviews of heritage, archaeology and history of Mauritius can be found in Seetah (2018).

⁵ Moree 1998; Cheke and Beentje 2018. For a preliminary account of excavations at Fort Hendrik see Floore & Jayasena (2010). There is no in depth account of the standing French period structures.

⁶ On the early history of Port Louis see Chelin (2017); and from its time as the capital, Toussaint (1973).

⁷ Mason (1969).

SUB-TROPICAL RAMBLES
IN
THE LAND OF THE APHANAPTERYX

PERSONAL EXPERIENCES, ADVENTURES, & WANDERINGS

IN AND AROUND

THE ISLAND OF MAURITIUS

BY

NICHOLAS PIKE

THE APHANAPTERYX

(From *The Ibis* for July 1869. By ALPHONSE MILNE-EDWARDS)

LONDON
SAMPSON LOW, MARSTON, LOW, & SEARLE
CROWN BUILDINGS, 188 FLEET STREET
1873

Fig. 1. Title page from Pike (1873).

Fig. 2. Frontispiece from Pike (1873).

Fig. 3. Map showing the location of Ile de la Passe with inset placing Mauritius in the Indian Ocean.

events the islet has gained a central place in the colonial history of Mauritius.⁸ Between 2000 and 2005, at the instigation of Philippe la Hausse de Lalouvière and under the auspices of the National Heritage Fund the author, together with architect Françoise Summers, made an architectural and archaeological study of Ile de la Passe with the participation of Earthwatch and Mauritian volunteers.⁹

⁸ Carter and Hall (2010). The Battle of Grand Port, the only significant Napoleonic naval victory inflicted on the British, was deservedly inscribed on the Arc de Triomphe. It was immortalized by Patrick O'Brian in *The Mauritius Command* (1977, many later editions).

⁹ For Ile de la Passe see <http://www.mauritius.metu.edu.tr/mahbay/ipass/index.html>. Also Summers & Summers (2009).

Fig. 4. Google Earth image of the Mahébourg Bay.

Geology and Geomorphology

Pike devoted the ninth chapter of his book to the geology of Mauritius and made additional observations elsewhere. Our concern here is his understanding of the Bay of Mahébourg, to this day called Grand Port. This was the deepest natural harbour in Mauritius, formed by a deep horseshoe-shaped channel that breaches the fringing reef. In the days of sail, however, exit through the narrow pass was severely restricted by prevailing wind. Perched on the reef on the eastern side of the channel are a chain of small, uninhabited, islets (Fig. 4). The most prominent and visually striking of these is Ile aux Phare, also known by its earlier name of Ile aux Fouquets (named after the shearwaters, *Puffinus pacificus*, that breed there), which boasts a late nineteenth century lighthouse positioned to warn away from the reef shipping making its way to Port Louis. Ile de la Passe is situated on the very north-eastern edge of the pass. On page 329 of *Sub-Tropical Rambles* Pike wrote of it:

“This island is also of upheaval, and of far more recent formation than Mauritius. It is composed of friable greyish sandstone in easily traced strata, that appear to have been thrown over by a sudden convulsion. The dip of the strata is at an angle of thirty degrees and inclined east and west. This and others of the group were most likely upheaved by the once very active volcano in Grand Port Bay”

And on page 135 he described what he took to be evidence of submerged forests in the form of casts of tree stumps that to his mind indicated that the land had at some distant time been below the ocean, and that it had subsequently been uplifted by volcanic activity.

“These casts abound in the islands near Mahébourg, particularly in the Isle des Aigrettes. I collected specimens, and submitted them to severe chemical tests with acids, but failed to discover anything like fibrous tissue.”

The idea that these casts were evidence for once submerged forests does not seem originally to have been Pike's. In a letter from Sir Henry Barkly to Dr. Hooker, dated February 13, 1869, the governor wrote:

“Is it not allowable to suppose that Round Island therefore is the remnant of a much more ancient Island or Continent which once existed where Mauritius is now situated and of which traces are to be found in the Casts of the stems of Submarine forests found by D^r Ayres in Gabriel Island & by

Fig. 5. Tilted beds of eolianite on the side of the French rockcut ditch on Ile de la Passe with graffiti carved by British troops in the mid nineteenth century.

M^r Charles in the Islands off Grand Port. If so how many hints in the chain of animal & vegetable existence may not have perished in the Volcanic eruptions which produced the Mascarene groups!"¹⁰

Pike was correct in his observations that the islets in the Mahébourg Bay comprised sandstone, not coral, and accurately noted the angle of dip in the strata, but his interpretations of their formation have not withstood the test of time. What Pike considered tectonically tilted beds of water-lain sandstone are in fact beds of aeolian sand dunes at their natural angle of rest (Fig. 5). This eolianite, or indurated sandstone,¹¹ in fact formed at the last glacial maximum, about 20,000 years before present, when the Indian Ocean was more than 100 metres lower than it is today¹². We should not, perhaps, be over-harsh in our judgements since Pike was writing decades before plate tectonics and Pleistocene/Holocene sea level changes were understood. Pike's observations in the field do not, on the other hand, appear to have been very astute. He failed to notice, for instance, that the sea birds who excavate nest burrows in the seaward cliffs on Ile aux Phares dig into the soft yellow sand of the dune behind the indurated crust. With regard to the casts, Ile aux Aigrettes is situated in the southern portion of the Mahébourg Bay. Now a nature reserve, the restored vegetation covers the ground, but these casts can be seen around the edge of the islet, especially on the southern side (Fig. 6)¹³. These sub-fossil deposits on Ile aux Aigrettes have been dated 15000-5000 BP, and could belong to the same period as the interglacial during which the deposit on Isle aux Phares containing casts of roots and subfossils of terrestrial molluscs that indicate tall semi-humid forest (Fig. 7)¹⁴.

¹⁰ <http://www.darwinproject.ac.uk/letter/?docId=letters/DCP-LETT-6655.xml>

¹¹ Bird (2005).

¹² Camoin, Montaggioni & Braithwaite (2004), Saddul (2002: 270-271).

¹³ For a history of pre-restoration vegetation on Ile aux Aigrettes see Parnell *et al.* (1989); Krieg (2018) provides a recent overview.

¹⁴ I am most grateful to Owen Griffiths for informing me of this dating that has been done in connection with his work on the snails that indicate the forest type, see Griffiths & Florens (2006).

Fig. 6. Fossil casts on the edge of Isle aux Aigrettes.

Fig. 7. The reddish brown clayey deposit on Ile aux Phare that formed during an interglacial is sandwiched between indurated aeolian dune deposits.

Fig. 8. The Mahébourg Barracks: *Mauritius: As It Was*, 66.

Pike's Visit to Isle de la Passe

Let us now turn to the cultural remains on Ile de la Passe. When Pike visited, presumably in the late 1860s, the islet was unoccupied. It can be assumed that the military buildings of the French period constructed between 1759 and capitulation to the British in 1810, were in a reasonable state of repair, having been reused by the British garrison until its withdrawal to Mahébourg in 1838.¹⁵ It is not clear if any new buildings were erected by the British, plans to build a Martello Tower having been abandoned.¹⁶ These French period defences included the Upper Battery and an impressive, unfinished, rockcut ditch that was utilized to house generators in WW II.¹⁷ As a prelude to his visit Pike wrote, pp. 323-234:

“The Isle de Passe lies at the entrance of the harbour, and will ever be famous in the naval annals of both England and France. On it there stood a circular fort and a barracks as a defence; but in 1810 it was stormed by Captain Pym, of the 'Sirius frigate,' and taken. It was kept by the British through all the thrilling events which occurred in the deadly conflict which took place in Grand Port Bay on the 25th and 26th August, in the same year, when the French gained their bloodiest but last naval victory over the English in the Indian seas. After the capitulation of the Isle de France, the barracks were occupied for some years by a garrison, but they have long been abandoned.”

Scant interest is here shown in the specifics of history, although the events of 1810 are briefly described (pp. 368-69) in the chapter on the history of Mauritius. Characterization of the defences as a “circular fort”, both in the passage quoted above and on p. 368, is over-terse and inaccurate. On the other hand, the American consul's description of his visit to Ile de la Passe can be considered a splendid example of evocative travel writing that has little or nothing to do with scientific pretensions. It bears extensive quotation:

“I had been spending a few days in Mahébourg, where I was most hospitably entertained by the officers of the 86th regiment, when a pic-nic was proposed to the Ile de la Passe. Most of them kept boats and they were all put in readiness for our excursion. Long before dawn on the day fixed, the Creole servants were conveying mysterious-looking boxes and hampers to be stowed away in the boats, filled with everything requisite for a good time. At sunrise the officers made their appearance in the mess-room, dressed in suitable boating costume, but with more regard to ease than elegance.”

¹⁵ la Hausse de Lalouvière (1998: 63).

¹⁶ *Ibid.* p.62.

¹⁷ <http://www.mauritius.metu.edu.tr/mahbay/ipass/index.html>. Summers (2008), Summers & Summers (2009).

Fig. 9. The Barklys with soldiers: *Mauritius: As It Was*, 63.

Thus were preparations made for a jolly day out, interestingly in boats that were the property of the officers themselves. Figure 8 shows the barracks at Mahébourg very much as they would have been at the time. Also seemingly at Mahébourg are Governor Sir Henry Barkly, Lady Anna Barkly and Miss Barkly, perhaps with Sir Henry's eldest son and private secretary, Arthur Cecil Stuart Barkly, standing in white, reproduced here as Figure 9. Some of the very same officers probably accompanied Consul Pike on his visit.¹⁸ On the journey across the water Pike was "able to hook up many interesting specimens of algae". The party crossed Trou Moutou, the maximum ten-metre depth of which he greatly exaggerated, arriving at Ile de la Passe after three hours of rowing.

"The place we landed at is rocky, and has been washed by the sea to such an extent there was a danger of the boats being stove in, if the sea proved rough, by getting sucked under the projecting rocks. We all proceeded to a small house that I took to have been the Commandant and soldiers' quarters."

The 'small house' would have been the stone building, recently restored, which was adapted for use as a generator room in WW II. Figure 10 offers a reconstruction of how this building, which is labelled as a storehouse on all French and British period maps and plans, would have looked at the time of Pike's visit. The account, in which this stone-built Store is assumed to have been quarters for officers and men, implies that neither the barracks nor the kitchen were still standing. We are told that extant weaponry comprised no more than two iron mortars and part of a gun carriage, all now very badly corroded but still there to this day, and a 68 pounder, which has long since vanished. Presumably the timber framed barracks building and kitchen were demolished when the rest of the cannons, carriages and platforms were removed at the time when the garrison transferred to Mahébourg, but no relevant records have been found in the archives. Pike's account continues:

"In close proximity to this house was the magazine, with a strong high wall built around it. The arrangement for heating shot was very curious, and the work spoke of ancient times."

¹⁸ These two photographs are from the collection of Sir Henry Barkly now curated at the Blue Penny Museum, Port Louis, see le Compte (2010).

FRONT ELEVATION WITH PHOTO

FRONT ELEVATION

STRUCTURE 2 - STOREHOUSE

Fig. 10. Storehouse on Ile de la Passe as it was in the 1990s and, below, a virtual reconstruction by Françoise Summers of the original French elevation as Pike would have seen it.

These two important buildings, the gunpowder magazine and the hot shot furnace, both French, constitute some of the most important 18th century French military structures preserved in the southern hemisphere (Figs 11-13). As to the elevated upper battery we are told only: “Room was made on the seaward in the rock for guns *en barbette*.” These notes are too brief to be of much utility. It is curious that no mention is made of the cistern, or of the great rock-cut ditch. Pike’s observation that a single explosive shell would have been devastating takes no account of the fact that the defences belong to the time of round shot and, rarely fired from ships, mortars.

Fig. 11. The hot shot furnace and powder magazine on Ile de la Passe.

SECTION AA

PLAN

STRUCTURE 3 - SHOT FURNACE

Fig. 12. Plan and elevation of the hot shot furnace.

Development of breech-loading guns that fired shells had, by the middle of the 19th century, rendered all such coastal defences obsolete.

Like any visitor today, Pike was captivated by the many graffiti carved into the soft sandstone and occasionally the harder basalt walling. Most were made between 1840 and the late 1860s, very many by officers

Fig. 13. Plan and elevation of the barrel-vaulted powder house.

and men of the Fifth regiment of Foot (VF). These provide names, enlistment numbers and, rarely, a date, together with occasional representation of military crests or other symbols (Fig. 14).

“Soldiers who were quartered there had amused themselves by cutting their names and numbers, and the number of the regiment they were attached to, on the walls. There was scarcely a stone inside or out of the magazine but had one or more names on it.”

One doubts, however, that these graffiti were carved while the islet was permanently garrisoned. This is confirmed by the fact that the earliest inscribed date so far recognized is 1840. Of yet greater interest we read, with reference to those killed in the Battle of Ile de la Passe, August 1810, as a result of subsequent accident, and possibly also in the early action of the Battle of Grand Port that¹⁹:

“In the middle of the island there were many graves; and I noticed the names some of the brave 86th, who had fought in the desperate engagements previously mentioned. There lay the remains of the poor fellows taking their final earthly rest in the desolate island, never more to start at the sound of the reveille, or the thundering din of battle:

And though no stone may tell
Their name, their rank, their glory,

¹⁹ It has not been possible to calculate the total number of men who died on Ile de la Passe and may have been buried there. In normal times any deceased soldier or slave would have been taken to the mainland for burial on consecrated ground, there being no chapel on Ile de la Passe. Some indication of the numbers can be found in Carter & Hall (2010).

Fig. 14. Graffiti made by Irish soldiers visiting Ile de la Passe 1840s-60s.

They rest in hearts that that loved them well,
 And they grace Britannia's story
 Some kind-hearted fellow of the present regiment had placed a new head and foot-stone at one of
 the graves, and rudely carved on it: 'The 86th Regiment'."

The verse, like other snatches of poetry in the *Rambles*, seems to have been penned by Pike himself. At least one of the graves is still in existence, and the author was immediately able to locate the inscribed head-stone in 2003 (fig. 15). This stone is now on display in the National History Museum at Mahébourg, having been moved there for safekeeping in the wake of disturbance by campers on the islet. Most other graves seem to have been covered by WW II concrete building platforms. Pike mentions additional stones on which he was able to recognize names from 1810. Some slight support for this report of the existence of additional inscribed tomb stones might be gleaned from a romantic novel, *A Maiden of Mauritius*, written by John Gorrie, a judge in Mauritius from 1869 to 1876, but only recently published²⁰. In this entirely fictional work descriptive licence has been taken, not least in placing the Ile aux Phare lighthouse on Ile de la Passe. However, in the same paragraph (page 97) Gorrie writes: "The epitaphs on the tombstones were deciphered." There can be little doubt that Gorrie visited Ile de la Passe himself, and it not impossible that his description of youngsters tearing down rafters from buildings to make a bonfire refers to the Store on Ile de la Passe rather than to the lighthouse (on Isle aux Phare) built in 1864 that, apart from a break during the Great War, was operative until 1927²¹. On the other hand, writing in Fiji after his transference thence from Mauritius, it can most probably be assumed that our novelist would have known Pike personally and would doubtless have avidly read his new book. He may equally well have based his fictional reference to engraved tombstones on Pike's account cited above. Furthermore, it might be thought that the roughness of the collective inscription commemorating fallen of troops of the 86th Regiment of itself precludes the existence of additional inscribed stones that would have rendered it superfluous. In any event, it is improbable that any further headstones will have survived to this day.

²⁰ Gorrie (2016).

²¹ Abandoned 1927 according to Mauritius Wild Life (2019: 9). For photos of the lighthouse in the early 1900s (and also of Ile de la Passe) see Kerven & Martial (2012); also: <https://www.facebook.com/vintagemauritius/photos/a.374663112619120/1193852334033523/?type=1&theater>

Fig. 15. The headstone on Ile de la Passe recorded by Pike and rediscovered in 2003.

And so to lunch! Pike again:

“After having examined everything worth seeing on the island, we returned to the house, where a bountiful repast was spread, and the popping of corks and rattling of dishes gave proof that the advance party had opened action, and in a few minutes the whole column was actively engaged in doing its duty, as English and Yankees know well how. All were in the best of spirits, and it would be hard to find a jollier lot of fellows than the officers of the 86th. After thoroughly discussing all the good things under which our table temporarily groaned, we found a goblet of iced champagne most welcome, as the thermometer had risen ten degrees since morning.”

The way home, after some brief hunting for shells, was marred by bad weather. One and then the other boat stuck on the reef and had to be pushed off, after which some hard pulling on the oars was required.

Conclusions

How, then, to assess the academic value of Nicholas Pike’s entertaining and evocative sub-tropical ramblings on what was, after all, a jolly day out. *Sub-Tropical Rambles* is most certainly deserving of a place in the history of nineteenth century travel writing, and doubtless possesses much to offer students of colonialism, but neither of those areas of interest concern the present paper. With regard to science, Pike might be forgiven for misunderstanding the geology of the islets. His attempts not only to explain what he observed, but to conduct experiments in order to learn more about the samples that he collected are indeed laudable. Much of his collections of flora and fauna, both terrestrial and marine, survive to this day in the Museum of Comparative Zoology at Harvard²². It is unfortunate that the avid collector of seaweed, shells, fish, birds and insects did not make fuller descriptions of the buildings and batteries; and frustrating that his account of the graves with their now lost head-stones is so short on detail. But we do learn that there were graves from the brief British military occupation in August 1810. The one engraved stone that survives would probably not have been rediscovered, nor the extant grave recognized, without their mention in Pike’s account. Furthermore, he informs us, if only by default, that armament and buildings had been removed by the 1860s. I am not competent to judge his broader contributions to natural history, but with regard to cultural heritage it might not be unjust to think that his

²² <https://mczbase.mcz.harvard.edu/SpecimenSearch.cfm>, I am grateful to Melissa Aja, Museum Projects Coordinator & Interim Managing Editor, Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard University.

writings are left wanting. It seems obvious enough that he did not make notes in the field, nor make sketches. Rather, he wrote from memory, and in the case of his visit to Ile de la Passe, perhaps not until some little time had elapsed once he had returned to Port Lois from his excursion around the Island. Sir Henry Barkly, who knew Pike well and was courteous about his description of the geology of Round island, perhaps summed him up most succinctly: “the American Consul Colonel Pike, who like most Yankees knows something of everything”²³.

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²³ <http://www.darwinproject.ac.uk/letter/?docId=letters/DCP-LETT-6655.xml>

Col. Nicolas Pike: homme extraordinaire

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It is a pleasure to join this group celebrating the bicentennial of the birth of Colonel Nicolas Pike. Before delving into the delicious details of his life, I would like you to entertain a few thoughts by way of a preface.

Homme Extraordinaire: Several other titles suggested themselves for these remarks: consul extraordinaire, diplomat extraordinaire, natural scientist extraordinaire. I chose this one, homme extraordinaire, because it includes all the others. Nicolas Pike was indeed an extraordinary man. He embodies the traditional Western ideal of an educated, cultivated, sophisticated, well-rounded person – in short, a Renaissance man. I trust you will reach the same conclusion after these remarks. End of Preface. Now, let's go.

Here he is: Col. Nicolas Pike in a drawing familiar to Mauritians from the famous book he wrote, *Sub-Tropical Rambles*¹. He is in his early 50s, surrounded by “his collection” of plants, one bird, his dog Quilp, a couple of corals, and a shell. He looks very dignified and stately, especially with his furrowed brow. There's a lot of gravitas here. A single drawing can never capture the full spectrum of a personality, of course, and the jaunty angle of his hat does suggest another aspect.

The collection of plants in this drawing reminds us of a passage in the preface of *Sub-Tropical Rambles*: “In a second volume, nearly completed, I propose treating more fully the Fauna and Flora of Mauritius.” Alas, many have searched in vain for this volume. It has been lost, as have been almost all his letters to family and friends -- and he was a prodigious correspondent -- and much of his correspondence to other natural scientists around the world over several decades. What we know about Pike comes primarily from his book and articles he has written, a few letters to him from Louis Agassiz, the founder of the Museum of Comparative Zoology at Harvard and an eminence grise among American naturalists, and a local Brooklyn New York newspaper that followed him closely for more than 50 years².

¹ Pike, N. 1873. *Sub-tropical rambles in the land of Aphanapteryx. Personal experiences, adventures & wanderings in and around the island of Mauritius*. London: Sampson Low, Marston, Low & Searle, & New York: Harper Brothers. 511pp. NB: footnotes throughout added by Anthony Cheke.

² The *Brooklyn Daily Eagle* (henceforth ‘BDE’) during 1846-1895 – see Dittberner, J.L. 2014. Nicolas Pike – natural scientist extraordinaire. *Proc. Roy. Soc. Arts Sci. Mauritius* 8: 117-139.

Pike is a great American naturalist, but it must be recognized that he is not well known now in the United States. He was much better known in the United States and internationally in the 19th century, especially in the East and in New York in particular.

I would not have known him at all were it not for a brief article in the Mauritian periodical *Prosi* in 1990 by Maurice Paturau³. My wife Ghislaine Dalais found an article about the 19th century US Consul to Mauritius Nicolas Pike and his collection of Indian Ocean fish paintings⁴. She and I subsequently visited the American Museum of Natural History in New York City to view the collection. We were simply astonished by the beauty of the watercolors. With support from the museum's Director of Special Collections, we concocted big plans to publish a book. What with raising children and other activities, those plans wilted and died, but we never forgot the astonishing collection and the beauty of the paintings. The scope of our interests later grew to fit the fish paintings into Pike's broader life, and it was there I discovered that it was his friend (and later wife) Maria Louisa Hadley⁵ who painted the fish, not Pike himself, though it remains known as the Pike collection. But we will get into that later in more detail later.

It was with delight and enthusiasm we were asked to return to the American Museum of Natural History in New York City and select 35 paintings of 468 in the Pike collection for the Blue Penny Museum's bicentennial exhibit in Mauritius. The museum staff welcomed us warmly and facilitated the exhibit at the Blue Penny by gratuitously providing high-definition photographs. Upon our request, they also contacted the Harvard Museum of Comparative Zoology to see if the museum still possessed the preserved *pikei*⁶ fish we had identified in a painting folio. Indeed, it still had that *pikei* fish in alcohol sent by Pike to Louis Agassiz⁷. It was there we also found a few important letters from Agassiz to Pike. The generosity and courtesy of the American Museum of Natural History have been very helpful for this exhibit and celebration.

Nicolas Pike is a man of so many major achievements I feel I have a tiger by the tail in trying to tell part of his story. First, there are no indications and no evidence anywhere that Pike studied painting, drawing or design or that he took classes or had formal training of any kind in the natural sciences. He was self-taught, must have read a great deal, and learned from discussing with other members of the natural history organizations that he so deeply enjoyed.

Born on January 26, 1818⁸, the fifth of 11 children, to a prominent New England family, he apparently showed a proclivity and delight for nature even very young, and rather than go to Harvard or join the military as others in his family had done and urged him to do so, he struck off on his own and headed for Brooklyn, New York in 1839, when he was 21. He found work variously described as an employee of a paper business. He married sometime during these early years, but all we know is that his wife died in 1845. He remarried into a prosperous Brooklyn family in 1846, and had four children in the next several years. He seemed to be quite gregarious. He joined the Mendelsohn Society and was known for a good voice, which he shared publicly with others, and was active in the local military reserve unit, reflecting a long family tradition.

It is remarkable that his naturalist dedication to study and collection emerges immediately. He threw himself into such activities with great energy. As early as 1842 – he's been in Brooklyn now for 3 years and is 24 years old -- he gave a collection of birds to the Brooklyn Natural History Society and began his collection and study of the algae of Long Island (finally finished as a collection and published in 1885). His intelligence and activism soon gained public recognition., and the list of his achievements in the next several years is impressive. He became interested in the new technology of the daguerrotype and soon was elected Vice President of the New York Photographic Society. In 1849 he was elected President of the Microscopical Society and Vice President of the Scientific Club of New York. He was a key person on the introduction of 'English' sparrows *Passer domesticus* to the United States to counteract the depredation of inch-worms

³ Paturau. M. 1990. Consul extraordinaire. *Prosi* 256: 16-17

⁴ Gudger, E.W. 1929. Nicolas Pike and his unpublished paintings of the fishes of Mauritius, western Indian Ocean, with an index to the fishes. *Bull. Am. Mus. Nat. Hist.* 58: 489-530.

⁵ Pike dedicated his book to 'M.L.L.' "for the valuable assistance rendered me whilst writing its pages; also for the kind care and attention bestowed upon me when stricken down with fever alone in a strange land..." [in 1867]. Paturau (*loc.cit.*) named Pike's friend as Madame Léa Lubbock, a currently untraceable 'modiste' running a shop in Port Louis and who was said to have contributed significantly to the illustrations in the book, which Paturau disbelieved, citing the publisher's prospectus (not seen by me) as saying that the illustrations were from 'the author's own sketches', in fact his photographs. As we know Marie Hadley painted the fishes for Pike, Paturau (or his source) may have conflated stories of two different women.

⁶ Blacklip damselfish (*Pomacentrus pikei*)

⁷ This was formally described from Pike's specimen by Richard Bliss in 1883: Descriptions of new species of Mauritian fishes. *Trans. Roy. Soc. Arts Sci. Mauritius* NS 13: 45-63.

⁸ see also: Dittberner 2014, Gudger 1929 *loc. cit.* & Barnwell, P.J. 1945. Pike, Nicholas [sic]. *Dictionary of Mauritian Biography*: 151-2.

Euonomos subsignarius devastating the trees⁹. He was elected President of the Natural History Society in 1849 and in 1850 Director of the Brooklyn Institute, an important and thriving intellectual scientific center. The same year, 1850, he was elected a corresponding member of the Zoological Society of London and Vice President of the *Société Universelle pour l'Encouragement des Arts et de L'Industrie*.

This is a dizzying accumulation of titles and honors for a person in his early 30s. I have never had the impression that the titles and honors were the results of self-promotion or a matter of Pike's personal ambitions. Rather, it seems they are indicative and public recognition of a person of exceptional quality, intelligence, and uncommon commitment.

There is, moreover, the matter of his uncommon, seemingly boundless energy. Following Pike's life and activities sometimes feels exhausting. He never tires. (Perhaps once, visiting Round Island.) His curiosity and his need to collect, categorize and understand are without limit. You may recall he became so restless waiting at the hunt for the deer to arrive that he left the stand to examine the flora. As he said, "I only regretted I was not at the *chasse aux plantes* instead of *aux cerfs*." He is simply passionate about understanding the natural world. If the contemporary advice to the young seeking what to do with their life is "Follow your passion," Pike is a splendid exemplar. He followed his passion.

If indeed he was so passionate about studying nature, why did his life work take a major turn in 1852 when at the age of 34 accepted the post of US General Counsel to Portugal? We do not have even a clue. He served there as a diplomat for six years, by all accounts conscientiously completing his diplomatic responsibilities without abandoning his curiosity and his commitment to studying nature. In fact, his greatest achievement in his Portuguese diplomatic years derives from this passion. A disease was devastating Portuguese vineyards and "threatening all the valuable wine districts of Europe." Pike was asked by the Portuguese government to study the problem. He produced a thorough report with drawings showing the various stages of the disease and suggested, with some trepidation, a solution. The solution was tried, proved successful, and the report was widely circulated to the governments of France and Portugal, read in London, and published by the United States¹⁰.

Returning to the US in 1860, Pike plunged into activities of several scientific organizations in the following years, lecturing on a variety of topics, e.g., the pork worm and the effect of colored light on plant growth¹¹. When the American civil war broke out in 1861, he was commissioned as a lieutenant colonel, served as a recruiting agent for the armed forces of the North, and emphasized in lectures photography as a front-line form of battlefield information and intelligence for the armies of the North.

⁹ This was Pike's most far-reaching legacy, introducing a bird, soon unwelcome, that now numbers many tens of millions in the Americas:

The English Sparrow was first brought to this country, so far as authentic information has reached the Department, in the fall of 1850, when the Hon. Nicolas Pike and other directors of the Brooklyn Institute imported eight pairs into Brooklyn, N. Y.

As this first importation of Sparrows is of much interest, we give in full Mr. Pike's account of it and of the following importation a year or two later. He says :

"It was not till 1850 that the first eight pairs were brought from England to the Brooklyn Institute, of which I was then a director. We built a large cage for thorn, and cared for them during the winter months. Early in the spring of 1851 they were liberated, but they did not thrive. In 1852 a committee of members of the Institute was chosen for the re-introduction of these birds, of which I was chairman. Over \$200 was subscribed for expenses. I went to England in 1852, on my way to the consul-generalship of Portugal. On my arrival in Liverpool I gave the order for a large lot of Sparrows and song birds to be purchased at once. They were shipped on board the steam-ship *Europa*, if I am not mistaken, in charge of an officer of the ship. Fifty Sparrows were let loose at the Narrows, according to instructions, and the rest on arrival were placed in the tower of Greenwood Cemetery chapel. They did not do well, so were removed to the house of Mr. John Hooper, one of the committee, who offered to take care of them during the winter. In the spring of 1853 they were all let loose in the grounds of Greenwood Cemetery, and a man hired to watch them. They did well and multiplied, and I have original notes taken from time to time of their increase and colonization over our great country." - from Barrows, W.B. 1889. *The English Sparrow in North America*.

Washington: Government Printing Office.

¹⁰ The disease was a fungus, powdery mildew, originally called *Oidium tuckeri* (it is still known as 'oidium' in Portugal), now known as *Uncinula necator* (or *Erysiphe necator*), which spread rapidly after first appearing in Europe in England in 1845. Pike must have been alert to trials elsewhere and recommended sulphur fumigation, which saved Portuguese vineyards temporarily until overwhelmed by *Phylloxera* aphid infestation a decade later. Although the oidium outbreak is still mentioned in discussions of Portuguese wine history, the devastation by *Phylloxera* was so much worse, that Pike's successful and locally lauded intervention (see Gudger, *loc.cit.*) has faded from contemporary histories (e.g. Morrow, D.W. 1973. *Phylloxera* in Portugal. *Agricultural History* 47: 235-247).

¹¹ Reported in the BDE, see Dittberner 2014, *loc. cit.*)

In 1866 he was offered a diplomatic post in China. He declined, perhaps because of the lingering effects of his second wife's death in 1865. Later in 1866 he accepted the appointment as Consul to Mauritius. As they say, the rest is history.

He arrived after an adventurous four-and-a-half month journey along the East coast of South America, including a strong hurricane which, of course, he analyzed in minute detail¹². He arrived on January 12, 1867, amid the fierce malaria epidemic of 1867-1868, which took tens of thousands of lives, sometimes as many as 240 a day in Port Louis at its peak. As he recounts in *Sub-Tropical Rambles*, the epidemic took him down for four months, almost, he says, to the edge of the grave¹³.

In the first months he reported regularly to the Secretary of State on the devastating impact of the epidemic on Mauritians and Americans¹⁴. Of the 25 Americans then in Mauritius, 7 died of malaria and many crews of incoming ships came down. He had to report on the deceased Americans and take care of their personal belonging. He himself ministered to the sick on ship when the hospitals were full and, as he recounts in his book, he ministered to others in their homes. He advised the US government to warn ships en route to China to avoid Mauritius. At one point he reported to the Secretary of State that he had two seamen on his hands, one insane, one blind. With the passing of the epidemic and return of his health, his reports to the State department began to reflect the normal work of the consulate.

The position as Consul was no sinecure. The staff was small: he had an Englishman as secretary, two Indian-origin helpers, and an American "outdoor clerk". US interests in Mauritius at this time were overwhelmingly trade and commercial, focusing particularly on whaling¹⁵. Much reporting to the State Department was bureaucratic in nature, including import-export statistics, vexing maritime problems with abusive captains and crew members, mutinies, deserters, port rates for whalers, the cost of ship repairs, ship arrivals and departures as well as the nature and value of their cargoes, postage costs, etc.

He was able to fulfill his diplomatic duties and still have time to pursue the passion of his life as a natural scientist. He was immensely energetic and productive in this pursuit. Mauritius was the equivalent of Eden for a naturalist, and as he says in *Sub-Tropical Rambles*, he was "bewildered with the beauty of the place." It is no easy task to indicate even summarily the extent of his activities. There is, first of all, the book, *Sub-tropical Rambles*, a comprehensive look at Mauritius, its history, customs, traditions, and populations, illustrated with 47 engravings of Mauritian places and people. In addition he published several articles, which were carried in the annual *Transactions of the Royal Society of Arts & Sciences*, and he was the first foreigner to become a Vice President of the Royal Society. Pike said he considered this one of the highest compliments ever paid him. He traveled all over Mauritius, its nearby islands, and the Seychelles, observing and collecting specimens of flora and fauna, aiming at that second book.¹⁶

He became deeply interested in the fish of the Indian Ocean and learned a great deal more, some, no doubt, from Louis Agassiz, the founder of the Museum of Comparative Zoology at Harvard and, as I mentioned earlier, an eminence grise in the world of natural scientists. Evidently Pike contacted Agassiz sometime in 1870. My wife Ghislaine found and carefully read the few extant letters from Agassiz to Pike. In letters responding to Pike in November and December 1870

¹² Pike's storm analysis was explored at the symposium in a talk entitled *Pike et la "Cyclonomie"* by Jacques Pougnet. See also: Pike, N. 1868. An account of a cyclone, January 6 and 7, 1867, encountered by the United States steamer *Monocacy* while on her passage from Simon's Bay to Mauritius, in the Indian Ocean. *Annual report of the Board of Regents of the Smithsonian Institution ... for the year ended 1867*: 477-481. There are some interesting differences in this account from that given in his book. In the book Pike also commented in detail on a cyclone at Mauritius in 1868.

¹³ This personal comment does not in fact appear to be from the book - ASC

¹⁴ Dispatches from US consuls in Port Louis, 1817-1906 (record Group 59), US National Archives (see Dittberner 2014, loc.cit)

¹⁵ In a talk addressing *Nicolas Pike – Consuls and Whaleships* for the bicentennial, Michael Eric Perrier laid out the legal powers and responsibilities of American Consuls over whaleships, Masters, and whalers in disputes. "No consul," he argues, could avoid problems arising from the discharge of his duties." The 1872 case study of Pike and Master John Pierce of the whaler *Annie Ann* is particularly enlightening. See also: Busch, B.C. 1994. *Whaling will never do for me - The American whaler in the Nineteenth Century*. Lexington: University Press of Kentucky. 265pp.

¹⁶ In his bicentennial conference paper "The Maverick and the Bureaucrat: the tension between Nicolas Pike and Edward Newton in documenting Mauritian natural history in the 1860s and 1870s" (this issue), Anthony Cheke examines the contrast and differences between the two naturalists exploring Mauritius during the same years, both members of the Royal Society. A "clash of key personalities" occurred – in their writings, not in public. Pike hardly acknowledges even the existence of Newton. Newton is seriously critical of Pike's professional knowledge, especially related to birds, assessing him on one occasion as "an awful liar and humbug", and speaking of his book as "full of gross lies". Cheke notes that Newton never substantiated the claim that Pike lied.

Agassiz expressed his elation that Pike was willing to collaborate on the matter of Indian Ocean fish since he had no other partner in that region. He was eager to give his advice. He advised Pike to send the fish preserved in pickle jars filled with alcohol to preserve the color and even specified that the size of the pickle jar openings should vary so larger fish and other matter easily could be inserted. Pike eventually sent hundreds of fish specimens preserved in alcohol to European and American institutes, in particular, to Louis Agassiz. Pike later boasted “My list of the fish is more than double that of any other collector. It numbers 871 species, of which there were 27 new species and one new genus...”

Many of these fish were painted, and there are now 468 drawings and paintings in seven (or eight) folio volumes found in the New York American Museum of Natural History. According to Nicolas Pike, the painter of the watercolors was Maria Louisa Hadley, the daughter of an English commissioner in South Africa known for her drawing and designs and who moved to Mauritius in 1870. (She later became Mrs. Pike.) Pike later publicly credited her on several occasions for the paintings¹⁷. He may have guided and probably played some role in their production, but he gave her all the credit. The water color paintings of the fish are masterpieces and magnificent¹⁸ Agassiz also suggested Pike collect corals, shells, and algae and use a dredging method to do so. Pike collected great quantities of these. Some – we do not know how many – went to Agassiz and the Harvard museum where they are today. Others went to museums and organizations around the world. So many went to the Brooklyn Historical Society that it ran out of storage space and pleaded with him to send no more. One meeting of another organization noted: Pike’s donations comprise “about 1000 species of shells, 100 species of ferns, 300 species of algae mounted; of all these there are great numbers of duplicates for exchange.”

Pike’s diplomatic duties and naturalist activities certainly did not exclude a vigorous social life. We know little about this aspect of his life here except from *Sub-Tropical Rambles*. His excursions and explorations usually had a social dimension to judge by his accounts. He gets along well with his companions on his visits around the island and to the outlying islands and describes their series of adventures with pleasure. Hospitality and friendliness, he says in *Sub-Tropical Rambles*, are universal. I suspect he was a welcome dinner guest. Toward the end of his time in Mauritius a small number of critics tried to impugn his reputation. To no avail. Pike forcefully refuted their allegations, and dozens of the leading citizens and businessmen in Mauritius, the United States, and Europe vouched for his reputation and rallied to his support. Hearing the allegations, Louis Agassiz even wrote to President Grant vouching for Pike’s integrity.

In early 1873 after 6 years in Mauritius, Pike requested return to the United States for reasons of health¹⁹, apparently a recurrence of dengue fever and malaria. The request was granted, and he left Mauritius in autumn 1873.

Now 55 years old, Nicolas Pike returned to Brooklyn in 1874 and lived for 32 more years, as active as he had been in Mauritius. He and Maria Louisa Hadley married in 1875 and continued their collaboration, often in the context of the same scientific institutions as earlier. The honors continued to accumulate. Again his research, collection, and various activities were too extensive even to summarize. For example, a newspaper report from 1887 mentions thousands of spiders in glass bottles classified in 350 distinct classes by the number and position of their eyes²⁰. Many spiders, it says, were drawn by his wife. He kept connections with Mauritius and was later appointed as the principal representative of Mauritius to the 1882 science congress in Boston.

He was almost unstoppable. Almost. His wife died in 1892, her obituary²¹ noting that “Her pictures of the fishes of the Indian Ocean, drawn and colored from life” are “among the remarkable instances of her talent and industry.”

It was apparently because he fell on hard times in the early years of 1900 that he approached the financier and great collector J P Morgan with the offer to purchase his folios of painted fish. Happily, J P Morgan bought them, then contributed them to the New York American Museum of Natural History, where they rest today, carefully guarded²². Nicholas Pike died shortly thereafter in 1905 at the age of 87.

What can we say about the legacy of this great American natural scientist and diplomat? I suggest that his legacy is at least four-fold. First, he represented and advanced American interests in a way that won the respect and even affection of Mauritians. Secondly is the picture of the complexity, variety, and richness of Mauritian people and life he depicted in *Sub-Tropical Rambles*. Thirdly, the collection of Indian Ocean/Mauritian fish his wife painted must be included as a Mauritian treasure. Fourthly and finally is the enormous quantity of fish, corals, shells, and algae now found at the Harvard Museum of Comparative Zoology – still in need of further examination.

At the end of the well-known monograph he prepared on the Pike fish folios for the American Museum of Natural History, E W Gudger wrote, “To rescue from oblivion the name of this man, to make known his work and particularly his drawings of fishes...these are the purposes of this article.” More broadly, they are certainly the purposes of this bicentennial event. Nicolas Pike: *vraiment homme extraordinaire* [truly an extraordinary man].

¹⁷ see Dittberner (2014) for further details

¹⁸ Emmanuel Richon framed the high-definition photographs provided by the American Museum of Natural History and displayed them well at the Blue Penny Museum

¹⁹ See Cheke *The maverick and the bureaucrat*, this issue, for alternative possible reasons for his leaving Mauritius

²⁰ BDE 31 July 1887

²¹ BDE 25 March 1892

²² Gudger 1929, *loc. cit.*

The maverick and the bureaucrat: the tension between Nicholas Pike and Edward Newton in documenting Mauritian natural history in the 1860s & 1870s

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Introduction

Either side of 1870 in Mauritius, there were two stand-out expatriate naturalists, both very active in collecting and writing, and both very much involved with the Royal Society of Arts and Sciences of Mauritius. One was American consul Nicolas Pike¹, whose birth bicentenary is being celebrated today²; the other was Edward Newton, the Colonial Secretary, i.e. the Governor's deputy, and the man effectively in charge of the day to day running of the then British colony. They could hardly have been more different in character, and it is perhaps not surprising that they were not, to put it mildly, the best of friends. Pike was in the island 1867-1873, Newton 1859-1877.

The *dramatis personae*

Although we don't have many descriptions of him from others (apart from Newton, of which more later), it is clear from his own writings, especially *Sub-tropical rambles* (Pike 1873), that he was sociable, ebullient, loquacious and possessed of a large ego³, evidently good company and entertaining. In his account of visiting the Seychelles in 1871 (Pike 1872) he proudly reveals when visiting the masonic lodge in Victoria that he "was very handsomely received by the Officers and Members of the Lodge, with the honors due me as S. P. R. S. of the G. O. F." – that is to say 'Sublime Prince of the Royal Secret' of the Grand Orient de France – that's the second highest of their 33 masonic degrees (Hannah 1952) – i.e. a very big fish in that small pond. He had a very high opinion of his own natural history knowledge, was often called upon to pontificate on objects exhibited at meetings of the *Société Royale*. Eighteen months after his arrival, he was elected a member in July 1868 'in recognition of his important position, the varied knowledge he possesses, and the services he has rendered to science' (Séance du 23 juillet 1868, *TRSAS*⁴ NS 3(2): 108, 1869; my translation⁵), and then to the Council the following January (Séance annuelle du 26 janvier 1869, *TRSAS* NS 3(2)135), topping the votes. In his undated farewell letter (Séance du 23 août 1873, *TRSAS* NS 8: 22-24, 1875⁶) Pike thanks the Society for electing him a Vice-President, though I cannot find evidence of when this was done. As I noted in *Lost land of the Dodo* (Cheke & Hume 2008), Pike "spent so much time exploring the island, both socially and physically, that his official duties must have been rather light". However, like Newton, he appears to have associated mainly with the British, in his case planters and especially, perhaps as an ex-soldier, the military. He had married in 1846, having four children, but his wife died in 1866 (Dittberner 2014). Although there is no evidence of any romantic attachment in his Mauritian *oeuvre*, the *TRSAS* or even in Newton's letters, Pike was quietly getting his fish collection painted by an Englishwoman, Maria Hadley, whom he married in 1874 on his return to America (Dittberner 2014) – dark horse!

Newton, 14 years younger than Pike, was by contrast somewhat of a loner and, meticulous and conscientious, almost a workaholic – in short the ideal bureaucrat. While personally affable, he was not given to much socialising, preferring a small circle of friends with whom to go birding, shooting small game etc. – James Caldwell, Malcy Moon (=de Chazal, talented botanical artist & Caldwell's girlfriend), William Kerr, S. Roch and James Currie feature most often in his letters. He was clearly seen in London as a 'safe pair of hands' in Mauritius, promoted from Assistant Colonial Secretary to Auditor-General in 1863 (Tristram 1897), then to the full post of colonial Secretary in 1869 (*MA*⁷ 1870: 287), and retaining that position until promoted to Lieutenant-Governor of Jamaica in 1877 (Tristram 1897). He married late in life (at 37), in 1869, but lost both wife and shortly afterwards his young son to malaria in 1870 soon after the malady first struck Mauritius. Although initially devastated by his wife's death, he had 4 months later recovered his stiff upper lip to the extent that he barely recorded the second tragedy in his letters home to his brother Alfred, professor

¹ He spelt his name without an 'h', but in the British edition of his book it is spelt 'Nicholas' on the title page.

² i.e. at the symposium held on 13th October 2018 at the Mauritius Commercial Bank HQ, Saint-Jean, Mauritius

³ I made this list of characteristics before finding the following in Dittberner's biography (2014): "he was an enormously curious, energetic, articulate and competent individual, probably gregarious, and a social celebrity and star in mid-19th century Brooklyn, at least among natural scientists..."

⁴ *TRSAS* stands for the *Transactions of the Royal Society of Arts & Sciences of Mauritius*

⁵ See Dittberner (2014) for a list of these activities and achievements, which were far from negligible.

⁶ The original manuscript of this letter was reproduced by Dittberner (2014); at the meeting where the letter was read out, Pike was described in the *procès-verbal* as 'one of the Society's most active and intelligent members' (my translation). Pike is listed as an Honorary Member in the membership list published in *TRSAS* NS 8: 166-168, 1875, though when he was so elected is not clear.

⁷ *MA* is the *Mauritius Almanac*, a government gazette published annually (title sometimes varied).

Fig.1. (left) Nicholas Pike, from the frontispiece of *Subtropical rambles* (Pike 1873).

Fig.2. (above) Sir Edward Newton, from RSAS Centenary volume 1932.

of zoology at Cambridge University: ‘This is but a sad letter to write – I have lost my poor little boy’ – he never mentioned the baby’s name! (Newton 1851-82). In general he comes over in his frequent letters home as a chronic mild depressive, and Governor Arthur Gordon (1894) remarked in 1871 in a letter that “Newton is awfully slovenly; his collar and cuffs are *Vandyked*⁸ by bad washing, and his shirt front has no buttons”, though admittedly he suffered “from frequent attacks of fever, but is, on the whole, in better preservation than his colleagues. He has, however, within the last year, lost both his wife and only child” (Cheke & Hume 2008: 322, note 94). Although happy to occasionally indulge in the elite Mauritian sport of *la chasse*⁹, Newton was an English chauvinist: “Newton is a gentleman, cultivated and agreeable; he is an authority on natural history, but not, I should say on political science. His ‘policy’ is the narrow old one of ‘stamping out’ the French language, French laws, French manners, French religion, thereby making everything English as unpopular as in Wales or Ireland. My policy is just the reverse...” (Gordon 1894); it is clear from other passages in Gordon’s book that Newton, while remaining civil and overtly compliant, opposed Gordon’s initiatives in a passive-aggressive manner – but then as his wife Rachael admitted (Gordon 1894) “They say here of Arthur that ‘he doesn’t *govern*, he *rules*’, so some push-back might have been expected from Newton who in Gordon’s words “has been accustomed to think of himself as a Prime minister, supreme over the administration, and only referring to the Governor in doubtful cases or for a merely formal approval”. He appears to have kept his relations with the Franco-Mauritian elite on a strictly business level, apart from the naturalists of the *Société Royale*, which he joined within months of his arrival on the island¹⁰ – he was present at the séance of 23 January 1860 (*TRSAS NS* 2(1): 147, 1860), elected to the Council in December 1860 (*ibid.* p.158), and the Presidency in January 1869 (Séance annuelle du 26 janvier 1869, *TRSAS NS* 3(2)135), a position he held on and off for the next 8 years. Unlike several of his

⁸ Given jagged edges

⁹ driven deer hunting

¹⁰ There is no complete published record of the meetings of the Royal Society in 1859. Some material appeared in the *Commercial Gazette* (see Staub & Herbereau 2013), but there is no mention of Newton’s admission to the society.

associates¹¹, there is no evidence that Newton was a freemason, and was thus outside one of the then important local social networks.

What was said, what was left out

Having assassinated both their characters, what about their relationship? Firstly their breadth of interests were rather different. Pike, as any reader of *Sub-tropical rambles* will know, dabbled in all aspects of natural history, but his primary love was fish and seaweeds, which he collected and catalogued assiduously (e.g. Gudger 1929 & TRSAS *passim*, 1868-73), and ferns. Arthur Gordon, who clearly had nothing against Pike, and had invited him to join him on a trip to the Seychelles in 1871¹², nonetheless summed him up succinctly, contrasting him with the botanist who was in charge of the Pamplemousses Gardens¹³: “We take with us Pike and Horne for scientific purposes. Col. Pike’s science is very superficial, but he has a large smattering of knowledge on many subjects, Horne’s science is real, but limited strictly to botany” (Gordon 1894).

Newton’s interest was almost exclusively in birds and their eggs, which he documented with a thoroughness unusual at the time, sending specimens home to his brother in Cambridge. He was very much involved in helping George Clark over the discovery and transmission to UK of dodo bones in 1865-6 (Hume *et al.* 2009) and later worked on Rodrigues subfossils (Günther & Newton 1879); he also occasionally took a passing interest in other animals (Newton 1861-82).

We don’t have, in print, any assessment of Newton by Pike, only passing references in his published writings to Newton’s publications or views on a specific bird, as in his account of the Seychelles (Pike 1872). He did however deliberately, possibly pointedly, eschew dodos for the equally extinct and flightless red hen *Aphanapteryx* in the title and preface of his book, and though he rambled right past the Mare aux Songes, on foot and by train, he avoided discussing it¹⁴. Pike spent several days in Mahébourg, consorting with the soldiers of the garrison, but neither mentioned nor visited the by then famous discoverer of dodo bones, local schoolmaster George Clark, the very man who inspired the title of his book¹⁵. There is not a single mention of Newton in *Sub-tropical rambles*, despite other officials and local luminaries featuring throughout. Newton’s letters reveal that he was one of the party on Pike’s second visit to Round Island, accompanied and promoted by his ‘good friend’¹⁶ the Governor Sir Henry Barkly in 1869 (Cheke & Hume 2008: 213), but Pike somehow forgot to mention this in his account (Pike 1873). When we see what Newton thought of Pike, one has to presume the feeling was mutual, though, presumably for political reasons, he praised ‘our Honoured President’ in his farewell letter read to the Society on 27 August 1873 (TRSAS NS 8: 23-24; Dittberner 2014) and thanked him “not alone for the friendly relations between us [!] but for his valuable assistance in my work on Mauritius”.

In print Newton never references Pike at all, though as they wrote on different subjects this is not entirely unexpected. In his letters to his brother (Newton 1861-82¹⁷), however it is a different matter. Perhaps because the intervening letters are missing¹⁸, he is not mentioned at all until 6 May 1869 following Pike’s reading of a paper on his

¹¹ In its listings of officers and officials of all sorts, some issues of *MA* (e.g. 1864, 1865) listed officers of masonic lodges in Mauritius, including several individuals involved with Newton’s ornithological activities, notably F.W.H. Barlow and C.E. Bewsher. Later issues had no such information.

¹² Pike (1872; Cheke & Hume 2008: 323, note 107) says, in his usual florid way, “I had long desired to see this interesting group of islands, and fortune at length favoured my wishes in the shape of an invitation to visit the various Dependencies of Mauritius in HBM Frigate *Forté*” – he did not specify who invited him, but it must have been the Governor.

¹³ The Royal Botanic Gardens, Pamplemousses, since 1988 the Sir Seewoosagur Ramgoolam Botanic Garden (Owadally 1976).

¹⁴ He did however acquire some dodo bones, presented to the American Museum of Natural History, New York: “in 1870 J Carson Brevoort, of this city, presented to the Museum a number of the bones which he had received from Col. Nicholas Pike, the United States Consul at that time at Mauritius” (Parish 2015, quoting the *New York Evening Post* of 18.10.1915).

¹⁵ Pike clearly borrowed his title from Clark’s *A Ramble round Mauritius by a country schoolmaster* (1859). Pike did not date his visit to Mahébourg, so it may have been while Clark was absent, ill, in England during 1869-71 (Hume *et al.* 2009).

¹⁶ That the Governor was considered a ‘good friend’ comes from a lecture in 1889 cited by Dittberner (2014); Pike simply refers to him as ‘my friend’ in a letter to Joseph Hooker dated 18 September 1869 (Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew: Archives, Director’s Correspondence, item KADC3047 - online on JStor). Barkly was Gordon’s predecessor as Governor.

¹⁷ All of Newton’s letters mentioned in this paper are to his brother Alfred, professor of Zoology at Cambridge University 1866-1907 (Anon. 1992: 2174).

¹⁸ Newton’s letter books (copies of outgoing letters) from 4 March 1866 – 10 March 1869 are missing from the Newton Papers in the Cambridge University Library; they were in a despatch box stolen from Newton on a train in Mauritius on 10 March 1869 (letter 10.3.1869).

first visit to Round Island in December 1868 (Séance du 22 Avril 1869; Pike 1870a, revised in Pike 1873), Newton wrote

“The last meeting [of the RSAS] I was at we had a most absurd paper by the American Consul here on ‘Round Island’. I could hardly keep any gravity when he read it – he is *supposed* to be a great naturalist, but is a most awful liar & humbug you ever came across”.

On 1 October the same year he commented that

“Col. Pike the U.S. Consul here is about preparing an elaborate work on this island & is devoting a chapter to the birds. He of course {sent} a most dreadful {number}, but I have tried to help him {.....}¹⁹ as to names. Sir H.B[arkly] is doing the same with his list of ferns. As American Gov^t publish any thing I suppose they will this, & I am anxious that the first list of Mauritian birds should be as correct as possible”.

Apart from some neutral references, for instance a summary account of Pike’s cyclone-lashed enforced stay on Round Island in 1869, he goes quiet until 1871 when Pike goes off with Gordon to the Seychelles:

We have got back General Smyth as our temporary chief, the Governor having gone down to Seychelles with the Admiral who arrived here about a fortnight ago ... Col. Pike too has gone down, but I do not expect they will bring back anything in my line [i.e. birds] worth having. I have posted them up and given Pike written instructions²⁰ as to what he is to do, but he is such a humbug (letter 23.8.1871).

Well, the Governor came back from Seychelles last month, but had done nothing in my way. Colonel Pike got one *Tchitrea corvina* [Seychelles paradise flycatcher], one *Zosterops modesta* [Seychelles grey white-eye] and a *Tinnunculus gracilis* [Seychelles kestrel] but nothing else (letter 19/10/1871).

In fact Pike shot, and thus presumably preserved, a whole lot more birds – *colibris* (sunbirds), merles *Hypsipetes* bulbuls), *paille-en-queues* (tropic birds) and white (=fairy) terns²¹, as well as collecting a whole gamut of other fauna (Pike 1872²²).

In 1872, a word of praise ! – “We [the RSAS] had our exhibition last week, a very poor affair generally, but the natural history section was certainly the best we have ever had. Col. Pike showed a very fine collection of sea weeds from our coasts, many of which were new & nearly all rare ...” (letter 23/8/1872; Pike regularly exhibited – see e.g. TRSAS NS 5), but the following year Newton had a couple of sharp stings in Pike’s tail to add.

At the *séance* of 20 March 1873 Pike announced that his book *Sub-tropical rambles* had just been published in London (TRSAS NS 7:113, 1874). It took a while to reach Mauritius, but on 20 August 1873 Newton wrote:

Colonel Pike’s book came out by the last mail – it is a most awful book as I expected it would be & full of gross lies and excess {print}. The only original points are the account of his own {sociessions} [?associations], all the rest is a compilation from different books. The second volume is to be on Natural History, & part of this may be valuable, though it may be difficult to divide the truth from the fiction. He is going to leave us, he says, for a promotion, but the only American merchant here says he has been recalled for malpractice in regard to the condemnation of ships &c., and I should not be surprised if this history is correct as I believe he is an old scamp.

Particularly interesting of course is the last sentence, suggesting that Pike was recalled for perceived misdeeds in his official work – and so it has proved. An inadequate response to a renegade American whaling captain’s fraudulent activities and cruelty to crew in 1871-72 appears to have been the trigger for his recall (Michel Perrier’s presentation at the symposium, Busch 1994); Pike himself refers obliquely to his problems in a letter to Joseph Hooker Director of the Royal Botanic Gardens at Kew in the UK dated 18 May 1872: “I am sorry to say that for some months my time has been so occupied with official business I have scarcely had a day to devote hunting for fresh specimens”.

In his farewell letter to the Society, mentioned above, read on 27 August 1873, he said that he was about to leave “on a short visit to my native land to see my family” (TRSAS NS 8: 23-24), suggesting he expected to be posted elsewhere – however the ‘short visit’ appears to have lasted the rest of his life (Dittberner 2014). Later, in a letter dated 9 October 1873 to Joseph Hooker, Pike told yet a different story:

¹⁹ Newton’s handwriting is abominable, and some words are illegible; illegible and uncertain words are in curly brackets.

²⁰ ‘instructions as to what he is to do’ is a pretty bossy attitude, which I doubt if Pike would have appreciated!

²¹ Seychelles Sunbird *Nectarinia dussumieri*, Seychelles Merle *Hypsipetes crassirostris*, White-tailed Tropic-bird *Phaethon lepturus*, Fairy Tern *Gygis alba*.

²² summarised in a letter to Joseph Hooker: “I went in for zoology & marine botany and was very successful especially in snakes, lizards, arachnids, birds & their eggs & snail shells both land and marine” (RBG Kew Archives: KADC3052).

My health has been precarious for many months this year. I have been unable to continue my researches for algae & I am now on the point of leaving for the United States and do not intend returning to Mauritius²³.

Finally, on 15 October 1873 we have a last barb:

Colonel Pike is due to leave in a day or so for the U.States. He gave me his chapter on the birds of Mauritius which is to come out in the second volume²⁴ – it will have been quite impossible to correct all his mistakes – the whole thing would require to be rewritten, but I think I have prevented him making more than ordinary blunders, but whether he adopts my corrections is another thing”.

Rival egos – were Newton’s strictures justified ?

Was this bile just personal dislike, or was there a reasonable basis for Newton’s opinions ? I think that it may have started with bruised ego. When Pike, already with a certain reputation as a naturalist, burst onto the island, Newton had already been there seven years, and was an established expert on the birds of the island and well ensconced on the council of the Royal Society. Pike arrived on 12 January 1867 (Pike 1873²⁵), and coincidentally Newton left on home leave, via the Seychelles, on the 18th (Newton 1867), not returning for over a year. Still in UK in February 1868 (Newton 1858-95), he is back in Mauritius by 30 April (Séance du 30 avril 1868, TRSAS NS 3: 109, 1869). In the meantime Pike had impressed members of the society, becoming, for instance, one of the first, in March, to land on Ilot Barkly, freshly emerged in Port Louis harbour after storms in January 1868. Newton now had a more charismatic rival. Gordon reveals how Newton, a few years later, was jealous of his position in the island hierarchy:

The Colonial Secretary is a gentleman, and fairly loyal in carrying out orders he don’t [*sic*] like, but he is tacitly and obstructively an opponent, for he disapproves of me, both as regards my political views and in my estimate of his personal position. He has been accustomed to think of himself as a Prime minister, supreme over the administration, and only referring to the Governor in doubtful cases or for a merely formal approval. This does not suit me ...

As a tranche of letters are missing, we don’t know if Newton commented to his brother about Pike before the report on his first Round Island visit, but there was at least one observation in that report (Pike 1870) that upset him – he added a marginal note in his copy of the *Transactions*²⁶ against Pike’s account of seeing petrels sitting on eggs that “the birds breed in holes of the rocks quite out of sight; he could not see them sitting”; Newton considered he knew all about Round Island, having been there himself in November 1860 (Newton 1861). In retrospect that was an unfair assessment, as Pike had probably encountered the surface-nesting ‘Round Island’ Petrels *Pterodroma arminjoniana* and not the burrowing Wedge-tailed Shearwaters *Puffinus pacificus* that Newton assumed – Newton himself indirectly reporting the former on their 1869 visit (Newton 1861-82, Cheke & Hume 2008).

Pike’s (1871a) article on his first visit to Round Island is indeed full of inaccuracies – the discussion of the lizards has the names all wrong²⁷, and the geology is way off, but unless Newton knew a lot more about lizards and geology than he lets on his letters, why would he find that excruciating ?

Newton commented unfavourably on Pike’s knowledge of birds twice in his letters. Without sight of Pike’s drafts this disparagement is difficult to assess. Apart from the cross-purposes on petrels, there is nothing much in Pike’s mentions of birds in *Sub-tropical rambles* that indicates errors or false observations, though Mynas are misprinted as ‘Nyna birds’ on p.286 and cave swiftlets’ nests are referred to as ‘edible swallow’s-nests’ on p.287, albeit with the correct scientific name. Since both the swallow *Phedina borbonica* and the swift *Collocalia francica* are called *hirondelle* by French-speaking Mauritians, this is hardly a grave mistake in a popular book. In the Seychelles (Pike 1872) he had the male and female *veuves* (‘widows’ = paradise flycatchers ‘*Tchitrea corvina*’) the wrong way round, which suggests he didn’t check the gonads when skinning them, and took the black sex to be female from the name. But

²³ RBG Kew: Archives KADC3054 (online on JStor).

²⁴ This promised second volume, already ‘nearly completed’ in November 1872 according to Pike’s preface in *Sub-tropical rambles* (p.vi), never appeared. In October 1873 he was still confident “My second vol. continues on the Fauna and Flora of Mauritius will I hope be ready for press early in the spring [of 1874]” (letter to J.Hooker 9.10.1873, already cited). ‘Nearly completed’ and ‘ready for press’ were clearly more fancy than fact, as in 1877 he wrote to Louis Bouton explaining that the second book was delayed by difficulty in curating and identifying all his collections of insects and crustaceans, though they were ‘in good hands’ (letter dated 23.9.1877 in RSAS archives, displayed in the Pike Exhibition at the Blue Penny Museum, Port Louis, October 2018). Oddly, neither this letter, nor the list of Mauritian fish which accompanied it, were referred to in the TRSAS of the period. The manuscript of the second volume, if it ever existed, has never surfaced despite searches (Gudger 1929, Dittberner 2014).

²⁵ Not in ‘April 1867’ as claimed by Dittberner (2014).

²⁶ Newton’s set is in the Radcliffe Science Library in Oxford, having been acquired by former Mauritian Government meteorologist and MA editor Albert Walter, who gave them to the library in 1960 (Cheke & Hume 2008).

²⁷ Barkly (1871), discussing the second visit, doesn’t do much better on lizards, but the companion paper by Pike (1871b) this time gets them right.

it is his compiled bird lists that clearly irritated Newton; the second attempt, subsequent to the publication of *Sub-tropical rambles*, still clearly a problem two years after he appears to have corrected an earlier version. In the interval Pike had promised his bird list for publication in the *Transactions* (séance du 21 Octobre 1871, TRSAS NS 6:4, 187²⁸), but he didn't deliver - it never appeared, and there is no copy in the Society's archives (pers. obs. 2008). Although assiduous in documenting his fish, Pike may have been less meticulous when it came to birds, and certainly when making miscellaneous off-the-cuff identifications at Society meetings, he was often wrong, the more experienced Louis Bouton providing the true answer (TRSAS NS vols. 3-7, *passim*).

It should be noted that Newton himself was just as remiss in publishing on Mauritian birds. In his speech at the *Séance annuelle* of 10 October 1874, he said that "For my own part, I may say that I have long been collecting notes on the Avifauna of the Mascarene Islands, and it is my intention, on my next visit to Europe, to work them up into a proper shape" (Newton 1875). He never did²⁹.

Final word – not really a conclusion

'A most awful liar & humbug', and *Sub-tropical rambles* being 'awful' and 'full of gross lies', are pretty grave slanders whatever scientific peccadilloes Pike may have made bird-wise, so must have a deeper origin. No doubt Pike's flowery literary style won't have been to Newton's more sober scientific taste, but again that's not enough to explain the bald accusation of lying, which Newton did not substantiate. I suspect that there must have been an incident relatively early in Pike's time in Mauritius that established him in Newton's mind as a thoroughly dodgy character; an incident possibly known only to him³⁰, as there's no evidence that other members of the *Société Royale*, at least, held any animosity towards him. Indeed they passed a motion at the meeting of 19 November 1873 praising his work and regretting his departure from Mauritius (TRSAS NS 8: 46-47); Newton was not present that day. Pike has to this day retained a place in the *Société's* heart, being belatedly inscribed on the Obélisque Liénard in Pamplemousses Gardens in 1997 (Séance du 9 juillet 1997, PRSAS 7: 125, 2004³¹), an honour not extended to Newton, whose contributions to the knowledge of Mauritian fauna, extant and extinct, if perhaps less visible, match or exceed Pike's³².

In the absence of any further evidence further speculation is futile, but perhaps in some old correspondence surviving amongst Mauritian archives or families, there may be clue to this clash of key personalities in 19th century Mauritian natural history.

Acknowledgements

Access to the Newton Papers in the Cambridge University Library was facilitated by Peter Meadows, and Jean-Marie Huron kindly sent me, via Marie-Josée Martial-Craig of the RSAS, page photos of the TRSAS volume (NS 8, 1875) missing from the Society's CD-Rom (Staub & Herbereau 2014). Geoffrey Summers helpfully sent me copies of Pike's letters to Joseph Hooker.

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- NB: In the text and in the list below PRSAS or TRSAS refers to the *Proceedings or Transactions of the Royal Society of Arts & Sciences of Mauritius*, and MA to the *Mauritius Almanac & Commercial Gazette/Register*.
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²⁸ "Col. Pike has willingly consented to put at the society's disposal his work 'Natural history of birds of Mauritius' to be published in the next *Transactions* of the society".

²⁹ He did eventually publish a summary table of birds in Mauritius, Reunion, Rodrigues & the Seychelles in the context of a talk about extinctions (Newton 1888), but it was nowhere near the comprehensive descriptive work he could have produced from his ample data.

³⁰ As Colonial Secretary he may have had access to privileged information not in the public domain, which he would not have been able to share with the RSAS or even his brother.

³¹ PRSAS = *Proceedings of the Royal Society of Arts & Sciences*, successor to the *Transactions*.

³² His collection of Mauritian birds and their eggs, in Cambridge University's zoology museum, remains the largest in any museum (Cheke & Jones 1987, Table 3). In Mauritius he promoted the first bird protection legislation for land-birds (other than game-birds) anywhere in the world, though it was not enacted until after he left (Cheke & Hume 2008). Although his writings on Mauritius, albeit valuable, are sparse, he made and published important discoveries in the (then) dependencies – Rodrigues and Seychelles, and actively promoted searching for subfossil bones in both Mauritius and Rodrigues (Hume *et al.* 2009, Günther & Newton 1879, Newton & Günther 1893).

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A VISIT TO THE SEYCHELLES ISLANDS

Nicolas Pike

(originally published in the *Transactions of the Royal Society of Arts & Sciences of Mauritius*, New Series 6: 83-142 (1872) and also the *Mauritius Almanac & Colonial Register* for 1873: 74-98)^A

I.

I had long desired to see this interesting group of Islands, and fortune at length favoured my wishes in the shape of an invitation to visit the various Dependencies of Mauritius in H.B.M. Frigate *Forte*. I was requested to be on board punctually by noon on Saturday the 19th August 1871. Duly at that hour I presented myself; bag and baggage, and was received by the Commanding Officer, who informed me that the Flag Lieutenant had given up his berth to me during our cruise. The requisites for our short voyage were soon comfortably stowed away, and all superfluous baggage such as boxes of bottles, &c. and the various appurtenances of a naturalist consigned to the hold for the time; these latter pretty considerable, as it was my intention to collect everything possible during my limited stay connected with the Fauna of Seychelles.

Before all was completed, the shrill whistle of the boatswain was heard and all was bustle and activity to receive H.E. Sir Arthur Gordon who was seen approaching from the shore. Away went the crew of over 500 men, and in a miraculously short time the yards were manned. Rear Admiral Cockburn, who was already on board, stood at the gangway with all his officers in full dress, a file of marines behind them, and all naval etiquette carried out to the letter to receive the Governor. The Barge containing His Excellency, General Smyth¹, Colonel Orme, the Hon. the Colonial Secretary², Mr. Gordon, the Governor's A.D.C. and Private Secretary, and the Harbour Master soon came alongside, when a salute of 17 guns was fired. As the distinguished party mounted the deck, the Marines presented arms, the Band struck up "God save the Queen", and in a few minutes the guests were ushered into the Admiral's State room, where a magnificent Tiffin³ awaited them. The viands were fully discussed, the sparkling vintages of France and Germany circulated freely, and the festive scene lasted for a considerable time. The bows of the Frigate were seaward, and the motion of the Screw began to give warning that it was time for the guests to seek their boats unless they wished to share our voyage. A shake of the hand, kind wishes and good byes were soon exchanged, our friends left, and very soon after the Frigate's berth was vacant. Away we steamed and bid adieu to Port Louis Harbour.

Never were the words "Tis distance lends enchantment to the view" more appropriately used than to Mauritius scenery. Once out of the Harbour, and all that is objectionable in the city fades away, and leaves only the fine outline of the mountain slopes in its back ground, shewing unmistakably their volcanic origin, and telling their own tale of the time when a fiery gulf was within their circle where the city now peacefully rests. As we receded, the grand ranges of the other parts of the Island came into view, and as the shadows of evening fell gradually on their giant cliffs, the effect was magnificent. I gazed at them in admiration till nearly dark, an admiration none the less deep that I had a pleasant personal acquaintance with them all.

On Sunday the weather proved serene and smiling, and by 8 o'clock all were assembled on the quarter deck for morning prayers, (a custom of strict daily occurrence on board the Frigate.) In the forenoon the gun deck was arranged for Service which was admirably conducted by the Revd. Mr Johnson. Many parts were chanted by the midshipmen, and very creditably too, and one of them played on the Harmonium.

The Church Service on board ship has always a peculiar impressiveness for me, the dash of the waves against the vessel's sides giving it an additional solemnity. At such times it is easy to take the splash of the water as a warning

^A This footnote excepted, all footnotes are Pike's, while the endnotes are editorial commentary, mostly identifying species or updating their names, by Anthony Cheke & Justin Gerlach, using personal knowledge and the following reference works; where no scientific name is given it is unchanged from Pike's time; square brackets in the text are also editorial additions:

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note that should "He blow with His winds" that gentle tone would be changed into the furious roar of the angry billows, and that the mightiest hull ever constructed by human hands would be but as chaff before them. I was delighted with the quiet harmony which seemed to pervade the ship, officers and men all in accord, and must say I never spent a happier Sabbath on shore.

On Monday, drilling and the usual routine of duties employed all on board, so I amused myself by throwing out my surface net from one of the Ports. I had been curiously watching a singular red streak on the ocean stretching as far as the eye could reach, and was very desirous for a closer acquaintance with it, as our course lay right through its midst. As we struck the outer edge of it, the streak was not so perceptible as when at a distance. Upon drawing in my net and placing its contents in a clear glass vessel, I found them partly animal and partly vegetable, the former rigid and sinking to the bottom the latter soft and floating. With a good lens I was enabled to separate them, and the rigid masses appeared to be a species of minute crustacea, probably feeding on the plant. This was a minute Alga, and from its peculiar undulatory motion, I presume it to be one of the marine *Oscillatoria* or near it. It is not improbable that it may prove similar to the one mentioned by Harvey as giving the red colour to the Arabian Gulf. He says: This colour is due to the presence of a microscopic Alga (*Trichodesmium erythroëum*) allied to *Oscillatoria*, and endowed with similar motive powers which occasionally permeates the surface-strata of the water in such multitudes as to redden the sea for miles. I carefully preserved specimens of both, in diluted alcohol to transmit to America for scientific examination.

On my voyage from America to Mauritius in the *Monocacy* U.S. Frigate, on the subsidence of a cyclone we met after leaving the Cape of Good Hope, I saw the same phenomenon, but the patches of colour were olive brown, and the Algæ were not so minute as those giving the red colour to this part of the Indian Ocean. The whalers say they often meet with the appearance immediately after a heavy storm. To my surprise I found entangled in the net, one of the curious oceanic insects, belonging to the family of the *Hydromelidæ*⁴ I believe. I have caught one about 25 miles from Port Louis and dozens in the harbour. What it feeds on I know not, but it certainly, minute as it is, lives out on the broad ocean, and from its great rarity at certain seasons, and abundance at others, would appear to approach the shore for the purpose of propagation. It is a marvel to see these little dots bobbing about just on the crests of the waves, and when pursued dive down through them. There are two species I have taken at Port Louis, and this resembled one of them, grey with a white abdomen, a black line on the back. Both kinds are diamond shaped, with large prominent eyes, shaggy thighs, very long hind and short fore legs, the antennæ and palpa resembling a spider. The little creature was so active and sprang about with such celerity I had a difficulty in securing him after he got his feet clear of the net. I have watched these insects often very closely, but have never been able to discover what changes they undergo, and I believe nothing is as yet known of their habits by the scientific world.

The sperm whales (*Catodon polycyphas* I believe⁵) are very abundant in this ocean and we several times saw them quite close to the bows of the Frigate, though the vessel's rapidly cleaving the waves seemed to startle them.

On Tuesday about 3 P.M. we sighted Agalega, but it lies so low, it is not observed till near. We ran within two miles of it, hove to, and fired a gun, but saw no signs of houses or people. The sea was breaking roughly over the coral reefs which nearly surround this Island and extend some distance from the shore; so we did not land, which I much regretted, for I wished to obtain some of the wild partridges, guinea fowls and peacocks⁶ said to be native there as well as other things of great interest to me.

Agalega is 11 miles long and entirely of coral formation, and has been in fact two islands, the channel between having been so nearly filled in, that at low water it can be crossed on foot. There are a few houses here but we passed to the W. so did not see them, and *filios*⁷ and cocoa-nut trees appear very numerous.

After leaving Agalega, we came to some extensive Banks when soundings were taken front 29 to 35 fathoms. The armature of the lead was, at my request furnished me. On close examination of it after my return to Mauritius, I found it to consist entirely of coral debris and Foraminiferous shells. The latter requiring a high power of the microscope to develop them at all. My instrument only enabled me to see that they were shells, but not strong enough to distinguish them, so I have carefully preserved the whole to send home.

These delicate shells exist in all the warm seas in the world, and those who have never seen them may form some idea of their minute size, when it is stated that "four hundred thousand of them have been found in forty six grains Troy of sand." Yet minute as they are surely and steadily are they filling up the depths of the ocean. The great Atlantic Telegraph plateau is a bank formed of the dead shells of the Foraminifera. The Indian Ocean also swarms with them. I have been informed by the captains of our whalers that on the Saya de Mala bank somewhat to the Eastward, they have found soundings, in five fathoms. Near this is a noted whaling ground, and some of the old sailors who have cruised there many years, tell me the bank is gradually rising, and the day is not far distant when the sea will break over it, and another and dangerous reef be added to the perils of this Ocean. It is supposed these Foraminifera feed on the Infusoria which they have the power of electrifying or paralysing by some hidden electric capacity. Thus, these, "The smallest and most microscopic of animals in existence, are un pitying flesh eaters, and become formidable destroyers by means of a homoeopathic dose of poison.

We constantly saw Frigate birds and others flying to Agalega from the sea to rest for the night, and two species of *Paille-en-queue* or Tropic bird. This evening a Booby alighted on the main boom, and one of the sailors crept cautiously along it and caught it for me⁸. We were steaming and sailing along at the rate of 10 knots, the ship rolling much, and for a change the waves dashed on to the poop deck where we were walking. We retired to the gun deck to chat and smoke but old Neptune tried hard to put our pipes out, by sending his emissaries thundering in through the ports and we all had to be spry to escape a ducking.

Wednesday was showery but I tried my net again and I fished up some of those singular Pteropodous Molluscs, the *Hyalea globulosa* (Rang)⁹. They were in great numbers but darted away with such swiftness that it was with difficulty I succeeded in capturing them. This rapidity, with the quick flap of the butterfly shaped fins (if one can so call them) gives them a peculiar motion in the water, and is a distinguishing mark of the *Hyalea*. As soon as caught they draw in the flappers, and they require most delicate handling not to crush the fragile bluish brown shells. Some of the genera of these Pteropoda form the principal food of the Right Whale of the northern seas, where they are in such myriads as to colour the water, and wherever they appear the whalers look out sharply for their monster cetacean prey.

On Thursday our last day on board, the men were drilled with the Schneider rifle, and exercised in fencing, and working the heavy guns. The general physique of the men was fine as any I ever saw, and they handled their guns admirably. I could not help thinking as I watched them, that if all Her Majesty's Men of War are conducted as this is, and all her Officers and men of such moral and physical calibre as those of the *Forte*, she has little indeed to fear from a foreign foe. I can only believe that the writer of the "Battle of Dorking"¹⁰ can know little of the real character of England's hearts of oak, or such a myth would never have originated in his brains.

Towards noon we sighted Mahé and could see most of the group of the Seychelles. Towards 3 p.m. we neared the Island and it appeared like a single mountain, wooded from shore to summit. On a nearer approach after passing St-Ann's and Ile aux Cerfs, the grand outlines of the precipitous Mt. Peaks began to stand out in bold relief from the forests. As we neared the roadstead a pilot put off to us, but we hailed him and declined his services. The above Islands are very picturesque as seen from the ship. Covered with dense foliage the vivid greens of those near the water's edge, contrasted with the sombre olive of the background and presented a brilliant picture, grateful to our eyes even after so short a voyage.

On rounding the Island Port Victoria came into view, and we dropped our anchor in the inner harbour about 5 p. m. In a short time a boat put off showing the English ensign, and Mr Franklyn the Civil Commissioner, Dr Brookes the Health Officer, and Mr Vaudin the English Minister soon boarded us after the usual inquiries pratique was given, and they returned to the shore, Mr Gordon accompanying them, to make preparations for the official landing on the morrow.

We found in the harbour the French corvette *Surprise* of 4 guns, Captain Thierry, and a small Arabian man of war. Officers from both ships soon made their appearance and apologized for not saluting, as they had not sufficient guns. The American whale ship *Herald* lay astern of us and she soon run up her Stars and Stripes. I was greatly pleased watching the men of the *Forte* heaving the anchor short at the Capstan, all keeping regular time to the lively airs played by the Band, such as "Champagne Charley", "Sally in our alley", "Tom Bowline", and other favourite nautical ditties. In the evening the Admiral gave a dinner on board the *Forte* and several ladies and gentlemen from shore were present.

II.

The morning of Friday the 25th August was bright and clear, and the crystal waters of the Bay of Mahé were smooth as a mirror. The town of Victoria could be distinctly seen from the Frigate, and as I gazed on the grand outlines of mountain and forest on the island, I was already revelling in the anticipation of pleasant hours spent in exploring the one and climbing the other. As it was understood that His Excellency was to land this day, I concluded to go ashore as soon as breakfast was over, in order to note everything there was to be seen, which I accordingly did.

About 8 o'clock a steam barge left the ship with two field pieces and a squad of sailors, and when I landed I saw them hauling the guns along the Chaussée in true military style. I found the town in a perfect ferment of bustle and excitement. Many planters had come in from the country with their families, and others from the neighbouring islands; all were dressed in their Sunday's best, especially the ladies and children, and all looked eager and happy. From an early hour the Chaussée was crowded with people ready to welcome Her Majesty's Representative. Towards noon a State Barge was prepared and as His Excellency left the Frigate, the yards were manned and a salute of 17 guns announced his departure, the echoes reverberating along the old granite hills carrying the news to the very depths of the forest: Every vessel, down to the smallest craft in the harbour displayed bunting in any quantity. Numerous plying boats were filled with spectators eagerly watching the Barge that bore the Mauritius flag for the first time out of Port Louis. At the landing place a group of gentlemen waited to receive His Excellency and offer him the customary official greetings. As the Governor set foot on shore, the above mentioned field pieces at the opposite end of the Chaussée thundered out a second salute of 17 guns. The bells of the Churches clanged forth a welcome, taken up by the ready tongues of the assembled multitude, "welcome, welcome to our Governor." He was received by Mr Commissioner Franklin, and I presume with the usual complimentary speech, but I was not near enough to catch it.

His Excellency passed up the Chaussée under an arch of evergreens which had been run up rapidly at the last moment, but in spite of haste it was very tastefully arranged. On each side of the Chaussée stood the boys and girls belonging to the various schools. The Catholics attended by the *Frères* and *Soeurs*, and the Protestant by their Teachers. His Excellency appeared greatly pleased at this and spoke a few words to each School as he passed. It was a very interesting sight, for the children were all neatly dressed and well behaved, and their bright faces showed their enjoyment of their fête.

On arriving at Government House, a number of Planters were in the Avenue leading to it, and H.E. addressed them. He stated the object of his visit, and his wish that all matters might be satisfactorily arranged where redress was needed, and invited them to call on him at Government House, that he might make himself fully acquainted with all

questions relative to the welfare and progress of the Islands, and in answer, a lusty cheer rose from all present. In the avenue was a second triumphal arch with two flag-staffs displaying the English and American Ensigns. At Government House a tiffin was prepared, of which His Excellency and many of the principal Planters partook. As soon as the bustle of the procession had subsided I began to look about me and inspect the town. Victoria was formerly called 'L'Établissement', but by special permission was named after Her Majesty in 1841. It lies on the S.W. of Mahé on a plateau between the base of the Trois Frères Mountain and the sea. Nearly the whole of the houses are of wood, and few of more than one storey. All the streets are short, narrow and slope to the sea. A profusion of fine flowers and trees flourish here, but I cannot say much for the order and arrangement of the gardens. It has two great advantages over Port Louis. The streams that flow through it to the sea are clean, not the filthy water courses offensive to the eyes and noses of the inhabitants of the city, as well as detrimental to the general health, and thus the harbour of Mahé avoids the pollution so fatal to that of Port Louis. Then again, the Seychellois wisely plant trees in their streets (instead of chopping them down) and I need hardly say how grateful is the shade of a Palm or *Badamier*¹¹ to the pedestrian, if only for a few moments' rest.

There are two sacred edifices, Catholic and Protestant. The Court House, Post Office and other public buildings have a general *tropical character*, i. e. rather shaky and time worn. They are erecting a new Custom House, which when completed, will be a vast improvement on the old tumble down affair which has hitherto served as *Douane*. Government House stands on a slight elevation and resembles an old fashioned country farm house; but it is embellished with fine trees and there are pretty walks about the grounds. In front is a very fair specimen of the *Coco de mer*¹², but inferior in size and beauty to those of Praslin. The Cemetery struck me as very singular. It was I believe during the occupation of the French the "Jardin du Roi," and was planted with fine spice and other trees, now it does duty for a mightier being. It is on a steep slope near Government House, but the graves are so little protected that after heavy rains, some of them must be entirely laid bare.

Near the Cemetery is the Mausoleum of the Chevalier Quéau de Quincy, Military Commandant under the French Republic. He was Governor of the Seychelles in 1794 when Commodore Newcome in the *Orpheus* accompanied by other vessels of war, entered the Bay and demanded the surrender of the place, giving De Quincy an hour's time to decide. Finding himself in a pretty considerable fix, he wisely complied with the demand; and the old and distinguished Officer was allowed to capitulate with all the honors of war. It would appear that he soon won the respect of his conqueror. The Commodore not being able to leave men enough to occupy the place, actually proposed to De Quincy to accept the post of Governor under the new Regime, which he did, and kept loyally to his compact. The French however did not give up all claim to the Islands so summarily wrested from them. In 1801 after the attempt to assassinate the First Consul, 71 of the conspirators were banished to Mahé, but with very few exceptions they all perished, no provision being made for them by the French Government. Some descendants of these few are still living. It was only in 1814 that these islands were formally ceded to Britain.

There is a good Hospital just outside the town. It is constructed of sawn blocks of coral procured from the reefs, and strange to say, the usual discoloration by the action of the elements on coral has not yet taken place, the blocks being still as white as snow. The Bay of Mahé is about 4 miles in extent, and capable of containing over 100 vessels. The entrance is however so intricate as to render it almost impossible for a stranger to enter it at night, and even in the day time it requires a good pilot. Mr Franklin has recently laid down a number of Buoys to assist navigation in the tortuous channel. Many little islets dot the Bay and from the *chaussée* can be seen the chain of islands encircling it, except on the N. and forming a natural breakwater. This archipelago consists of 29 islands situated between Lat. 3° 33' to 5° 45' S. and Long. 55° 15' to 50° 10' E. and lie at a distance of over 900 miles from Mauritius. Their authentic history commenced in 1742 when they were discovered by Capt. Picault of the *Elizabeth* who was cruising in those seas by the order of the Mauritian Governor Labourdonnais. The group was then named after him and the largest called Mahé, but later their appellation was changed to Les Seychelles, after Vicomte Hérault de Seychelles.

These islands must have been known very early, probably to the Phoenicians who were constantly trading up and down the African coast. There is certain evidence of their being known to the Arabs, as in the Ile du Nord Arabic inscriptions have been found cut on the rocks. It is not improbable that the Arabs of the E. coast of Africa made them a refuge in their piratical expeditions. Who knows what horrid tragedies may have been enacted amongst the lovely scenery of this archipelago, equally dark and blood stained with those perpetrated by the Buccaneers of the West. A short time ago, on cutting down a large "Bois Blanc" in the forest at Mahé an arrow head of hard black wood was found embedded in its heart. It must have lain there for ages as the surrounding wood was quite discolored, and the wound was so perfectly closed that the arrow was only discovered on sawing the tree into planks¹³. It is not improbable that the Arabs of the Zanzibar coast would man their boats with slaves from the natives tribes N. of the Lupata Mounts, many of which are skilled in the use of this primitive weapon, which is often used for killing birds.

The second day after my arrival I hired a pirogue and proceeded to make acquaintance with the coral reefs in the Bay, which had about a foot of water on them at the time of my visit, and are never quite exposed they tell me. I found the corals very similar to those at Mauritius. The blocks of *Astræas* and *Porites* are immense, and they are sawn into shape and used for building, being more easily worked than the hard granite of the mountains.

Lying loose on them I found fine heads of live *Meandrinæ*, the *Gracilis* and others, their polyps of a lustrous green, and various small *Astroæas* of all shades of green and brown. The beautiful silver grey *Poecillipora elongata* so rare at Mauritius was here abundant and covered with *serpulas*, many of their animals of the brightest scarlet. I found some pieces of a *Poecillopora* near the *elongata* quite new to me, but all dead. The fine rose tinted *P. coespitosa* was

plentiful, its square fairy cups filled with a snow white polyp. There were large pieces of dead *P. verrucosa* so much sought for by the coral vendors for bleaching as the branches are solid as well as elegant, unlike the fragile *Madrepora alcornonis* which breaks at a touch. I saw a great deal of it, but mostly broken. The tips are of delicate blue, and the vendors often colour this and other corals to imitate nature, an imitation that looks as if it had been dipped in a blue bag!

Like loveliest gems lay the pink and lilac tipped *Madrepora alirantanoides*^B, their cups resembling exquisite lace work. Fungi from the size of a crown piece to a platter lay all about, and numbers of other corals some well known and others new to me. Sporting amongst these treasures of Ocean were innumerable fish their scaly sides showing combinations of colour so marvellous that when drawn they appear impossibilities, or would do so had we not daily verifying proof in our fish market. I was surprised at the scarcity of *Echinas* [sea-urchins], star fish etc. but crabs of all sizes and hues were abundant, scrambling and scampering about the rocks, and hiding in the crevices when disturbed with a celerity defying capture. I detached a tube of a large and curious *Tubicolous Annelide*, the elegant arborescent appendages brilliantly tinted with violet, yellow and red. These tentacles which form the respirating apparatus of the animal are drawn in instantaneously at a touch, the quickest case of collapse I know; though how he tucks in the large feathery head and his stiff body into the comparatively small case is a wonder—but once his door is shut by thick fleshy filaments, and so closely, that it is only when death takes place and they relax their hold that the creature slips out of his house. The tentacles were nearly three inches in length over 60 in number and when extended they equalled in beauty any Passion flower that ever grew. The case though rough and unsightly out-side, is lined with a substance as soft and shiny as brown satin. It preserved so well in alcohol that it is now on its way across another ocean with numbers of other curiosities to excite the admiration of scientific men at home.

The reefs appear to be making in rapidly just as they are in Mahébourg Bay. The formation of the actual reef coral, as is well known is of the slowest possible, yet the light surface corals are of rapid growth and the coral debris brought in by every dash of the waves, counts for much in the course of a year. How long a time has elapsed since the foundation of those reefs was laid who can tell? The fellows sawing up the giant blocks little thought of the tiny architects of the ponderous masses. According to the scientific calculations, I should think the first polyp must have begun his work somewhere about the time when man had arrived at a few stages from his original Ascidian state, of Darwinian notoriety.

III.

On Monday the 28th I rose very early in order to enjoy a long walk before the oppressive heat of the day set in. I took the road North of the town, which makes along the shore for a distance of about 5 miles. The fine road was I believe commenced under the administration of the Hon. S. Ward, and is still being carried on by Mr Commissioner Franklin.

After leaving my residence I came to a number of large Turtle pounds on the right of the road, which are in fact inlets from the Bay, and the tide ebbs and flows in them. The flesh of the [Green] Turtle forms the 'Beef' of these Islands, and is in great demand. I paused to watch the capture of some by several stout Mozambiques. One of the fellows who seemed to be quite an expert, having selected a fine large one, cleverly caught it by one of its flippers and managed to turn it on its back, and then dragged it to shore. Some of his comrades at once seized it and soon lifted it to a sort of wooden barrow still on its back. Four of them then shouldered the barrow and carried the turtle off to market to be cut up for sale.

I would here mention that my friend the Hon. S. Ward has kindly given me the use of the copious notes he made on all subjects connected with the Seychelles during the time he was Civil Commissioner there. They are full of valuable information and I willingly avail myself of it. My time there was so limited I am glad to be able to supplement my own observations with *facts* from so able a source.

The Green Turtle (*Chelonia viridis*) and the Hawksbill Turtle (*Caretta imbricata*)¹⁴ both abound in these seas, but from their reckless destruction, their numbers are gradually lessening. The former, of Aldermanic repute, grows to a great size, but its shell, with the exception of the centre plate called "*Caouane*" is worthless. This is used for common veneering, and it takes 3 turtles to give a pound of it, yet, every year large numbers are sacrificed to procure it. In 1862, 600 pounds of "*Caouane*" were exported for which 1800 turtles must have been destroyed, giving an average of 490,000 lbs. of weight good eatable flesh wasted and left to rot on the beach.

The valuable Tortoise shell of commerce is procured from the Hawksbill. Some are speared as they lie floating on the water, with an instrument like a sharp spike nail attached to a long stick. When struck with this spear the air rushes in under the carapace and prevents the animal from sinking, thus facilitating its capture. Others are caught when they come on shore to lay their eggs, as they only require to be turned on their backs to secure them. They come on shore at night and dig a hole 3 or 4 feet deep in the sand with their flippers, and therein deposit their eggs, afterwards so carefully covering them that it is only an expert can find them. Before I left Mahé, I saw one of my country men unearth a nest which had over a hundred eggs in, and he took them and buried them near his house in an enclosure that he might get them when hatched, at which period the turtle is considered a great delicacy. When they leave the eggs, they have only a soft shell and many perish from the attacks of birds as they seek the sea, which instinct teaches them to do, as soon as hatched. There they meet a still more formidable foe in the numerous sharks, but with all this they propagate very rapidly. When a full grown turtle is attacked by a shark, it defends itself by turning its flippers over the back, thus

^B I use the word *Corals* in the ordinary acceptation to save a repetition of scientific words; of course it is well known Madrepores and others are not true Corals.

leaving nothing to lay hold of, but if speared and trying to escape, the flippers are instantly nipped off by the savage brute.

After killing the turtles, the upper part of the carapace is taken off; a hole is dug in the sand and a fire made in it, over which is placed the hollow carapace, and this is completely covered with wet sea weed; when the steam soon separates the laminae, or outer plates, the only part used for commerce. The turtles of the Atlantic feed in a great measure on the *Zostera marina* or Marine grass, but I saw none of it here, though so abundant in Mauritius. Their food appears to be principally a species of *Sargassum* which is in great abundance.

After passing the Hospital I came to a fine bridge constructed in Mr. Wards' time. It spans a deep ravine and I passed to admire the rich vegetation clothing the banks of the crystal stream that was quietly finding its way to the sea. There were clumps of the feathery Bamboo over 40 feet in height, that at once stamp the character and give such elegance to Tropical scenery, they bent gracefully over the profusion of ferns, flowers, and grasses, whispering, who knows what of Nature's secrets, in their soft creaking tones, to the lesser, yet still lovely denizens of the wilds at their feet. Beautiful green lizards¹⁵ were playing hide and seek on the Bamboos, or patiently waiting for the unwary insects that should venture within reach. I wished for my camera to be able to carry away some tangible souvenir of the scene, but "There were forms so various, that no powers of art, The pencil or the pen, may trace the scene!"

I met many Mozambique men and women, sauntering along the road, most of them going to work in the town. One of them had a curious musical instrument on which he was playing. It was called a fiddle, but certainly did not resemble one, nor was a bow used on it. It consisted of a straight piece of wood, with 3 or 4 niches cut in one end, which served the same purpose as the frets of a guitar. Half a large gourd was affixed to it as a sounding board, and the hollow side is held against the breast when played. Two Banana fibre strings were fastened at one end and then tight drawn and secured on the niches. They were struck with the fingers of the right hand, and the thumb of the left assisted. The music was plaintive, but not unpleasant although in a minor key. These people all looked very happy and contented and were not apparently in any hurry to get to their work however industrious they may be when at it, though that I take to be very doubtful.

Some distance further I came to another brook and bridge, and passed under instead of over the latter in search of curios. I there for the first time saw those singular animals called the "Jumping fish," *Periophthalmum koelreuteri*¹⁶. I at first took them to be Lizards, for they live as much out of the water as in it, taking life easily by sunning themselves on the roots of old trees or on stones. They are very quick, and when frightened dart into the water skimming its surface more like a bird than a fish, I was a long while before I succeeded in catching one and though his fins are bright yellow and grey, his coat is homely and the two eyes close together at the top of the head give him an evil look. The large pectoral fins have at their base strong muscles, and can be lowered and by help of them and the ventrals, the fish can move rapidly when out of the water in humid places. Its prey is said to be terrestrial insects which it leaves the water to hunt, and it is found both in rivers and on the sea beach.

I have seen stone broken in many parts of the world, but here I found quite a novel method at least to me. I came upon a large fire of coco fibres, and asked what such an amount of good fuel was being wasted for. I was answered that it was to crack the granite rocks, that are so hard that ordinary drills will not pierce the great boulders, so recourse is had to heat to split them. The sun was now just rising from his watery bed, the sky cloudless:

"The eastern gate, all fiery red,
Opening on Neptune with fair blessed beams,
Turns into yellow gold, his salt-green streams."

I wandered up a narrow path through the bushes towards the high lands with a view to gain the top of the mountain. I soon entered a large grove of Cashew trees (*Anacardium occidentale*) then laden with fruit and in many places it was strewn all over the ground. I noticed that the natives who saw me eat them shook their heads, and they told me they were not good to eat, but the cashew being an old acquaintance of mine I did not heed them. It was astonishing to me that this beautiful tree should be so neglected. It is in many respects a valuable one and grows luxuriantly in most all land below 1000 ft. When in Fernambuco some years since I attended an Exhibition and saw a quantity of wine made from the Cashew, and the Governor informed me, that in the following year it was expected that enough would be made to export to Europe and America, and he hoped soon it would form an important item in the products of the country. It was well flavoured, far nicer than most of the Australian wine, I have tasted. The nut is good for desert, and capital when roasted. It is said also that they make a delicious pickle, only to be known to be appreciated, and the wood is useful for furniture. I have seen a fine side board made from it, so it would prove as serviceable as a cocoanut tree if cultivated and looked after. Many acres waste land could be easily planted with it, as everything grows so luxuriantly in this Island. The soil is composed of degraded granite and vegetable mould and in the flatland near the sea is in most parts very rich. A little patch of creole rice was growing where I stopped to rest, and I was told it yielded largely and was very profitable, and to judge from appearance it was as fine as any I ever saw. Why all the various articles of culture which have been proved such a success here are now so neglected is a marvel. From cotton alone large fortune are said to have been made I was informed one proprietor having remitted to France £ 70,000 all drawn from his cotton plantations, (put it down at francs and I should think it nearer the mark.) Any way cotton of most superior growth thrives here equal to the best sea Island, in silkiness and length of fibre. The peculiar soil and climate are admirably suited to it. How much might not such a country produce! but from the present state of things it appears that little trouble is taken to make the most of the goods so lavishly provided. The indomitable *laissez-aller* of tropical climates evidently prevails here.

As I proceeded up the mountain, I came to some clumps of Jamrosas¹⁷ and wild Guavas. The shade was grateful for the heat was very great. I had long known that the Jamrosa is the favorite food of the Leaf fly (*Phyllium Siccifolium*)¹⁸, and its branches their especial habitat, so soon commenced a vigorous search for them. The peculiar dress nature has bestowed on them, enables them well to elude the pursuit of the uninitiated. In form they imitate various leaves, and the veining of the wings keeps up the resemblance, and at different stages the shade of green changes. Some grow to over three inches in length, and all have curious leaf like expansions on the legs. They hide on the under side of leaves, and it was sometime before I succeeded in finding any. When disturbed, they have a peculiar way of doubling themselves up, so that the illusion continues for they are then like little crumpled up leaflets. The eggs resemble a brown seed Carambole form, and are very numerous. Those I found were under a loose piece of bark in the crevice of a Jamrosa. Crawling on this tree I saw insects of all ages and sizes, some only a quarter of an inch long. I brought some away with me as they bear confinement well, and eat voraciously, but many came to an untimely end as their enemy, the small red ant, found them out, and made a meal of them. On some of the trees I saw the nests of a *Caria* or Termite, similar to those in Mauritius but the ants are, I believe, different. They are black and very active and bite like the mischief¹⁹.

There were also those curious slowgoers, yet marvellously wide-awake little animals the Chameleons²⁰, but not amongst the dead leaves as I found them in the Cape, but crawling up the grasses and bushes. This I am told, is not its favourite haunt, but on the Bamboos, where it is more active and at home than elsewhere. They are very tame and will pursue their prey in a window just as well as in the bush. The eye is on the ball and socket principle, and the creature has the power of turning one completely round while the other is stationary. This power is of the greatest use to it in catching its prey. When lying apparently asleep, from its utter quietude of manner, if closely examined, one eye will be found turned a little behind the other, and the small pupils scanning every point before and behind. Should any fly or other insect come within its range of vision, it quietly collects itself into marching order, but so stealthily the movement is almost imperceptible, and when within what it conceives to be an accurate range, out shoots the long tongue, and it is not often it misses. If it does, it at once drops into quiescence and waits patiently its next chance. The Chameleon is very harmless, but can be excited to anger by rubbing on the back when it will open its mouth, a great yellow cavern, and puff itself out with a hissing sound, but I never saw it attempt to bite. It changes its colours according to the substance it is on, and when angry becomes very dark. At night it is perfectly white, and it then curls itself up and sleeps till the first streak of light wakes it to hunt for prey. Its foot consists of two prehensile toes without any claws, and its movement is peculiar as it often makes several attempts before it puts the foot down, a precautionary measure to secure a firm foothold I presume.

After considerable mounting I came to a sort of plateau where was a clean looking hut, and behind it rose a giant granite cliff showing a straight inaccessible face, utterly precluding my further progress. I saw a woman and some children, and a little boy brought me out a bench and placed it under a bread fruit tree; my hot and wearied look I suppose touching the woman's kindly nature, and I was but too glad of a rest. She made me understand her husband was a fisherman and that even then he was on his way home up the mountain. He very soon put in an appearance, and when he saw me he welcomed me in English, as he told me he had served in an American whaler. He at once offered to get me some coconuts, and his wife busied herself to prepare me some bread fruit she had been roasting in ashes for her husband, very good I found it the first time I had tasted this delicious fruit cooked in this manner, and the coconut milk was most refreshing after my climb. My visit seemed to make quite a small excitement. The man now told me his history, a simple one enough, his father was a Mozambique slave, and he himself had tried all sorts of employments, but having made some money whaling, he had settled down on this mountain, and cultivated a little patch of ground. Some *patates*²¹, rice, etc., forming nearly all his wealth, with some fowls that lived mostly by their wits and scraped a livelihood in the bushes. He told me that formerly he had planted tobacco and made some profit by it, but now it was so heavily taxed he was obliged to abandon it. He might have done it on the sly, but he said his priest who was a good man, told him not to do so, not to break the laws, so he obeyed, but found it very hard. He eked out a living by fishing, and thus helped the daily larder. I filled my pipe with some capital tobacco grown in the island, and as it is very possible by far the greater number of those who use the "weed" in Mauritius know nothing of its culture, I will give a slight summary of it.

As soon as the plant shows flower every bud and small shoot on the base of the stem must be picked off each plant, and this every 24 hours. By doing so the leaves acquire great breadth and all the vigour of the plant. When fit to cut, which is proved by the thick, spotty appearance of the leaf and a gummy secretion on it of a brown colour, it is taken off about three inches from the ground, and laid in the sun for about a quarter of an hour, and then hung up to await its final preparation of having the veins of the leaves extracted. All injured ones are laid aside, and the good are rolled up tightly into "carottes" and bound together by being placed in a portion of the heart leaves of a palm, and tied up very carefully with plaited aloe fibre. If this ligature is always tight the tobacco will preserve a very long time, but if it becomes loose and is exposed to the air it soon moulds. It appears to me a great pity the Government has thought proper to put such a heavy tax on the cultivation of tobacco, as it deters the small landed proprietors from a more profitable culture than canes for them, both here and in Mauritius.

The man showed me a musical instrument called, as well as I could make out, a "Bobre." It is just the form of a bow and about its size. The string is played with the back of the fingers of the left hand, and struck with the right by a little stick about a foot long, on which is tied at the end a bundle of small pebbles that rattle as it touches the string. He played some merry tune on it and all the children danced to it, even the mother figuring in at times. I saw many of the

pretty little white sea birds *Sterna Alba*²² hovering over head, and they told me their nests and those of the *Paille-en-queue*²³ were so well known, that one little fellow started off and brought me presently what I should have taken for a lady's large powder puff, but from old acquaintance, I knew better. The tropic birds (*Phaeton candida*) only lay a solitary egg, and for some time after it is hatched it is like nothing but a ball of down, I must not forget it has a beak in it, for the little savage-can nip sharply, and not all backward to do it, and screeches horridly when disturbed. As it was precisely the same as those I have had so many of in Port Louis I sent it back to the parent bird, who doubtless bewailing its loss. A nice time she must have of it, when *Pater familias* has flown away to fetch food from the sea, for when hungry it screams till its hunger is appeased, and until it is satisfied and the mother, Papa must wait, and even go supperless if he has brought short allowance. Their principal food is a kind of *Sepia* or *Ourite* called *Loligo*²⁴, which is abundant in these seas.

When I was thoroughly rested, and rose to go, the man offered to show me a short cut down the mountain. Wild pineapples were growing up to the path, with a bright red flower, but none of the fruit was ripe. We met a man with a covered basket, and when he saw me he took off the leaves and presented me with a handful of fine cashew nuts, and I found them so good I bought his basket full which he carried for me down to my quarters, and relieved me of some of my load of ferns and boxes and bottles, for I had secured a good collection of insects on the way. It was nearly noon when I got back, the heat quite oppressive, but it did not prevent my enjoying a very hearty breakfast, and I spent the rest of the day in arranging all my treasures.

V

I received a special invitation to visit Recife and Frigate islands in the French Corvette *Surprise*, capt. Thierry, (mentioned in a former letter). I went down to the pier early morning and being ahead of the party took the opportunity of examining this really fine construction. I met Mr Chalmers, the Superintendent of part of the work, and he promised me some written details of it, a promise he fulfilled later. Never was anything in Seychelles erected with such celerity and not alone with speed but well done into the bargain. Here is positive proof that the Seychellois can work well, and let us hope that this may be the beginning of improvements essential to the interests of the place. When this pier is built it is expected that goods may be landed or shipped with facility, whatever be the state of the tide, a matter hitherto difficult and oft times impossible. The pier was commenced during the administration of Mr Ward, but only 100 feet were completed, circumstances preventing its continuation. In March 1870, it was recommenced and on the 21st September 1871 it was advanced to 1750 feet, It has been entirely done under the personal superintendance of Mr Commissioner Franklin.

The mountains and the ocean have contributed to this admirable sea wall. The former has supplied its everlasting granite for the side walls, which are about 8½ feet high; the latter has rendered up its mysteriously wrought corals to fill to the centre, thus aiding man in forming a barrier, firm enough to withstand the attacks of its boisterous waves. The breadth of the pier is about 20 feet, and it is intended to carry it on to a length of 3,600 feet.

On the 28th August 1871 a tramway was begun and by the 21st September, 1,600 feet were completed and trucks working on it. There is a crane at the upper end to lift goods from the trucks to the new Custom-House, and it is proposed to erect a second at the point of the pier, to lift cargo from ships or lighters into the trucks. The Tramway, Trucks and Crane were sent from the Mauritius Railway, and up to this period have cost about £500. The whole of this part of the work has been superintended by Mr Chalmers who went from Mauritius for that purpose, and infinite credit it does him.

By the time I had well inspected the place all were assembled and soon on board. The Corvette had her steam up ready to start, and quickly slipped her cable from the Buoy and threaded the intricate channel. It was a glorious morning overhead, but with such a heavy swell on the sea that made walking on deck anything but comfortable for a landsman, to say nothing of the tribute exacted by Neptune from some of the party. This latter, I was happily exempt from, and could enjoy the exhilarating scene. Words fail me to give any adequate idea of the loveliness of the view of these islands from the sea; wherever one gazed the eye took in such exquisite picture as will remain for life impressed on my mind, vividly to be recalled whenever I think of the Seychelles. Whole schools of Albacore²⁵ followed the ship, cutting rapidly through the waves and sheaving their fins out of water. The Executive Officer threw out a line, and in a few minutes the bait was greedily caught, and soon a fine fellow lay on the deck. He was done justice to by the cook for breakfast at a later hour. When we had steamed out about three quarters of an hour the whole group of Islands came into view. Not long after we came to Ile Recife and held up steam to leeward of it. It is only at certain times boats can land at this little island, but we determined to try if we might be of the favoured ones. A whale boat was lowered with 8 men in her, and with two of the midshipmen from the *Forte* and myself we set off to make an attempt to land. We got close to the breakers, when a person on shore signalled to us to go back as it was impossible a boat could live in the sea then running, and very reluctantly we returned to the ship, which was not done without some trouble on account of the strong current, and the waves curling all round us.

This island is leased to a person from Mauritius who reaps a profit from the eggs collected there and sold at Mahé. It is astonishing to see the immense numbers of black birds hovering over it, the *Anous stolidus*²⁶. It resembled a rookery on a large scale and the birds appear to be as resentful of intrusion on their domain as rooks are, for they say, no other birds are found here. The smell of the guano was very disagreeable, and the proprietor told me he intended to begin to collect it for exportation. The manner of procuring fresh eggs is curious. A patch on the sand is cleared from stones, and old eggs, and on the following morning it is found covered with new laid ones, as these birds build no nest.

We could see over the Island which is destitute of vegetation, mere barred [*sic*] granite rocks, with here and there patches of soil from their degradation, and some spots of sand on the shore. There are two small huts on it for the guardians. We steamed from Reciffe to Frigate Island, which is about 50 miles from Mahé. We saw great numbers of that species of Porpoise called by whalers the cow-fish²⁷. They are of an olive brown with a white stripe from head to tail, and as they followed the ship constantly leaped out of the water often many feet in an oblique direction, but as we were steaming and sailing fast, we soon left them behind. Large turtles lay apparently asleep floating on the waves, for our passing did not seem at all to disturb them. When about 3 miles from Frigate Island there is a strong current, and one single rock just shows above the waters, which break madly round it. At a short distance from it are soundings over 50 fathoms, so that very probably it is the top of some submerged mountain of a former continent.

We ran in round this rock and fired a gun. We could plainly see the houses on shore and people moving about, and a flag staff with the English ensign but no one came off, and after waiting some time, the midshipmen volunteered to go on shore in the whale boat. In rounding the island we lost sight of them, and supposed they intended landing on the other side which is very high, and we expected to see them, but as a good time elapsed and no appearance of them, some fears were entertained for their safety. After waiting till 3 p.m., we fired another gun, when in a few minutes we saw a very large whale boat approaching, and it proved to contain M. Savy the proprietor of the place, come to invite the party on shore, to visit his house, an offer willingly accepted, and we landed on a bold shore, the waves breaking directly on the rocks near us. Our landing was effected by anchoring the boat in the surf about 50 feet from shore, when two men paid out the cable till her stern was near enough the rock, that we could leap out. We had to climb up the side of the only mountain there, about 280 feet high through a few stunted trees, passed over the top where the bare rock shews in many places and in others patches of coarse grass, and descended the opposite side to the low land where Mr Savy's house stands, shaded by magnificent Banian and other trees. This gentleman was exceedingly polite and hospitable and after offering refreshments proceeded to do the honors of his Island home.

He has a Distillery for Rum made from sugar-canes, a plantation of which looked well. His vegetable garden was flourishing and we were all astonished at the monster cabbages growing there. A number of Madagascar cattle were grazing about the place, and he told us he made considerable oil from the cocoa-nut trees which were most prolific, and employed about 40 men in all. It appears to me a great pity that some enterprising men does not introduce into these islands proper machines for thoroughly expressing the oil from the "copree" [copra] or kernel of the cocoa-nut. It is an item of great financial importance, as a fair price is given, and a ready sale always found for it in Mauritius. I find that in 1862 about £10,000 worth was exported and with proper appliances that amount might according to good authority, be easily doubled. The means now adopted are only those employed from time immemorial, in India, Ceylon, &c.. namely, the old wooden mill on the pestle and mortar principle worked by an ox. By this miserably clumsy appliance nearly half the oil is lost. It takes one cwt. of "copree" to make 4 velts (40 wine bottles) of oil, with proper mills and suitable presses, at least 7 velts might be obtained from the same amount. The cocoa nut tree is certainly the greatest boon ever bestowed on a tropical climate, from its numerous uses, and as I have observed before, it should be planted wherever one will grow, and not only here but in Mauritius also. Why the culture of so useful a tree, not to speak of its beauty should be utterly neglected in Mauritius I know not. It is one of those enigmas yet to be solved.

To go back to Frigate island, after seeing a good deal of the place, I soon began hunting about the bushes, but I was warned by Mr Savy to beware of the scorpions and spiders, especially a large species of the latter, which is abundant, and its bite venomous. He told me that when the men went to work in the fields they took a small phial of concentrated ammonia with them, as these spiders attack them by springing on them as the *Epeiras* do on their prey. Sometimes the bite when not promptly attended to will cause death or long illness, but even when dressed at once with ammonia, the victim is laid up for 8 or 10 days. The poison induces vomiting, cramps, and swelling of the whole body. This same spider is also at Mahé and I saw an American on Mr Sedgewick's Estate who was bitten by a spider while asleep, and he had been in bed for some weeks. It did not however appear to me as common there as at Frigate Island. I found them amongst husks of cocoanuts and dry leaves, and succeeded in bottling a number. It was with the greatest difficulty I could get the Mozambiques to come near me when they saw I had caught some. In brushing over some dead leaves for a *Scincus* new to me, a spider jumped out at them, and they ran for dear life as if a tiger was after them; no inducement could make them help me put them in the bottle of alcohol.

This spider belongs to the genus *Phrynus*²⁸, and resembles the *P. reniforme* Fab. but if the drawings I have seen of the latter are correct, then these I procured are of a different species or a very strongly marked variety for there are notable differences in the palpi and legs. This genus is easily known by the excessive tenuity of the multi-articulate fore legs, which apparently serve the purposes of antennae rather than of locomotion. Like all the Pedipalpi, the maxillary palpi resemble legs, are very stout and long, and terminate in a formidable group of claws. The mandibles are very short and sharp; and the legs have a double serration on the outer side to the second articulation where is a sharp spine, and they terminate in a double claw. Armed thus at all points, and carnivorous, they must be most terrible enemies to the insects they feed on. I have some females 14 lines long, but the males rarely exceed nine. The fore legs of the former measure over 5 inches. The latter have brown and yellow stripe on the legs whilst the female is of a uniform dark brown except the palpi that are nearly black. This genus exists I believe only in Seychelles, Brazil and Lower California.

I captured several scorpions from 8 to 9 inches long, but the men did not seem afraid of them as they were of the spiders. One small one not more than an inch and a half long of a different species seems to be the only one dreaded, the bite of it causing violent inflammation²⁹. I was only able to procure one specimen of it. Several snakes were brought

to me alive, said to be harmless. Some of a bright yellow and olive colour, others ash colour with dirty white spots, and they were said to be different species, but on examining them before and after death, I concluded them to be only varieties of the same species, the differences caused probably by various food and ages³⁰. They call them harmless, simply because they don't attempt to bite unless attacked, but if they do bite, it is never without danger more or less.

On almost all the coco nut trees is found a large Gecko of a yellowish brown colour, somewhat repulsive looking³¹. Strange to say it is only found on this island and at Curieuse. I now first saw the beautiful bird the *Pie Chanteuse*, *Copsychus Sechellarum*³² first brought to the notice of the scientific world by the Hon. E. Newton and his brother. I should have liked to procure a specimen but the proprietor was unwilling to have one shot as this, as well as other indigenous birds in the various islands will soon be but memories of the past, as are the Dodo, Solitaire, &c., from their constant destruction by cats and rats, both of which are in formidable numbers in most of the islands. A nest with a young one was brought to us, but one of the party requested it might be at once replaced, which was immediately done. This nest was roughly and loosely made of dried blades of coarse grass outside, but the interior was of very fine grass neatly interwoven, interspersed with tufts of wild cotton. It was about 4 inches in diameter within. The young bird had still its pin feathers and was very fat. The plumage of the full grown birds is nearly black with a brilliant gleam of blue when in the sun, except a white patch on the upper wing coverts. I quote a few notes on this bird from Mr Newton's "Land birds of the Seychelles Archipelago" as he studied it particularly whilst there. He describes them as bold and familiar, even entering the houses. Their food appears to be millepedes, beetles, lizards, &c. They have a jerking motion of the tail and sit with the wings drooping and tail erect. The bird has a pleasant succession of low soft notes heard chiefly morning and evening. The young if taken from the nest are rarely if ever reared. A good drawing of this bird may be seen in the *Ibis* for August 1865.

When hunting for shells on the shore a coloured man evidently a labourer, came up and asked me the names of some species he had in his hands and of which he told me about their animals. I at once gave him them as they were familiar to me. One of our party laughed at the idea of such a man wanting to know anything of conchology. Now it struck me as anything but laughable, this pursuit of knowledge under difficulties. I could not help comparing this humble aspirant for information, who had well studied the animals and their habits, with the numerous shell collectors in Mauritius and elsewhere, who load their memory with long scientific names, and know nothing of the habits, habitat or forms of the architects of the shells.

Frigate Island has but sparse vegetation, no large timber trees, only here and there clumps of bushes. It is entirely of granite, and I think of more recent date than Curieuse, which I visited later. The granite of the mountain is less degraded, and has fewer fissures, and there is a scarcity of the detached boulders on the lower parts of the island, compared with those I saw elsewhere. The reef near Mr. Savy's house makes off to some distance, and I was astonished to find it consisted in a great measure of the Scarlet *Tubipora Musica*, so brilliant when in the water but that grows dull directly it is dry. I have however seen some pieces from St. Brandon preserve their colour many months. The colour instead of being a bright scarlet is orange, so it is possible it may be another species of the Tubiporæ, it being now decided by zoologists that there are others besides the *musica*, distinguishable by the colour of the polyps. These animals appear to have been more closely studied than any other of the corallines. "The Tubiporæ live in societies but do not appear to be united, as the compound polyps. A group presents several stages of tubes, one above the other, but appear slightly to diverge as radiating from a common centre; they are separated by intervals and support each other by horizontal laminae. From each tube issues a membranous animal of a grass-green colour, the mouth being surrounded by 9 tentacles, furnished along their edges with rows of minute fleshy papillae."

I found some interesting Algae the same as those at Mauritius, but very large. The *Laurencia papillosa*, *Padina pavonia* and *Hydroclathrus cancellatus*. The fronds of the *Gracilaria crassa* so small in Mauritius were very large, and it lay in masses on the shore. The lovely *Plocamium cornuta* that I have taken at Flacq and Flat Island, was also abundant of the most brilliant scarlet. To my surprise I found a plant dead on the beach I have looked in vain for at Mauritius, the *Bryopsis plumosa*. This elegant little plant is found the world over from the cold north in the Faroe Islands through the tropics southward, to Cape Horn and New Zealand. Between the shore and the reefs grows the *Caulerpa denticulata* but I did not see any of the long fronds of the *C. Scalpelli formis* so abundant in Port Louis Harbour. In the Pacific archipelagoes several species of *Caulerpa* are eaten, and the green fat of the Turtle is said to be owing to the semi-gelatinous, bright green endochrome containing starch grains mixed with oily particles, that fills the fronds of all *Caulerpas*. I picked up a branch of *Turbinaria*, but it appeared much coarser than the *ornata* at Mauritius. The cup like tips of the fronds were filled with the pretty little coralline parasite, *Jania antenina* its pink colour having the effect of a flower, it was in such masses that it was very difficult to know which was the original plant. This however was not the only parasite that had adopted the *Turbinaria* as a home. I was waiting for the rest to return to the boat and sat down under a cocoanut tree to examine the plant with my glass. Some of the fronds were covered which appeared to be a disease, to the naked eye, but on close inspection, proved to be minute *Lepralia* or *sea scurf* as it has been called, a sort of congeries of egg-shaped cells of calcareous matter, but as the *Turbinaria* had been long out of water of course I did not see the polyps. Under it on the rock lay a delicate *Hydatina physis*³³, with its animal still alive. It is worth a walk to the sea shore to see this beautiful creature, and if any one in Mauritius possesses an Aquarium I would recommend the owner to procure one as soon as possible, as it bears confinement well. The colours are a lovely buff and sky blue, and when it outspreads its diaphanous mantle as it will do on the hand, it is a most interesting object. Bits of *Flustras* lay about, shewing how rich in Marine plants these seas are, and I wished I had a longer time to remain,

to examine the reefs and shore. One bit, I snatched up in haste and pocketed, prove to be on examination a pretty *Sertularia* growing on a *Flustra Foliacea*.

The Corvette was lying off and on about three quarters of a mile away, not daring to approach nearer, but the whale boat that brought us to shore was tossing up and down like an egg shell, not at all to the inconvenience of the men who lay half asleep in her. As we embarked, a wave broke over the boat and gave us a thorough wetting. Mr Savy accompanied us to the Corvette bringing with him a fine basket of vegetables. We then took leave of the hospitable owner of Frigate Island and steamed back again towards Mahé. A passing shower that fell at some distance from us, revealed a new beauty which added a wonderful charm to the already attractive scene. A double rainbow was formed and seemed to bridge the distance between two of the islands.

“Gaze on that arch of coloured light,
And read God's mercy there.
It tells us that the mighty deep,
Fast by the eternal chained,
No more o'er earth's domain shall sweep.
Awful and unrestrained.”

I cannot speak too highly of Capt. Thierry for his politeness and attention to his guests. I must not forget the sparkling champagne which he dispensed so liberally that was grown on his father's estate in France. The last probably for years he would have from the vineyards so laid waste during the late war's desolation and destruction. We did not arrive at Mahé till long after dark, but greatly gratified with our trip, for which Capt. Thierry had our best thanks.

VI.

The Mail Steamer of the Messageries Maritimes called at Mahé on its return from Bourbon and Mauritius. This time it brought Mr Horne, Sub-Director of the Botanical Gardens of Mauritius. As soon as he arrived I at once set on foot plans for making a botanical and zoological examination of the Island.

On Saturday the 2nd Sept. we were up at day light and off to the mountains. We took the range to the N.W. of the town, and began our ascent through a small cultivated plot of ground owned by a German. Melons, Tomatoes, Cucumbers, Batates, Carrots and other vegetables, Manioc, Tobacco and mountain Rice all looked healthy and promising, owing doubtless to their evidently careful cultivation. The proprietor, an old man was watering his plants and appeared both active and intelligent. He replied to our questions promptly, anything would grow in Seychelles and yield a rich harvest if people would only attend to their work. But no, he said "my neighbours will come here and talk for hours, looking at me working and admiring my vegetables, if they would only work as I do they would soon have as great an abundance as I have." I was much amused with the old fellow's quaint remarks and his evident pride in his garden. He is quite right as to the general indolence, judging from the usually neglected appearance of the grounds round the various huts I have seen. Like all places where the ground is naturally so prolific, there, least care is ever taken to make the most of land. Just enough is grown to supply the family, or to have a few baskets to exchange at Bazar for Fish or Rum, but no trouble is taken for further profit; although a ready sale could be found for their produce. The principal bread used by a large portion of the inhabitants is a sort of flat cake made from manioc flour. This plant only requires a stalk placed in a hole in the ground, and when left to itself will flourish and give a tuberous root that when grated and washed supplies the farina so dear to the tastes of the Seychellois. We passed along the foot of the mountain wending our way along a path between enormous blue granite boulders, certainly the largest I have seen in any part of the world. Some hundreds of thousands of tons in weight, luckily sufficiently apart to enable us to thread our way through them. A mass of vegetation has sprung up between them, and in many places giant Palms overshadow them, shewing how long they must have lain there since the time they were dislodged from their mountain bed and toppled over. In some places the people had taken advantage of the squares sides of the boulders making them serve as one end for their houses, certes, they were safe on that side from hurricanes or thieves!

I noticed at intervals, cocoa-nuts and the Bread fruit and Jack trees. The Bread fruit grows all over Mahé most luxuriantly. Doubtless the size and beauty of these trees is owing to the freedom of the island from hurricanes. The wood is excessively brittle and the handsome leaves snap off easily, so that it requires shelter from heavy winds. The fruit appears quite free from the species of coccus that infects it in Mauritius. Whilst making a visit to the gentlemanly and intelligent Magistrate Mr Esnouf; he called my attention to a Bread fruit tree near his country villa over 50 feet high, loaded with hundred of fruits many ripe for gathering, and the branches spreading wide and forming a magnificent canopy.

We passed up the first spur of the mountain and then halted near a neatly built cottage under the shade of some coconut trees, to wait for the surgeon of the *Forte* to join us. The construction of this dwelling was ingenious. The frame made of small poles cut from native trees pegged together, closed in outside with plank 2½ inches wide and an inch thick, sawed from the coco nut trees, and the bark stripped off. It was thatched strongly with long grass laid very neatly inside. The owner told us he got 50 strips of wood from one tree, and said it would last many years being very durable. We had not long to wait for our friend, and as soon as he joined us we proceeded on up the mountain. On the dead trees we passed was an abundance of what looked like a scarlet blossom, but that proved to be the brilliant Judas ear fungus (*Eridia auricula Judoe*), in colour and texture when fresh like rich velvet. My comrades both botanists were all eyes for the wealth of vegetation we encountered at every step. I wandered on a little ahead of them till I came to a valley between 2 spurs of the mountain, enlivened by a clear streamlet tumbling amongst the boulders. I was soon

occupied in catching a snake and some Geckos which were very numerous on the Bananas and coconut trees. Looking round me I was attracted by a tree in the distance which called forth such admiration I shouted to my comrades and we all went up to it. A *rara avis* it proved to be;—a double headed palm of the genus *Hyphoena* specie unknown about 40 feet high, as straight as an arrow, larger and more robust than ordinary palms; with a rough spiny back, of equal size from the column upwards. The leaves were very dark and long the two crowns dividing at top, and the leaven drooping with inexplicable grace all round. The fruit appeared long and large, hanging in clusters but so far out of reach. Mr Horne was unable to procure any, but he secured some portion of the leaves, &c. Near this was a Marroon Bread fruit tree, which resembles true one in the outside appearance of the fruit, but inside the kernels are larger than those of the Jack; but the foliage is scraggy and the leaves not so deeply cleft³⁴. Mr Horne procured many of these kernels. When roasted they are not unlike a chestnut. I know their taste from experience, as in one of my trips up the mountain I was invited to a breakfast, and these kernels boiled and eaten with salt and manioc cakes, proved to be the collation for a man and his wife, a child and myself.

Just above this we found some beautiful ferns, a store of which we secured. I caught several of the pretty *Euchelia formosa*³⁵ moths, the crimson spots contrasting beautifully with the pure white and jet black of the wings. They were hovering over the long grasses at the sides of the path. The *Cyllo Leda*³⁶ were very abundant, resembling those so common in Mauritius. One specimen is however very curious, instead of the hind wings being simply rounded and scolloped as in the ordinary type, the median line is elongated giving it more the look of a *Papilio* than a *Cyllo Leda*. I found just as great a variety in the colouring of the under sides of the wings as in Mauritius, the markings ranging through all the shades of greys and browns to pale buff. The *Euploea euphone*³⁷ was also very common, but small.

Our Mozambiques had my double barrel gun and Monte Christo rifle lent me by my friend Mr Durup, and I shot a fine pair of *Paille-en-queues* and some *Sterna alba*. We passed over the highest point of this mountain and came to the spur called Signal Mountain a portion of which has as an almost perpendicular face. It was formerly a Signal Station, with flag staff and house, but the latter is now in ruins destroyed by the only hurricane ever known to visit these Islands, in 1862. I climbed to the cap and hoisted a white flag on the staff in order that our friends of the *Forte* might know of our whereabouts.

Here we had lunch on, but found a number of uninvited guests. Large striped lizards³⁸ soon showed on every leaf, and grew so bold they fairly ran over us to get at bits of bread and chicken. At last they were daring enough to snatch food from our hands, they were however exceedingly difficult to catch, as they threw off their tails when seized by them. I am sorry to say I ill requited their friendship by imprisoning many of them in a bottle of rum. These lizards are inveterate enemies of the Geckos, and make war on them incessantly. I had noosed a Gecko with a horsehair and was drawing him in, when a lizard seized him and bit off his tail before I could interfere. The Gecko's only chance is flight as the peculiar formation of its feet gives it an advantage on a smooth wall over the sharp claws of the lizard. I found here a species of *Phasma*³⁹ about 5 inches long of a bright red, quite different to any species I know.

One of the first things a stranger would remark in Seychelles, a naturalist especially, is the curious mason wasp⁴⁰, that intrudes everywhere. It is of a bright brown colour about 1¼ inch in length. No place is sacred from them. As a friend tells me, they invaded his books and allied works of the most incongruous character with their muddy cement. The strong odour of nicotine in an old pipe did not prevent their filling the bowl with their cells. Even a piece of string left hanging from a shelf was appropriated as a foundation. Their cells, nearly hexagonal in form, about ½ an inch in length and diameter are built of red mud. No creature shows more wonderful instinct in its provision for the young than these wasps. A single egg is laid in each cell, when the female makes a terrible raid on the neighbouring spider's webs, carrying off and imprisoning the luckless owners until the cell is full, when it is at once covered with a thin coating of mud. It is supposed that the wasp stings its victims, and paralysis is ensues, so that it is easy to stow them away in the cell, which could not be done if they struggled. A supply of fresh food is thus laid up and it is supposed the poisonous acid of the sting possesses an antiseptic and preserving property; spiders and locusts having been found to retain their colours weeks after being stung, even in moist situations under a tropical sun. There is sufficient food for the larva till it is ready for the pupa stage. They are said to be dread enemies to cockroaches. They have one redeeming quality which ought to be generally known. They never attack if unmolested, so that on the approach of one, it should never be beaten away as is a common practice, for it is pretty sure then to turn and take an active part in the affray.

Soon after we commenced our descent we came upon a boulder about 15 by 30 feet and 17 ft. high. It had toppled over and was resting on 3 large round stones on the side of the hill, thus forming a sort of cave. My attention was attracted by some ferns growing near the entrance and some Lichens on those stones. I crawled in under the boulder on hands and knees, and found the whole roof covered with the nests of the mason wasps, which were flying in and out in numbers, and I must say, as long as I confined myself to being spectator only they left me alone. After I got out, I tried to detach a nest with a stick, when I was pretty quickly compelled to beat a retreat, as those belonging to other nests untouched, turned out like bees for mutual defence. I however escaped being punished for my temerity in intruding into a wasp's family circle unbidden.

Over this boulder was growing in wild luxuriance the *Piper Betel* so much used by the Indians for chewing, when mixed with lime and areca nut. Still more interesting to us were the beautiful Ferns, the *Acrostichum repandum*, and the *Lindsaea Riki*⁴¹. All over the mountain sides, growing in, even between the boulders was the grand Palm the *Stevensonia grandifolia*⁴². "A thing of beauty is a joy for ever" truly, for no matter how abundant may be the various

members of the Palm family, one never wearies of them, but looks up at them ever with a glad recognition of their wondrous grace and beauty. We soon came to a charming little brook, with a natural basin in the rock, and its silver waters were too tempting to pass, without refreshing ourselves by a plunge therein. There is a curious opening in the rocks near and we took out some specimens of minerals. I found in this water two plants that interested me greatly, one a fresh water *Cladophora*, and the other *Batrachosperma*. The boulders hereabouts are very much water-worn. Not far from this is a well built Aqueduct, conveying the water down the side of the mountain. We followed it for a good distance when we came to a fine grove of the Cocoa tree, *Theobroma cacao*. Clusters of fruit hung on every tree, but on examination we found that each kernel had been extracted by those voracious pests of these islands, the rats⁴³. This plantation had evidently been at one time carefully cultivated, but was now abandoned. A few Clove trees *Caryophyllus aromaticus*⁴⁴ were still flourishing; their blossoms shedding fragrance on the air. I wonder this tree is not more often seen even in gardens. It is very handsome and the spicy fragrance exhaled from every part of the tree should make its presence most acceptable. In planting it however, heed should be taken that this tree absorbs moisture in so remarkable a degree that little vegetation will grow beneath it. However the value of a grove of Clove trees would well repay the land devoted to them, whether for the cloves themselves or the essential oil they yield. How many things are neglected that, though not perhaps sufficiently certain remuneration alone, would make profitable adjuncts to larger industries. I caught near here a number of *Euploea* and other butterflies very similar to the same species in Mauritius and one moth quite new to me.

I nearly met with an accident in our course downward, that would have considerably shattered all my ideas, if nothing more serious. I was hunting a curious centipede, a *Iulis*⁴⁵ about 2 inches long that inhabits the grass at the foot of coconut trees when a monster nut just ripe enough to fall clattered, down barely missing my head, which if it had struck it would have inevitably cracked from the force it had acquired falling from such a height. I confess it startled me considerably. However I secured many of the *Iulis* in question.

Many of the coconut trees thereabouts looked sickly and dying. A planter informed us that the grub of a beetle peculiar to these trees burrows near the root eating voraciously. He had cut them out round the collum [column?] of many, but he feared the mischief was too deep and that he would lose the greater part of his trees. This is not the only enemy of this useful Palm. A large black beetle, not unlike the female stag beetle⁴⁶, eats its way into the heart and then works down the tree. The only remedy is to watch, and on the least suspicion to use the knife sharply and cut out the intruder. We arrived at last at a good sized plantation of sugar canes, which belonged to Mr. Mallet called Maloustanta and here we found the use of the aqueduct. The water had been brought a great distance down the mountain, and was used by this gentleman to turn his cane mill, for grinding the canes, the juice to be distilled into rum.

On this day the Admiral gave a picnic to which we were invited, and had promised to join it in the afternoon. On arriving at Mr M.'s we found a large party dancing in front of the house. Directly opposite in a cocoanut grove a large tent was erected but tiffin was already over. As soon as the Admiral saw us he came forward and welcomed us heartily and most liberally supplied every want of the weary travellers. We declined figuring in the mazy dance, our rough and dusty costume not being exactly fitted for even an out door ball room, and we soon left, as we had still about 4 miles to go before reaching Port Victoria.

Some time after leaving the party we saw some of the pretty little birds called *Colibri*, *Nectarnia Dussumieri*⁴⁷, and I shot several. Our road now led us down towards the sea shore and we fell in with a gang of prisoners lifting stone into boats for the construction of the pier; and others busy burning the rocks, as before described, instead of blasting them. They were mostly large thick set Mozambiques almost nude. Further on, they were cutting down fine Bois Noir *Acacia lebeck* trees for firewood, for lime burning. The Kilns are merely holes dug in the sides of the mountain in which the coral is burnt. Branching off is a wild ravine, and turning over the stones I found centipedes, scorpions, and other insects, and under the dead leaves some shells of the genera *Helix*, *Bulima* and *Pupa*. Fishermen were landing their fish for the market, but they had only a small variety most of which I knew. I caught up every sea weed I could see, but none differed from those I have taken in Mauritius. The following appeared very common; viz: *Lingbya Majuscula*, *Zonaria variegata*, various *Codiums*, a *Galaxaura*, a *Dernomenia*, *Actuotinhia rigida*, *Gracilaria dentata* a *Geladium*, *Corallina pedunculata* and several varieties of *Sargassum*. These were very few in an extent of over 4 miles of shore but they will enable me in a measure to compare the marine Flora of Seychelles with that of the Mauritius, as I have now nearly completed my list of Algae of the latter Island.

I noticed one remarkable circumstance, the almost total absence of plants of the order *Ulvacea*. I did not meet even the common *Enteromorpha* or *Ulva* that are found on nearly every shore from the Arctic and Antarctic basins to the Equator. Certain vegetation I remarked was apparently confined to particular localities; for instance on the reefs opposite the Trois Cascades, the *Padina Pavona*, covered it in great patches. Those near the Port, have masses of the *Gracillaria Crassa*. By the time we arrived at Port Victoria our *Vasculum* refused to hold another leaf, and our men bent under their loads, our very pockets so crammed we looked like walking museums. Though physically somewhat fatigued, we had found so much to interest us at every step, so much that was new to all of us, in our long ramble, that we forgot our weariness in recalling the incidents of the day.

VII.

On Tuesday September 7th I received an invitation from the Governor and Admiral to visit Praslin and the neighbouring islands the following day, and it was pretty sharp work to get all our preparations ready in so short a time. It was late before I finished, and then the anticipation of seeing these islands I had heard so much of, completely drove

away sleep. The window of my room looked on to the sea, and the soft fresh breeze came in delightfully. The scene that was soon displayed) before me as I lay in bed, made me forget sleep and all else for the time being. The moon, then in the beginning of the last quarter slowly rose from the Ocean, lighting it up till the crest of every wave showed molten silver, and to me it appeared to emerge between St. Anns [Sainte Anne] and Stag Island [Ile au Cerf], both of which lay clearly outlined. Heavy banks of clouds were massed on the horizon, half in shadow, half like sunlit snow, and it needed little imagination to trace out endless likeness to things on earth in the fantastic shapes they assumed. Still more transitory were they than even mundane objects, for before I had well decided on the form of some turreted castle or the outline of a polar bear, lo! as by magic, they were gone, and left but ruined crags, or mountain masses. "Pelion on Ossa piled."

Long before daylight Mr Horne and myself were up and about, and our luggage pretty nearly filled the boat that took us off to the Frigate. Sir Arthur Gordon who is also an early bird, arrived very soon after with his Secretary and Mr Commissioner Franklin, and we were soon out on the ocean. We arrived at Praslin about mid day, but could not steam direct to it on account of the dangerous rocks, but had to make a detour round Ile Curieuse, into a beautiful bay formed by that Island and Praslin. These rocks have a singular appearance, reminding me of old Druidical ruins I have seen in France and England.

We anchored about three quarters of a mile from the shore, and soon the Governor, Mr A. Gordon, Dr Micklejohn, the Surgeon of the Frigate, and myself, landed at Curieuse. We were received by Mr George Forbes, an old Scotch-man who has lived there over forty years. We visited his house where he shewed us his collection of shells, and gave us some crystals he had found in the granite. Then we went on a tour of inspection through the Establishment for Lepers. Small comfortable huts are erected near the sea shore, shaded by Palms and Coco nut trees, and each contains a cot and some plain furniture, utensils, etc., and were very neat and clean. Some were seated at their doors, but most shewing ghastly sores, and some were literally dying by inches and unable to leave their beds. In every cabin is a coffin ready for the inmate, which must I should think have a depressing effect at first, but from habit they don't seem to mind it. It is however a wise precaution, as from the nature of the disease, when death ensues, interment must be immediate^C.

If Mr Forbes had kept a journal of his experience during all these years, what an awful record it would be, of this, the most direful ill that flesh is heir to. I have seen a good deal of leprosy in Spain and Portugal, also in S. America, but it struck me that the disease at Curieuse assumed a different form to any I have seen before. I was glad to turn aside, for there is to me something so loathsome and repulsive in this disease, and verily the man who has spent best part of a life relieving as far as possible its wearying agonies, is worthy to be reckoned amongst the world's heroes. This island was formerly well covered with the *Coco de Mer (Lodoicea Seychellarum)*⁴⁸ but only their relics, in the curious old hard bowls remain of them, except a few that have been planted by the orders of Government. There is no level land but the strip on the shore where the huts stand, the mountain rising directly from it to a height of about 250 feet. It is entirely of granite, but it is so time and water worn, and in so decomposed a state that large pieces will often crumble under foot when trodden on. Mr Gordon and myself walked over the top of it, and I got a few dragon flies and butterflies but all old friends. I found the same lizards and gecko as at Mahé, scorpions and centipedes, but my time was too short to make a careful examination. We left Curieuse about 5 o'clock, and returned to the Frigate.

Next morn all were up bright and early ready to go on shore. The Governor concluded to land with a party on the north of the Island, and walk across to Mr Campbell's house. All equipped in easy costume they set off, and early as it was the sun shone out fiercely. I decided on taking our baggage and steaming round in the launch. We took a coloured man as a pilot, but when we got towards the Anse Marie Louise, the sea broke round us, and the launch danced about like a cork, and rolled till I thought her engine must come out of her, and as we ran into the pass we shipped considerable water. However the midshipman in charge managed her capitally and we got there before the walking party. Mr Campbell was on the beach with some people, looking out for the Governor who was expected to come in the launch. I introduced myself and he politely led the way to his house.

Sir Arthur and his party soon arrived, looking considerably the worse for their 5 miles tramp in the sun, their coats and jackets all left behind, or at least invisible. Mr Campbell with his family and neighbours were in a state of great excitement and no wonder. Was it not the first time that Praslin's soil had e'er been trod by one of Her Majesty's Representatives! I was not a little amused at these good people, out of whose eyes shone the heartiest welcome, trying to subdue it within the proper bounds of reverence for so august a personage. That soon passed away and the old Scotchman's native tact come to his aid, and he did the honours of his place in a manner that would have done credit to a higher sphere. No doubt His Excellency coming from north of the Tweed gave a heartier ring to his welcome, and an additional pleasure to what will be the greatest event of his life time^D. As soon as all had removed the effects of the

^C Great praise is due to Mr Forbes for his kindly treatment to these poor outcasts of humanity, and it reflects great credit on the Government for providing so comfortably for the poor creatures. This terrible plague is as yet unknown in America, and I pray God to keep it for ever from our shores.

^D To shew how easily the human mind grows habituated to what we are accustomed to regard one of the saddest sights viz a coffin, I will mention that when in the Cape I was informed, that far up the country the Dutch Boer always keeps his coffin in his ordinary family room. As soon as he is a man of some substance, he goes into the forest and selects the finest timber tree he can find, helps to cut it down, and has a coffin made of most capacious demensions, for the chances are, he is over 6 feet high, and as he ages, will become stout in proportion. If a rich man, formerly it was elaborately carved. When completed it is used as a corn-bin; and the Fraaw if there is one, places her milk pans on it. This is not I

journey, we were seated under some fine old Badamier trees, and coco tendre, calou and cocoa milk and spirits were handed to us which were very refreshing.

Near by a pavillion had been erected covered in with leaves of the Coco de mer, and one single leaf formed its end, and it could have covered a much larger surface; the leaves are pegged down with wooden nails made of bamboo split. We did not long wait for breakfast, and 14 of us sat down to a table covered with everything the island could produce, and I promise you we all did it ample justice. The sides of the pavilion were festooned with Lycopods and flowers and an idea I never saw put in practice before gave quite a novel effect to the decorations. Between every festoon hung a bunch of Mandarin oranges and sweet lemons, even from roof, to just within reach.

After breakfast, all set off exploring, and of course, our first visit was to the grove of the world's wonder the *Coco de Mer*, indigenous only to Ile Ronde, Curieuse and Praslin. From the first it has entirely disappeared; from the second, as above stated, it is fast vanishing and at Praslin it is still flourishing but if not more care is taken to plant fresh ones, as the old are so rapidly being destroyed a nut will be soon as great a rarity as when the Emperor Rudolph offered 4,000 florins for one. To me as to most other people the first sight of a full grown tree was somewhat disappointing. A tall thin stem towering up over a hundred feet with a ragged head of green and withered leaves does not impress one. A cocoa nut is decidedly handsomer. These, however, are the male trees, the females rarely are over 60 or 70 feet, and not being so high are less exposed to the winds but when old are not much better looking than the males. But in this grove, the tree is to be seen in all the beauty that has made it so famous. It is certainly one of the loveliest vegetable productions when about 20 or 15 years old before the stem begins to rise. The leaves have then perhaps attained their greatest size and are in the highest luxuriance before fructification commences. (Its curious process has been too accurately described by Mr Ward and Mr Clarke to need detail here.) Of course we saw trees of all ages, and the nuts from the first stage when it looks only like a large green berry on a twisted stem, through all its changes to the hard conical looking nuts when fit for exportation, or to be cut up into the various utensils made from the hard shell. To me the first act of the plant's life is about as singular as any. It takes 9 or 10 months after planting before the germ is ready to shoot, when it ignores its parent bed and shoots away nearly 20 feet before it rises, and each leaf requires a year's elaboration in sun and air before the next appears. Considerable difficulty too attends the birth of one of these trees. If the nut does not fall with the germ downwards, when it strikes and does not meet the ground to draw its sustenance from, after an ineffectual struggle for some few feet on the surface, it exhausts all vitality from the nut, and the heat and want of moisture finally destroy the vegetable baby. Every nut grown for some years ought to be planted to keep up what *may be* a connecting link with an antediluvian Flora, and which *is* unique in its kind and confined to such an isolated corner of the world. The texture of the articles made from the young unfolded spathe, are too well known to require description. It would certainly be a handsome heirloom to his children if every proprietor of even a small plot of ground would plant a few nuts of these trees, though he could not hope to reap any benefits from it, his children and grand children would. It wants little trouble like the common cocoanut, but it grows while he sleeps, and the labour of this generation would be amply repaid in the next.

We crossed a march over a road made expressly for the occasion by Mr Campbell, and up to a hut which was to be the base of our future operations. We explored till pretty late when we ended our day by a good dinner, and slept at Mr Campbell's. Next morning the Governor and his party started to walk round the Island, and Mr Horne and myself to explore the valley and then climb to the highest point literally the backbone of Praslin. We began in the grove of the Cocos de mer. I was stripping some of the dead leaves of these trees looking for insects, and wherever it was damp I found at the base of each, a species of *Typhlops*⁴⁹ from 14 to 16 inches long, and twice as large as an ordinary goose quill; jet black in colour, but so active they vanished like a flash of lightning, and though I saw so many I only succeeded in capturing a small one. I never saw a snake with such rapid movement. It was quite new to me, and I was a little afraid of it, particularly as the men gave it the credit of being poisonous. Not one of them would attempt to catch these snakes.

We came here upon another floral beauty. I thought I had found a new fern, but Mr Horne soon settled it as the common langue de boeuf *Asplenium Nidus*; but under such unusual conditions it was scarcely astonishing I did not recognise it. From between the granite boulders the fronds sprang up to a height of 9 or ten feet, and 12 inches broad. Great clumps of it were met occasionally. It is on the Coco de mer that are found the large shells of the *Helix Studeriana* of two varieties, dark brown, and olive yellow, and the pretty little *Cyclostoma insulare*⁵⁰. The former may be seen up the stems through one would think they could scarcely pierce the bark which is so hard as to require an axe of the finest temper to cut it. When young it is said the Helix eats its way into the nut, but as it increases in size it cannot get out of what eventually proves its prison grave. We came to numbers of trees loaded with mandarin, oranges and sweet lemons of which we took a provision in our vasculums. Though we were not at a loss for refreshment as cocoa nuts grow every where, and you can always get a darkie to climb for the fruit by the inducements of the smallest coin. As we climbed the mountain I looked in vain for the black and green parrots once so numerous there, and the beautiful

am told from any religious feeling, but that when he dies, he may have a coffin of good seasoned wood, that will not easily rot. I apprehend the origin of it was, that, as there were no cemeteries up the country, hundreds of miles formerly intervening between the churches, every one was buried on his own farm, and if great care was not taken to dig deep, which the rocky nature of the soil would often prevent, the chances were the jackals would dig him out, and if his coffin was not sound, he would be made a meal of before it could be discovered. A termination to his relics, not at all agreeable to Dutch notions.

pigeon *Erythroena pulcherrima*⁵¹ with its lustrous black plumage with a violet sheen when in the sun, and brilliant scarlet head. I saw a few birds but could not get a shot at them. As to the *Cateau vert Palaeornis Wardi*⁵², I only saw one in all my walks and that was the first day of my arrival, and though I employed a man on purpose to hunt for them I did not succeed. They tell me these birds have been so destructive to the maize and other grain that the people have waged war on them, till they will soon be extinct. The *Cateau noir*, *Coracopsis Barklyi*⁵³ are seen at times but they are scarce. They seem to patronize the *Filaos (Casuarina)* which I find are called *Cédres* at Praslin. I saw a few of the Pie Chanteuse *Copsicus Seychellarum* near Mr Campbell's house which he told me he had brought from the Island of Ladigue, in hopes to renew the breed, as he said he did not think there was one left in Praslin.

The heat was oppressive, for the tops of these mountains are only covered with scanty bush, of slight growth shewing that it had only been there since the last conflagration. Fires are of frequent occurrence and do terrible damage to the trees especially the Cocos de mer. The island is not quite 8 miles long by about 3 broad, with a good deal of marsh land on the coast, and doubtless from this upwards the mountains were formerly very densely wooded but now, timber trees are very rare. We passed over the point of the continuous chain of mountains to the N. E. and then descended to the shore. We found some Tatamaca trees of great size which Mr Horne pronounced of a different species to those growing in Mauritius. I was surprised to find such a scarcity of animal life. During our long walk the only birds I saw were those already mentioned and the *Merle Hypsipetes crassirostris*⁵⁴. The latter bird appears common in the island and so tame it is easily approached; I shot several, and prepared their skins. I did not see a specimen of coleoptera although I looked carefully in places most likely to meet them. I caught a fine Death's head the *Brachyglossa atropos*⁵⁵, which appeared more like the European than the Mauritian type. The only other animals I found were some large green lizards⁵⁶ and these were so unlike the generality of lizards, that I caught them by hand without any trouble. We terminated our descent at Grand Anse, and were received by the Rev. Mr Vaudin who met us on the beach and kindly invited us to visit the Church establishment close by. The Episcopal church is a good sized structure built I believe by the inhabitants of the island about 20 years ago. There are now about 400 members, out of which over a hundred are communicants. The establishment is under the direction of a catechist, a coloured man, who receives 20 dollars a month from the Society for the propagation of the Gospel, I think they told me. Every two months the Rev. Mr Vaudin visits the island to administer the sacrament, baptise or marry, as occasion requires. Round the Church is a pretty garden and a cemetery lies behind it. To judge from the few graves, the death rate must be at a low figure. There is also a school house, but it is such a distance for little folks to walk to it that there are only about 20 regular attendants. The school mistress gets 12 dollars a month and profits of the coco grove surrounding the place.

We returned to Mr Campbell's along the shore. In one of the little caves we saw some fishermen just come in from sea and unloading their boats. To my astonishment I found in one of their baskets three specimens of a fish I have been hunting for a year past in Mauritius, vainly. The *Myripristes lima*⁵⁷ or very near it, a single specimen of which was sent over 40 years ago to Baron Cuvier and appears to be unknown since. I had a sketch of it sent by Professor Agassiz requesting me to procure as many as possible of it, and though I have swept hundreds of fish in my net, and attended the market almost daily I have not yet met with it in Mauritius^E. I found a good many sea-weeds and remains of shells on the shore sufficient to prove their existence in this locality. We again slept at Mr Campbell's house but next day bade adieu to him and his hospitable family. We crossed the mountain and descended close to the remains of what was once doubtless a fine dwelling house, but it and the 130 once luxuriant garden were mere wrecks; and the proprietor long dead. We fired a gun as a signal and a boat put off from the Frigate and took us on board. The following day being Sunday we lay still at our anchorage, and it was always most religiously kept, as I observed before. Mr & Mrs Campbell came off and joined in the services of the day.

On Monday we steamed away and brought up at about a mile from La Digue. The Governor and a party left in the launch for Félicité. After their departure, Cap. Fairfax kindly put his cutter at my disposal and we rowed away to La Digue. It looked easy enough to land from the ship, but on approaching we found a strong current running 14 knots an hour, and the surf breaking on the shore. A boat put off to us and signed to us to hold on, and we did so till they came up, when they said that the pass was very dangerous, but they would guide us in. Only a few years ago Dr Robinson with an American Captain and eight of his crew were drowned whilst attempting to land. They piloted us safely in and then I saw about 100 people assembled on the shore. As soon as I landed I was greeted by the firing of guns and pistols, ringing of hand bells and letting off crackers, and found I was receiving the honours due to His Excellency.

I was so astonished at my reception and the din of the 'feu-de-joie' that for a few minutes I could not make it understood I was the wrong man. At last I announced myself as the American Consul, but assured them the right man would be along in an hour's time. In spite of my loss of dignity I was warmly welcomed, and after partaking of some refreshment I made my way to Mr Nageon's place, escorted by a policeman, through a grand coco nut tree avenue nearly a mile long.

La Digue is about 4 miles long by one broad, more wooded than any other of the islands I visited. It has about 600 inhabitants mostly coloured, and a pretty Catholic church which they told me was well attended. Mr Nageon has the finest coco grove there; about 60,000 trees all in full bearing, yielding about 8,000 velts annually. He has planted young trees very largely. His drying house is recently built, and in a most improved style. The roof of corrugated iron, is made

^E I may here state that after all I lost my fish as the glass jar in which they were preserved with many other valuable specimens of Natural History was smashed when my luggage was being put on board the steamer, and the contents fell into the sea.

to run off and on at will, so that should a storm occur, the coco nuts can be covered in a moment. Mr Nageon appears to be an enterprising man, one of the few with really an eye to the future. So soon as I arrived I had breakfast with the family and then set out looking for specimens of Natural History. Just behind the house is the monster boulder noticed by former visitors. I thought I had already seen the largest granite boulder to be found, but all sink into insignificance in comparison with this. It is true granite, about 125 feet high and nearly half a mile in circumference, very much water worn and I was told inaccessible. I wandered about the forest and found many interesting objects. The snakes I get were the same as those found in other island, and are peculiar to this archipelago, the *Tropidonatus Seychellensis*⁵⁸. Mr Nageon gave me a small turtle⁵⁹ which is found only at La Digue, I saw the beautiful Widow Bird, *La Veuve Tchitrea Corvina*⁶⁰ described already so well by the Honorable E.Newton, which he gives as a native of Praslin, but I doubt if a single specimen is to be met there now, and fear it will soon be another of the extinct birds of this region. I shot a female, in her black dress which I suppose give its name, but did not succeed in getting a male, though I saw two or three. The plumage varies so much, the latter might be taken for a different bird, for the only black it shews is on its head, so glossy and so relieved by the brilliant blue and yellow beak and bright sharp eyes that he wears no sign of mourning for his coat is of brown with a snowy vest. The female however in the sun has a glint of colour to relieve the sombre grey black of her plumage. I did not see any of the *Mangeurs de riz*, *Foudia seychellarum*⁶¹ though said to be there.

We returned on board about 4 o'clock p.m. when the Frigate had her steam up and sails loose and we soon left our anchorage when under full headway there was a cry of "man over board" spread through the ship. All was excitement and every one rushed to the rescue, but luckily the poor fellow in his fall from the bowsprit caught in the chains, and thus was saved from a watery grave. We soon reached Mahé, but when within 3 miles from the shore, the Frigate hove to. A number of boats were in waiting for us, to take us to shore, as the Admiral had decided to proceed that night on his voyage to Trincomalee. We bade Adieu to our friends to whom we had become much attached and wished them God speed to their destined port.

VIII.

On the 12th September a deputation of Free-Masons waited on me with an invitation to a Banquet to be given in the evening, which I accepted. During the day Mr Horne and myself packed up our traps, with a good store of bread, canned meats, wine, &c., all ready for a start at daylight next morning up the mountains. The owner of the estate *Exil*, Mr Jean François Chauvin had kindly given us permission to rusticate there for some days, and a sort of Pavilion for lodging. Mr Commissioner Franklin had temporarily repaired it for us, and sent us four men to carry up our belongings and make themselves generally useful. They were stout Mozambiques encumbered with the smallest modicum of clothing necessary. From sundry peculiarities discovered later we named them *Drowsy*, *Grumbler*, *Gourmand*, and *Tipsy*. Their distinguishing qualities easily guessed from their names.

In the evening I visited the Masonic Temple and was very handsomely received by the Officers and Members of the Lodge, with the honors due me as S♠ P♠ R♠ S♠ [Sublime Prince of the Royal Secret] of the G♠ O♠ F♠ [Grand Orient [Lodge] of France]⁶² During the evening I witnessed two receptions which were conducted in true masonic style. The Temple was filled with the leading men of the island, and when the business of the Lodge was over, we adjourned to the Banqueting room. After discussing the bountiful supply of good things provided, speeches were made and healths drunk, and I quitted the Temple with favourable impressions as to the progress of Masonry in Mahé. The lateness of the hour left me little time for sleep.

At day dawn we were on the move as our climb to our mountain home for the next few days was to be nearly 2000 feet above sea level. We equally distributed our provisions, vasculums, pressing boards, bottles, &c., among the four men, and hurried off so as to make as much head way as possible before the sun was high. Our first rest was in the cocoanut grove of Mr Aristide Dupuy some distance up the mountain. Here we saw the sun rise gloriously from the Ocean to the cloudless blue sky, which we did not appreciate as much as such a scene deserves from the but too certain indications of a glaring hot day.

Here the guardian offered us the use of a house if we would remain, but after taking some coco nut water we pushed on till we came to a grove of stunted trees. Among them we found a curious *Vacoa*⁶³ tree the first of the kind we had ever seen and it interested us greatly, Mr. Horne deeming it a new species. Aerial roots, descended from the branches all round the trees nearly to the earth (in many we saw later they had reached it.) They were perfectly round, and some of them as large as the trunk itself. Whether these strong aerial roots are for steadying the stem in case of high winds or for drawing additional moisture, I know not but for both purposes, I should suppose. The tips have an outer coating to protect the cellular integument in its downward progress, but once on the earth it quickly buries itself and each one helps to imbibe nourishment probably for the perfection of its fruit. Mr Horne took a number of seeds and leaves.

After leaving the grove we came to a patch of coarse rank grass 8 or 9 feet high. We found many Chameleons on it, and the red *Bulimus velutinus*, and I got specimens of the large *Iulus*, *Spirostreptus obtusus*⁶⁴. We came to a little plateau, and were anticipating the end of our journey, when we found we had still a long pull up a steep rocky path of some hundred of feet. It somewhat dismayed us, for we were already well fagged, but resting a little, and getting rid of one outer garments we put a good face on the matter. When about half way up we came to a bright little spring of water gushing out between the boulders, and Mr. Horne was lucky enough to find a beautiful Orchid in full flowers which he appropriated instantly. It was a little break in our hard climb and helped us on the rest of the way and we were not sorry

when we got to our quarters which Mr. Horne at once christened the Eyrie, and well named too perched as it was on the top of the rock we had just climbed. How the poor Mozambiques dragged themselves up with their heavy load I don't know, it was as much as we could do to carry ourselves.

Breakfast was soon on foot—and after a quiet pipe, we got our hammocks slung and our house in order. We all took a rest and the men fixed up a shelter for themselves while we examined our quarters. Our house consisted of one entire room, and a second with only a roof on posts. It was situated on the one of the little plateaux so numerous in these mountains, and behind it rose a high granite wall of rock and out of the crevices in it grew the [endemic] *Stevensonia grandiflora* Palms, in every stage, and we looked longingly at the Ferns and Orchids which hung above us as hopelessly out of reach as the foxes' grapes.

When pretty well refreshed we began our explorings and entered some of the ravines of the Morne Blanc. We had constantly to cut our way through the rank growth of Ferns and underbrush, and occasionally were brought up suddenly by a huge boulder, and had to cut a path round it. We penetrated about half-way, but found it such hard and slow work that it would be night fall before we got to the top. We declined sleeping in the bush, as showers fell most every night so we returned home, Mr Horne with I know not what of rare and beautiful I saw him snatching up at every turn, and my vasculum filled with land shells, centipedes and scorpions. I got a good supply of the fine *Helix unidentata*, a small *Helix* resembling the *Similaris*, a silvery looking *Pupa*, the striped and plain *Bulimus fulvicans* and the *Helix insulara*⁶⁵. After our dinner we amused ourselves watching the Flying Foxes (*Pteropus Edwardisi*)⁶⁶. Some appeared very large but flew so high and wheeled so rapidly it was impossible to get a shot at them. They came out of the Clefts in the high rocks behind us, flying to a grove of *Badamier* trees where they fed on the nuts. While we were enjoying our pipes and discussing the treasures we had accumulated in the day, I was surprised to hear a sort of shrill prolonged whistle as if from a child's voice that seemed to come from the Cliffs. Mr Hickie, a policeman, who had joined us, said it was the cry of a very curious bird that only made its appearance at night. He told us he had never seen but one, though he had been so long in Mahé, and that was found killed under a fallen tree where some wood-cutters were at work. It lives only at the top of the mountain, is as large as barndoor fowl, with long legs and is of an ashen grey colour, according to his account. I was so much interested in the story he and a forester gave us of the bird, I offered a handsome reward for a specimen either skinned or in spirits. The one that paid us a visit, kept up his cry nearly the whole night, and a queer one it was such as I never heard from a bird before^{F, 67}. The fresh specimens of Natural History I had procured were put temporarily to cleanse them in a jar of Mahé Rum placed in our outer room. I had a good many of the previous day's in our bed-room in some poisoned rum brought from Port Louis, luckily as it happened. When we got up next morning and I went to look at my jars, the one in the outer room was full of the specimens truly, but the rum was *non est!* Mr Topsy had drunk it all! A precious draught he must have had, as any naturalist will easily guess who knows what the first spirit is like that has snails, snakes &c. steeped in it. He did not appear any the worse for it, but I was obliged to send back to Mahé for a fresh supply much to the annoyance of Grumbler. It is well he had not hit upon the poisoned one, or I might have been had up for murder. As it was I so frightened them about the poison I was going to put in the next rum I got, that I had no more theft.

We determined on climbing to the top of the Morne Blanc which is the highest point in the Island. We got on very well through the path we had made in the ravine the day previously, but after that had to slash about us to get along. Towards the top we found the vegetation very spare. A short time before a party from the "Forte" with Lieut. Halifax had climbed up to it by another road and had left a flag flying, but suppose the wind had carried it away for we could not find it. They measured the mountain the day of their ascent, and gave me the result as 2,998 feet.

The view is very fine from the summit. Looking down to the harbour, the coral reefs lay distinctly mapped out and at this height had a singular appearance. The sea lay calm as a mirror and blue as sapphire, but the reefs looked like sheets of ice grounded near the shore, the edges furrowed and indented as if they were beginning to thaw. The various islands of the group seemed to lie at our feet. The wooded sides of the mountains shewed well with their grand Palms and trees and bearing flowers whose names I know not; the surrounding peaks seemed so near as if we could touch them by a stretch of the hand. Above, below, all was bright and exhilarating, but the spot on which we stood was very dreary, only a little coarse grass, a stunted tree or two and the granite rocks crumbling beneath our tread from the wear of time, light, air, and water. It was late before we returned, and we had little to repay us for our toil save the view. In the evening we saw many fireflies some of which I secured. In the grass round our eyrie we caught some of the *Tropidonatus seychellensis* [snakes] of different ages and in so varied a dress that any one not knowing them must have mistaken them different species. Earliest next morning, we were astonished with a visit from Sir Arthur Gordon who climbed to our quarters alone. Some time after, Mr. A. Gordon arrived. We did the honours of our mountain home to our guests, but we could not induce His Excellency to remain for breakfast, so after a long chat he left us to return to Mahé for his morning meal, which I should think he needed by the time he arrived there. We accompanied him down the spur below our house, when he continued his route alone and he went at a pace that shewed he was well used to a cross country tramp.

We devoted this day to the exploration of a mountain peak to the S. of us. We took a coloured man as our guide, but getting fatigued at our long walk he skeepaddled. However we had old Drowsy and Grumbler and they forget for once their characteristics, and though they did not know any regular path, like monkeys they seemed quite at home

^F The Hon. Newton who so perseveringly collected the Birds of these Islands, many of which are exceedingly rare, but did not escape his notice, informs me that he never even heard of this bird.

in the bush, and soon found us a way. They were quite delighted with our day for they found abundance to eat. I never saw a nigger yet that couldn't find something to make a meal of on a tramp, from a cabbage palm to an earth nut inclusive. Here there was no need to go to these extremes, for there was any amount of mandarine, oranges, guavas &c. with which they beguiled the way. In one of our rests Drowsy gave us a little of his personal history, when it appeared that his "lines" had fallen in anything but "pleasant places" formerly, and the recital woke him up to most unwonted energy.

He had not been many years in Mahé, but had been stolen by the Arabs from his country which he indicated by pointing over the Ocean to where it lay. He had seen his father and mother killed, and he with a number of others had been put on board an Arab Dhow, where they were terribly beaten and ill used. They were fastened hand to hand to pole, so that no one could jump over-board, and if, when pursued, the Arabs could escape in their boats they would often scuttle the Dhows or set fire to them so that there was no hope for poor wretches. This time they were suddenly attacked by an English steam launch and captured. The slaves were sent on board the *Columbine* Man of War, and the Dhow was burnt the slavers thus meeting the cruel fate they had destined for their victims, if the chances had been in their favour. We asked if he wanted to return to his native land, but he said "No, Mahé very good place, me well treated and when me work me get plenty eat." We returned laden with rare and interesting botanical specimens, but with the exception of a few common shells I saw no other object of natural history. I don't remember seeing a single bird, not a sound broke the stillness of the woods save our own voices and our foot steps as we forced our way through the thickets. As we rounded the foot of the spur of the mountain we came upon a hut occupied by an old man. He was the oldest black man I saw in the Island, as grey as a badger, but busily occupied preparing green bananas for his supper. He told us he was once a slave and remember some of the former French Governors.

After dinner we lay on the grass outside, and the men improvised a dance for our amusement. The music consisted of an empty tin biscuit box held on the breast and struck sharply with the fingers. All sang, if singing it could be called, made up of cries, and wails and yells clapping their hands in time to the music (save the mark). They kept up their dances with a vigour I should not have given Drowsy credit for. The fun grew fast and furious, and we were obliged at last to put a stop to it so as to get a good night's rest, as it was the eve of our departure.

I had forgotten to mention that we had not been utterly without game. One morning at breakfast time we were astonished by a visit from a maroon Sow⁶⁸ with a litter of 13 young ones, pretty little stripped creatures. All were at once the alert for a chasse. A chasse, if without honor, certainly not without danger. The old mother was a vixen A. I. and we had to look sharp to keep clear of her, for the way she grunted and chased *us* was worth seeing. The little ones too were as active as cats, and what with their squeals, the Sow's grunts and the men's yells it was a very Babel. They succeeded in capturing three in spite of the mother, and at last drove her off. They arrived safe and well in Port Louis, and to see their cunning ways, and good appetites, no one would suppose they were only young sucking pigs, they might have been on their own hook for months. Mr Gordon left us next morning, and we packed up all our loot of every kind and sent it off to Mahé by Grumbler and another man, and we left our *Eyrrie*, for new explorations.

Our way lay over one of the most villainous paths of the island, covered with great boulders. Frequently we had to cross half rotten trees which had fallen over them bare-foot; boots we dare not trust to, for a slip would have sent us down and jammed as in between the boulders, where help would have been almost out of the question. When we had crossed this bad part of the mountain we came out into the woods and found a very fair path. This we ascended till we came to the spur, passed over it and then descended into the Black forest.

After traversing it for some distance we came to an immense grove of Clove trees, some 40 to 50 feet high. Thousand of young trees were on the side of the hill, enough to make a fortune to any one who would work them properly. The soil evidently suited them, for the ground was covered with the fallen fruits and they were shooting in all directions. Many were in full flower, others just in the state for gathering the clove of commerce, which is the tubular calyx with a roundish projection at top, formed by the unfolded flower buds. Many of the trees had been cut down, and coffee planted in their places. It was a luxuriant spot with a stream of water flowing through it and it was Mr Horne's opinion that it was an admirable place for the cultivation of any tropical production, yet this, that might be made an earthly paradise was apparently uninhabited. On our descent we come across a patch of sugar canes, and a very primitive mill for crushing them. It was made under a temporary shed hidden in the jungle and consisted of a sort of table grooved at both sides for the juice of the cane to run into, and a tub of one end to catch it. The canes were cut into short pieces and crushed with the trunk of a tree about 20 feet long that has been barked and roughly fastened at one end to a live tree. This was then rolled backwards and forwards over the canes at one end of the table. We saw no still but I presume there was one handy. I had been attracted to this lonely spot by a number of butterflies and as I pushed through the tall grass I came suddenly on a pile of *bagasse*⁶⁹ and the shed, and the owners, two colored men looked quite disconcerted at my presence.

This Forest is wild and romantic in the extreme. Near the foot of the ravine we passed through, we noticed where a fearful slide of rocks from the mountain had taken place. Thousands of tons of rocks had been detached from the peaks above crashing down for over a thousand feet, enough to give a shock to the whole Island. Numerous rocks lay loose on the top and sides of this mountain, ready with a very slight impetus to roll into the valleys below; and it gave a somewhat unpleasant feeling to look up at the craggy sides, and think that at any moment one of those erratic rocks might follow us.

When we got well down the scene was very picturesque. To the right stretched a grove of Cocoa nut trees as far as we could see, with little elevated spot between where stood small huts. I suppose for the guardians. Down near

the shore was a pretty cottage belonging to the proprietor of the place. The line of breakers combing and foaming on the rocky shore with little islets covered with Cocoa nut trees that appeared to stand in the midst of the crested waves made up our picture. We rested and had some Cocoa nut water at the house occupied by the guardian of Mr. George Sauzier, and we then went ahead, for we had many a weary mile to go before we reached one resting place for the night. We got out of our path and it was only on turning back to the shore we were all right for South Point. It was noon by when we arrived at Mr. Marchand's house, and with the usual hospitality of Frenchmen he invited us to take breakfast, an offer most gladly accepted. This gentleman has a fine plantation, and he has recently made, great additions to it, so that he anticipated shortly very large oil crops. We were shown what appeared to be very fine sugar canes, but Mr. Horne thought they were deficient in saccharine matter. Mr. Marchand said he intended to cultivate Tobacco on a large scale and I do not doubt, he will find it a profitable speculation, when well managed.

After we left our courteous host, and kept on the shore I gathered a good many shells and marine plants. Mr Horne was not behind-hand in his botanical researches, I abstain from more than just touching on the Botany of the Islands as I have done all through these letters, as Mr Horne is making up a Botanical Report on them. When we were beginning to feel fatigued we met an old Man of War's man a Mr Green, and he told us we were very far from South Point, and that it would be advisable to go to Mr Felix Poole's near by, who would put us up for the night. This suggestion was too valuable to be neglected and we went at once to his place.

When we were refreshed we took a stroll to the Church and were introduced to Père Pierre Valentin, who welcomed us warmly. The bells were rung and guns fired in honor of our visit. The good Père showed us a fine collection of Marine shells he had gathered from the shores. Mr Poole gave us a most excellent dinner, and a comfortable little Pavillion to sleep in, and I shall never forget his kindness and attention to all our wants, nothing could be more cordial and hearty than our welcome. Mr Poole is by birth a Swiss and a baker by trade, and also keeps a sort of general store with the sign of the "Pauvre Diable."

After thanking our host for his hospitality, we proceeded on our way to South Point. Our path lay partly on the mountain and the rest by the sea shore, till we arrived at Mr Sedgewick's plantation, where we slept Sunday and Monday night. The Cocoa nut grove is not so extensive as many I have seen, but it is in fine condition. I could not help noticing how tall and straight the trees are in these Islands compared with those in Mauritius, where it is rare to find a top that has not the greater part of the trees with crooked stems from the high winds. Mr Sedgewick appears to be an enterprising man; he has a Carpenter, Cooper, and Blacksmith's shop on the place; and builds his own boats. He dries the Cocoa nuts for oil making, by artificial heat in an oven, a much more expeditious way than that generally adopted. When the nuts are cracked, the kernel is taken out and is ordinarily dried in the sun before passing it through the mill, a very slow process. We were treated with the usual kindness extended to strangers in Mahé and left on Tuesday morning.

When, within some distance of the 'Trois Cascades,' Mr Horne went on ahead for Victoria and I remained behind. The reefs make off here to a good distance and I waded on to them. I found little to repay one, except a few shrimps, starfish, &c., and some common shells. My examination of these reefs shewed me still more, how closely they resembled those in Mauritius. For about three miles they were covered with the *Turbinaria ornata*, *Gracilaria* and *Padina Pavona*, and not another weed could I find.

I remained so long on the reefs it was nearly dark when I turned homewards, and the scrambling over boulders in the dusk is far from pleasant. I was hurrying on when I was overtaken by a rather shabbily dressed Englishman. He entered into conversation, and incidentally mentioned that he was of high family, had been doing India—had killed 22 tigers, &c., &c., and was now on his way to S. Africa to shoot larger game. The Hippopotamus, Rhinoceros, Elephant in short anything that came to hand. He was or intended to be a second Gordon Cumming. With half the nobility of England he seemed perfectly familiar, and after a long tirade, by which time, I can only suppose, from the sequel, he had set me down as a green Yankee just out on my travels; he asked the loan of 5 dollars being short of cash at the moment! I will only say, he didn't get it, but before he left he was very glad to accept half a dollar. I have seen abroad too many of these loafers, all belonging to "the First Families," but in a decidedly reduced condition, too proud to work, but not ashamed to beg or sponge on any one not up to them.

It was nearly 9 o'clock when I arrived at the Victoria Hotel, kept by Mr Ducasse, and I would recommend all travellers in Mahé to try its accommodation. The 21st September was the day of the Banquet given to the Governor, and after that to the 24th we spent in packing up and visiting Mahé. On that day we left in the M. M. Steamer *Danube* for Port Louis. Thus ended my trip to the interesting islands, I should have liked to spend another month there, as there were many places I had had to hurry over, that wanted close examination, and others I had not time to visit at all.

Whatever may be the faults of the Seychellois, I must bear testimony that kind heartedness and hospitality are among their most prominent virtues.

N. PIKE.

¹ Major-general Edward Selby Smyth, acting governor while Gordon was away.

² Edward Newton

- ³ Anglo-Indian word for a light, or sometimes substantial, lunch.
- ⁴ Pike often used ‘-oe’ for ‘-ae’ in family names etc; we have corrected his occasional ‘Algoae’ to Algae. In this case he is referring to a sea-skater, *Halobates* sp. (Gerridae)
- ⁵ now *Physeter catodon*
- ⁶ *Margaroperdix striata*, *Numida meleagris* and *Pavo pavo* respectively; see A.S. Cheke (2004) Boobies on Agalega...
Proc. Roy. Soc. Arts. Sci. Mauritius 7: 1-6
- ⁷ She-oak *Casuarina equisetifolia*
- ⁸ respectively *Fregata* spp., Red-tailed & White-tailed Tropic-birds *Phaethon rubricauda* & *lepturus*, Red-footed Booby *Sula sula* (see also Cheke 2004, *loc. cit.*)
- ⁹ now *Cavolinia globulosa*, but could be an other species of these curious pelagic molluscs
- ¹⁰ *The Battle of Dorking: Reminiscences of a Volunteer* is an 1871 novella by George Tomkyns Chesney, evoking a fictional defeat of Britain by Germany, following Bismark’s defeat of France in 1870.
- ¹¹ Indian Almond *Terminalia catappa*
- ¹² Double Coconut, *Lodoicea maldivica*, tall fan-palm endemic to Seychelles.
- ¹³ there are a number of puzzles in this story. *Bois blanc* is *Hernandia nymphaeifolia*, a tree with ‘mediocre’ wood (Rouillard & Guého 1999) not normally used in construction, so making planks is odd. Odder still of course is the black arrowhead, and if the story is to be believed then this would have been an extremely important piece of archaeo-history, as recent research (e.g. Anderson 2018) has detected no evidence of pre-European visits to the granitic Seychelles.
- Anderson A, Camens A, Clark G & Haberle S. 2018. Investigating pre-modern colonization of the Indian Ocean: the remote islands enigma. pp 30–67 in K. Seetah ed. *Connecting Continents: archaeology and history in the Indian Ocean*, Athens, Ohio: Ohio University Press. 428pp.
- Rouillard, Guy & Guého, Joseph. n.d.[c1999]. *Les plantes et leur histoire à l’Ile Maurice*. Mauritius: [authors]. 752pp.
- ¹⁴ now *Chelonia mydas* & *Eretmochelys imbricata* respectively
- ¹⁵ day-geckos *Phelsuma* spp.
- ¹⁶ generally now known as mudskippers; *P. sobrinus* also occurs - both are *kabo soter* in creole
- ¹⁷ rose-apple *Syzygium jambos*
- ¹⁸ Gray’s leaf insect, *Phyllium (Pulchriphyllium) bioculatum*
- ¹⁹ Pike’s description sounds like the termite *Nasutitermes maheensis* but the biting is more like one of the small black ant species
- ²⁰ *Archaius (ex-Calumna) tigris*, endemic
- ²¹ sweet potatoes *Ipomoea batatas*
- ²² Fairy Tern, now *Gygis alba*
- ²³ White-tailed Tropic-bird, now *Phaethon lepturus*
- ²⁴ species of squid
- ²⁵ *Thunnus alalunga* also called Longfin Tuna
- ²⁶ While there may have been Common Noddies *A. stolidus* present, the description of birds laying on sand without a nest fits Sooty Terns *Sterna fuscata*, the species whose eggs are most commonly harvested in the Seychelles.
- ²⁷ although ‘cowfish’ is normally used for the Bottlenose Dolphin *Tursiops truncatus*, the animals Pike described appear to have been Spinner Dolphins *Stenella longirostris*.
- ²⁸ the animal Pike described is the harmless but fearsome-looking whip-scorpion *Tarantula (ex-Thrynictus) scaber*, apparently confused by the locals with the mildly venomous giant crab spider *Heteropoda venatoria*.
- ²⁹ The larger species was *Chiromachus ochropus*, the smaller, more painful one, *Isometrus maculatus*
- ³⁰ probably the Seychelles Wolf Snake *Lycognathophis seychellensis*.
- ³¹ bronze gecko *Ailuronyx* sp., probably *A. seychellensis*.
- ³² Seychelles Magpie-robin.
- ³³ a species of sea snail, a marine opisthobranch gastropod.
- ³⁴ this is the breadnut, *rima* in creole, a seeded variety of the breadfruit *Artocarpus altilis*.
- ³⁵ now *Utetheisa elata*
- ³⁶ now *Melanitis leda*, Evening Brown.
- ³⁷ now *Euploea mitra*, King of Seychelles
- ³⁸ *Trachylepis (ex-Mabuya) sechellensis*, Seychelles Skink.
- ³⁹ Seychelles Stick Insect *Carausius sechellensis*.
- ⁴⁰ *Delta allauaudi*, also called Potter Wasp, *mous masonn* in creole.
- ⁴¹ *Achrostichum aureum* and *Lindsaea kirkii*
- ⁴² The name used at the time for the palm *Phoenixophorium borsigianum*
- ⁴³ in the mid-19th century the only rat in the Seychelles was the Black or Ship Rat *Rattus rattus*.
- ⁴⁴ Now *Syzygium aromaticum*
- ⁴⁵ Pike used ‘*Iulus*’ (now usually *Julus*) as a general term for millipedes; this one may be *Spirostreptus sorornus*

- ⁴⁶ Rhinoceros Beetle *Oryctes monoceros*; the larva feeds in debris around the trees, and may be the grub referred to by Pike.
- ⁴⁷ Seychelles Sunbird, correctly *Nectarinia dussumieri*.
- ⁴⁸ now *Lodoicea maldivica*
- ⁴⁹ given the size, it seems that Pike had in fact disturbed one of the endemic caecilians; *Hypogeophis rostratus* is the only one reaching the length (14”) mentioned by Pike.
- ⁵⁰ the ‘*Helix*’ is now *Stylodonta studeriana*; the ‘*Cyclostoma*’ is now called *Tropidpohora pulchrum*.
- ⁵¹ Seychelles Blue Pigeon, now *Alectroenas pulcherrima*.
- ⁵² Seychelles Parakeet, now *Psittacula wardi*, extinct.
- ⁵³ Seychelles Black Parrot.
- ⁵⁴ Seychelles Black Bulbul.
- ⁵⁵ Death’s Head Hawkmoth, now *Acherontia atropos*.
- ⁵⁶ large day gecko *Phelsuma sundbergi*
- ⁵⁷ Cardinal Soldierfish, now *Plectrypops lima*
- ⁵⁸ Pike now identifies the snake, as we suspected at endnote 16, as (current name) *Lycognathophis seychellensis*
- ⁵⁹ a freshwater terrapin; the two species in the Seychelles are *Pelusios castanoides* and *P. subniger*
- ⁶⁰ Seychelles Paradise Flycatcher, now *Terpsiphone corvina*; Pike muddled the sexes – the male is black and the female chestnut and white with a black head.
- ⁶¹ Seychelles Fody
- ⁶² initials indicating masonic ranks and orders identified from Hannah, W. 1952. *Darkness visible – a revelation and interpretation of Freemasonry*. London: Augustine Press. 228pp. ‘SPRS’ is the 32nd of 33 degrees – Pike was thus quite a senior freemason.
- ⁶³ *vacoa* is the vernacular for screwpines *Pandanus* spp., in this case probably, from the description of the stilt roots, the endemic *P. sechellarum*, though there are several other species including also one, *P. (Martellidendron) hornei*, named after John Horne.
- ⁶⁴ Pike failed to mention these last two are respectively a snail, now *Pachnodus velutinus*, and a giant millipede, now *Sechelleptus sechellarum*. *Spirostreputs obtusus* is a giant millipede from the Congo, so presumably he is referring to a giant millipede, the only Seychelles species is *Sechelleptus sechellarum*, although this has not otherwise been recorded from Mahé, so this is an interesting record.
- ⁶⁵ snails: *Helix unidentata* now *Stylodonta unidentata*, ‘*Helix* resembling the *Similaris*’ is *Bradybaena similaris*, ‘silvery looking *Pupa*’ is unidentifiable, ‘striped and plain *Bulimus fulvicans*’ are varieties of *Pachnodus kantilali*, *Helix insularis* is a variety of *S. unidentata*.
- ⁶⁶ Seychelles Flying-fox, now *Pteropus seychellensis*.
- ⁶⁷ This mystery bird will be the subject of a separate note – Anthony Cheke
- ⁶⁸ feral pig *Sus scrofa*.
- ⁶⁹ the brush of leaves and crushed cane left once the sugar has been extracted.

Correcting an egregious error – rediscovering early images of the Seychelles Blue Pigeon *Alectroenas pulcherrimus*, with a comment on Sonnerat’s original misapplied geographical location.

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The misidentification

Ever since Tuijn (1969) first drew attention to two paintings attributed to Gijsbertus Haasbroek held in the Artis-Bibliotheek of Amsterdam University, these watercolours of a living *Alectroenas* pigeon from 1790 have been uncritically assigned to the extinct Mauritian species *A. nitidissimus* (Fuller 2000, Cheke & Hume 2008, Hume 2011, 2017, Winters 2011, 2013, Hume & Walters 2012, Hume & Winters 2015). Until, that is, they were re-assessed by Knolle & Vlek (2017: end-note p.271) who discovered (and re-printed) a third cognate Haasbroek painting (Fig.2) from a 2016 Tajan sale in Paris, where it was simply listed as ‘Étude d’oiseau exotique’ and attributed to ‘Haalbouck’ [*sic*]¹. Winters (2020) mentioned this correction, also slipped into a footnote. The second smaller painting noted by Tuijn (1969) is almost identical to the larger (seen in Fig.1) and is presumably copied from it²; I will not discuss it further.

Tuijn (1969) quoted a manuscript note by Arnout Vosmaer attached to the larger painting saying that the birds, only one of which was alive, “were sent to me [in 1790] from the Cape, but [actually] came from the island Mauritius”. This mention of Mauritius as source, and the fact that the published image in Tuijn’s paper was in monochrome, seems to have blinded later writers, their reviewers and readers (including myself), even when the coloured image resurfaced (Hume 2011, 2017, Winters 2011, 2013, Hume & Walters 2012, Hume & Winters 2015), to retaining the Mauritian identification. However it is perfectly clear from the coloured original (Fig.1), reproduced in Hume (2011), Winters (2011) and Hume & Winters (2015), that the bird is in fact a Seychelles *pizon olande* (Skerrett *et al.* 2003), *A. pulcherrimus* – the tail is dark blue (not red) and the crown is red (not white); likewise the 2016 Tajan sale painting (Fig.2). The accuracy of the artist’s rendering of the display behaviour of the pigeon in the Artis-Bibliotheek painting (Fig.1) is confirmed by its close similarity to the artwork of a Seychelles Blue Pigeon displaying in plate 36 of Skerrett *et al.*’s field guide (2001). Vosmaer noted the local name as ‘*pavillon hollandais*’, clearly a version, or corruption, of the term *pigeon hollandais* used for the bird in both Mauritius and Seychelles. Both pigeon species show some degree of red, white and blue, the colours of the Dutch *pavillon* (flag) – before the 1789 revolution the French flag was gold fleur de lys on a white background, not the current *tricolore* (red, white & blue).

While Vosmaer’s mention of Mauritius as source has misled, it is nevertheless probably correct, insofar as any products (wildlife included) from the Seychelles will have been shipped via Mauritius at that date (Toussaint 1957), and so would likely have been reported as ‘from Mauritius’, of which the Seychelles were then a dependency.

1 <https://auction.tajan.com/fr/asp/fullCatalogue.asp?salelot=1640+++++73+&refno=++498997&saletype=>

2 It differs in that a head-&-shoulders image of the bird with the ‘ruff’ in the normal unraised condition is added (apparently mirror-reversed from Fig.2), and in being signed by G. Haasbroeck (Tuijn 1969).

Figure 1. The 1790 watercolour of a Seychelles Blue Pigeon *Alectroenas pulcherrimus* held in the Artis-Bibliotheek of the University of Amsterdam, formerly identified as a Mauritius Blue Pigeon or Pigeon Hollandais *A. nitidissima* (from Hume 2011).

Figure 2. Painting of a Seychelles Blue Pigeon by Gijsbertus Haasbroek c.1790 offered for sale by Tajan in Paris in 2016 as an ‘Étude d’oiseau exotique’ (see text).

A back-story of error and deceit

While the above embarrassing mistake is recent, the species’s history began with a grosser error, or more probably a deceit. Pierre Sonnerat (1776) described and illustrated the species (Fig.3), but bizarrely claimed it came from ‘Antigue’ (error for Antique), the western coastal province of the Philippine island of Panay. There has been much speculation, summarised by Ly-Tio-Fane (1978), as to why Sonnerat rather too frequently gave erroneous localities for species he described. In this case, as in several others, it appears that he decided to use material he had worked on and drawn for his sometime employer in Mauritius, Philibert Commerson, after the latter died in 1773 and his manuscripts were shipped to Paris, to lie unused for decades (Ly-Tio-Fane 1978). Commerson had sought and received material from the Seychelles (Ly-Tio-Fane 1978, Monnier *et al.* 1993, Cheke 2008), and notoriously pirated Commerson’s description of the coco-de-mer *Lodoicea maldivica*, publishing the first description himself (Sonnerat 1776), giving the impression that he had been to the Seychelles, which in fact he never visited (Ly-Tio-Fane 1978, Monnier *et al.* 1993). At least he gave the correct locality for that species, but why he allocated the Blue Pigeon to the Philippines, and falsified the origin of numerous other species (e.g. Lysacht 1952, 1956) remains a mystery. Sonnerat (1782) was also the first to describe the pigeon’s Mauritian counterpart, the original pigeon *hollandais*, this time with a correct locality, but oddly not mentioning its great similarity to the species, allegedly from Panay, that he had described only six years earlier. His

Figure 3. Image of the Seychelles Blue Pigeon *Alectroenas pulcherrimus* from Sonnerat (1776).

description of the Seychelles Blue Pigeon was accurate, and clearly taken from a live bird or fresh specimen (or possibly from Commerson's notes on such a specimen):

Le Pigeon violet à tête rouge d'Antîgue [error for Antique], est de la grosseur du Pigeon qu'on nomme en France le Jacobin; une membrane charnue, d'un rouge assez vif, s'étend de chaque côté depuis l'origine de la partie supérieure du bec jusques pardelà les yeux qu'elle entoure ; le sommet de la tête est couvert de plumes fines, qui forment une calotte d'un rouge vif; le col, le haut du dos & le haut de la poitrine- sont d'un gris bleuâtre, plus clair sur la poitrine ; le reste du corps, savoir le dos, le ventre, les ailes, la queue, est d'un noir velouté changeant: en violet &; renvoyant quelques reflets bleuâtres. Les pieds & le bec font gris ; l'iris est composée d'un large cercle rouge , & d'un plus étroit, qui est gris.

The Violet Pigeon with a red head from Antique is the size of the Pigeon known in France as the Jacobin³ ; a fleshy membrane, of brightish red, extends on each side from the base of the upper mandible to just beyond the

3 The Jacobin is an ancient fancy breed of domestic pigeon *Columba livia* that has a raised ruff around the neck (Wikipedia; http://svdp.de/pages_eng/Per%FCckentauben_eng.htm) a bit like that of *Alectroenas* fruit-pigeons

eyes, which it encircles.. The top of the head is covered in neat feathers, forming a bright red skull-cap. The neck, the upper upper back and upper breast are a bluish grey, paler on the breast. The rest of the body, that is the back, the belly, the wings, the tail and the breast are a changeable velvety black – toward violet and also showing some bluish reflections. The feet and the bill are grey ; the iris is composed of a wide red circle and a narrower one which is grey [my translation].

Sonnerat, in keeping with French practice at the time, did not use Linnean binomial nomenclature, leaving it open to others to apply modern scientific names to his new species. Thus a few years later Giovanni Scopoli (1786-88) gave both the new *Alectroenas* species Linnean names. Scopoli hid his nomenclatural acts in a subsection, ‘Specimen Zoologicum’, in the 1786 part of a rare book in Latin ostensibly on the flora and fauna of Insubria (=Lombardy in Italy) – a book so obscure, but with such important namings, that Cambridge professor Alfred Newton (1882) felt obliged to edit and reprint the ornithological sections for the wider benefit. Scopoli used the catch-all genus *Columba* for all his pigeons – *C. pulcherrima* for the Seychelles bird, *C. nitidissima* for the Mauritian (respectively birds 98 and 89 in Newton’s edition).

Acknowledgements

I am grateful to Ria Winters for subtly revealing her (and others’) mistake in a footnote in her book chapter on animal trading in the Indian Ocean, and to the Biodiversity Heritage Library for making publicly available the 18th and 19th century texts cited in this paper.

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Records of Lepidoptera from the Malagasy region with description of new species (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae, Noctuidae, Alucitidae, Choreutidae, Euteliidae, Gelechiidae, Blastobasidae, Pterophoridae, Tonzidae, Tineidae, Praydidae, Cosmopterigidae, Batrachedridae).

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Keywords: Lepidoptera, Tortricidae, Choreutidae, Alucitidae, Noctuidae, Gelechiidae, Tonzidae, Pterophoridae, Tineidae, Praydidae, Yponomeutidae, Cosmopterigidae, Batrachedridae, Mauritius, Madagascar, Réunion.

Introduction

Twenty-four species are described as new for science in the families of Tortricidae, Choreutidae, Alucitidae, Noctuidae, Gelechiidae, Tonzidae, Tineidae, Pterophoridae, Praydidae, Yponomeutidae, Cosmopterigidae and Batrachedridae: *Apotoforma smaragdina* n.sp., *Cydia corona* n.sp., *Thaumatotibia rassembi* n.sp. and *Thaumatotibia rochata* n.sp. (Tortricidae), *Tebenna cornua* n.sp. (Choreutidae), *Megalonycta kissa* n.sp. (Noctuidae), *Anarsia dodonaea* n.sp., *Anarsia tremata* n.sp., *Aristotelia bicomis* n.sp., *Faristenia tamarinda* n.sp., *Dichomeris andasibea* n.sp., *Helcystogramma malagasy* n.sp. (Gelechiidae), *Agnathosia nana* n.sp., *Amphixystis guttata* n.sp., *Amphixystis patelia* n.sp., *Erechtias nigrocaputis* n.sp., *Eudarcia oceanica* n.sp. (Tineidae), *Tonza toga* n.sp. (Tonzidae), *Megalorhipida monsa* n.sp. (Pterophoridae), *Prays armynoti* n.sp. (Praydidae), *Kessleria gibeauxia* n.sp., *Xyrosaris canusa* n.sp. (Yponomeutidae), *Pyroderces spix* n.sp. (Cosmopterigidae) and *Batrachedra rainha* n.sp. (Batrachedridae).

36 species are recorded for the first time from Réunion (two also occurring in the Seychelles islands), 2 species for Mayotte, 10 species recorded from Mauritius and 4 new species for Madagascar. New and recent host-plant records for 28 species are communicated.

Synonyms:

Synonymies are established for: *Cosmetra spiculifera* (Meyrick, 1913) with *Cosmetra anthophaga* Diakonoff, 1977 (syn. nov.), *Amyna acuta* Berio, 1959 with *Amyna incertalis* (Guillermet, 1992) (syn. nov.), *Dichomeris hortulana* (Meyrick, 1918) with *Cymotricha tetraschema* Meyrick, 1931 (syn. nov.) and *Dichomeris ceponoma* Meyrick, 1918 (syn. nov.), *Amphixystis serrata* (Meyrick, 1914) with *Amphixystis maillardella* (Viette, 1957) (syn. nov.) and *Calicotis attiei* (Guillermet, 2011) new.comb. [orig.comb. *Stathmopoda attiei* Guillermet, 2011] with *Calicotis cuspidata* (syn. nov.) Guan & Li, 2015.

Collection site: Most specimens were collected in Réunion, La Possession, alt. 400m. Geographical coordinates 20°55'37"S/55°21'45"E. Other sites of collection are indicated in the text.

Holotypes: Holotypes will be deposited in the collections of Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands.

Plate 01: Tortricidae

- 01. - *Apotoforma smaragdina*, adult
- 02. - *Apotoforma smaragdina*, adult

- 03. - *Apotoforma smaragdina*, male genitalia
- 04. - *Bactra stagnicolana*, adult
- 05. - *Bactra stagnicolana*, female genitalia

Species:

Tortricidae:

Apotoforma smaragdina nov.spec. - Figs. 01-03.

Description: Wingspan 19mm. Palpi & head greenish. Antennae beige, emerald greenish at base, 1/2 forewing length, simple. Forewings: dark emerald-greenish with irregular brownish and blackish markings. Elongate-truncate, costa strongly rounded at base, straight posteriorly, termen straight. Hindwings: bronze-beige.

Male genitalia: valvae rounded; dilated with a pointed appendix in the middle of sacculus, pointing downwards. Tegumen large with a longue subscaphium. Aedeagus very short, with a bunch of short and slender sinuate spines.

Holotype: male, 24.iv.2015, Réunion, La Possession, alt. 400m, 20°55'37"S/55°21'45"E, leg. M. Bippus in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108624.

Paratypes: 2 males, 04.i.2020, Réunion, La Possession, alt. 400m, 20°55'37"S/55°21'45"E, leg. M. Bippus in Naturalis Biodiversity Center and 05.i.2020, same locality, in collection M. Bippus.

From my files I found later that I had observed this species also on 12.xii.2013 (same locality, not collected).

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Bactra stagnicolana Zeller, 1852 - Figs. 04-05.

1 female on 14.ii.2018, La Possession, alt.400m and Mauritius, Flic-en-Flac on 13.vi.2016.

Distribution: Angola, Congo, Kenya, Malawi, South Africa (TL), Zimbabwe
Regionally found in: Comoros, Madagascar, Mauritius and Réunion.

Borboniella allomorpha (Meyrick, 1922) - Fig. 06.

Wingspan: 19-25mm

This seems to be a rather variable species and I believe that several of the later described species (Diakonoff, 1957) are its junior synonyms, although the imagos illustrated of the different species by Diakonoff (1957) are insufficient to establish exact synonymies particularly as there is more than just a single valid species involved.

I bred this species from a large variety of plants. Although its larvae looked the same, the imagos that I obtained are rather different in markings. However their genitalia are identical.

Host plants: *Claoxylon parviflorum* A.Juss (Euphorbiaceae), *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. (Rutaceae), *Hubertia ambavilla* Bory (Asteraceae), *Hypericum lanceolatum* Lam. (Clusiaceae) and *Smilax anceps* Willd. (Smilacaceae).

Martiré & Rochat (2006) had already reported this species also feeding on *Antirhea borbonica* J. F. Gmel. (Rubiaceae), *Aphloia theiformis* (Vahl.) Benn. (Flacourtiaceae) and *Hypericum lanceolatum* Lam. (Clusiaceae).

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Brachiola amblopiis (Meyrick, 1911), Figs. 07-09.

Wingspan: 13-14mm

Material examined:

Mauritius: 3 specimens, Blackriver 06.-10.vi.2016 and Flic-en-Flac, 11.vi.2016.

Réunion: 6 specimens, La Possession, alt.400m: 04.viii.2015, 25.iv.2016, 13.v.2016, 20.viii.2016, 13.vii.2018 (male, gen.prep.RE-3579) and 8.ii.2020 (fem.).

Distribution: Comoros, Mauritius, Seychelles (Aldabra, Cosmoledo, Silhouette), new for Réunion.

Coniostola stereoma (Meyrick, 1912)- Figs. 10-12.

Wingspan: 9.5-13mm.

In La Réunion I could raise this species from inflorescence of *Pithecellobium dulce* (Roxb.) Benth (Fabaceae) (02.xi.2016, La Possession, alt.100m).

Host plants: raised in Africa on several *Acacia* sp. and *Pithecellobium dulce* (Roxb.) Benth (Fabaceae).

Distribution: widespread, from continental Africa to Indonesia. Comoros, Madagascar, La Réunion, Seychelles.

Cosmetra spiculifera (Meyrick, 1913) - Figs. 13-15.

syn.nov. *Cosmetra anthophaga* Diakonoff, 1977 (TL: Réunion)

Wingspan: 13mm

The male genitalia of *Cosmetra spiculifera* was illustrated by Razowski & Krüger (2007) while Aarvik (2016) illustrated its imago, male and female genitalia. These are identical to *Cosmetra anthophaga* Diakonoff, 1977 syn. nov. described from Réunion.

This species is also present in Mauritius where one female was collected (Flic-en-Flac, 10-12.vi.2016, gen. prep. Mru-133).

Plate 02: Tortricidae

06. - *Borboniella allomorpha*, larvae

07. - *Brachiola amblopiis*, adult

08. - *Brachiola amblopiis*, female genitalia

09. - *Brachiola amblopiis*, male genitalia

10. - *Coniostola stereoma*, adult

11. - *Coniostola stereoma*, male genitalia

12. - *Coniostola stereoma*, female genitalia

13. - *Cosmetra spiculifera*, adult

Plate 03: Tortricidae

- 14. - *Cosmetra spiculifera*, male genitalia
- 15. - *Cosmetra spiculifera*, female genitalia
- 16. - *Cosmorrhyncha acrocosma*, adult
- 17. - *Cosmorrhyncha acrocosma*, male genitalia

- 18. - *Cydia corona*, adult
- 19. - *Cydia corona*, adult
- 20. - *Cydia corona*, male genitalia
- 21. - *Cydia corona*, female genitalia

Collection dates (in Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m): 23.iii.2013, 11.xi.2014, 08.i.2015, 25.v.2015, 28.v.2015, 25.i.2016, 08.ii.2016, 01.iii.2016, 08.v.2016, 29.viii.2016, 29.iii.2017, 30.iii.2017, 20.vi.2017, 16.xi.2017, 20.xii.2017, 14.ii.2018, 20.vi.2017, 10.ii.2018, 14.v.2018, 05.i.2020, 15.i.2020 and 18.i.2020.

In Mauritius: 1 female, Flic-en-Flac, 10-12.vi.2016.

Months of the year: i, ii, iii, v, vi, vii, viii, xi, xii.

Host plant: inflorescence of *Mangifera indica* L. (Anacardiaceae) (Jean Etienne).

Distribution: widespread in continental Africa, Cameroon, Congo, Gabon, Ghana, Nigeria, South Africa (Aarvik, 2016). Regionally: Réunion and Mauritius (new record).

Cosmorrhyncha acrocosma (Meyrick, 1908) - Figs. 16-17.

This species was misidentified in the Mascarenes as *Cosmorrhyncha ocellata* (Mabille, 1900).

Guillermet (2011) reported *Cosmorrhyncha ocellata* from Réunion but misidentified its genitalia. I followed his identifications for Mauritius and host-plant records from Réunion and Mauritius (Bippus, 2016b) on *Tamarindus indica* L. (Fabaceae) and *Acalypha indica* L. (Euphorbiaceae).

Both publication (Guillermet, 2011 and Bippus, 2016b; Fig.63) illustrate the male genitalia of *Cosmorrhyncha acrocosma* that was earlier illustrated by Aarvik (2004) and not *Cosmorrhyncha ocellata*, as illustrated by Diakonoff, 1959b, Fig.4. Both host-plant records belong to *Cosmorrhyncha acrocosma*.

1 specimen (not otherwise examined) was raised also on *Desmodium intortum* Urb. (Fabaceae), 23.v.2020.

Host plant: *Tamarindus indica* L. (Fabaceae), *Acalypha indica* L. (Euphorbiaceae) and *Desmodium intortum* Urb. (Fabaceae).

Distribution: Congo, Kenya, Malawi (TL), Mali, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Tanzania (Aarvik, 2004); Réunion and Mauritius (misidentified as *C. ocellata*).

Cryptophlebia peltastica (Meyrick, 1921) - Figs. 22-23.

Wingspan: 21-22mm

Three additional specimen (male) were bred on 17.ix.2016 from larvae in fruits of *Acacia farnesiana* Willd. (Fabaceae) collected in Réunion, La Possession, alt. 100m. I had previously already bred the same species of Lepidoptera from fruits of *Pithecollobium dulce* (Roxb.) Benth. and *Bauhinia monandra* Kurz (Fabaceae) (Bippus, 2016).

This species was also collected at light in Mauritius, 2 specimens in Blackriver, 06-10.vi.2016 and one in Mahébourg, 13.vi.2016 (not otherwise examined).

Hostplants: *Acacia farnesiana* Willd., *Pithecollobium dulce* (Roxb.) Benth. and *Bauhinia monandra* Kurz (Fabaceae).

Cydia corona nov. spec. - Figs. 18-21.

Description:

Wingspan: 9.5-10.5mm. Head, antennae and thorax dark greyish. Antennae short, about half. Forewings are scattered dark greyish with irrorated blackish that are crowned with a small field of orange or yellowish scales at tornus.

Hindwings are uniformly grey.

Male genitalia (Fig.20): Tegumen weakly sclerified, uncus absent, saccus absent, strongly dilated valvae. Aedeagus moderately broad and long with sclerotisation.

Female genitalia (Fig.21): Ductus bursae short with sclerotisation. Two very large signa, with scobinate hooks in unequal bases.

Holotype: female, 21.i.2020 (gen.prep.RE-4080); Réunion, La Possession, 400m; 20°55'37"S/55°21'45"E; leg. M. Bippus in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108636.

Paratypes: female: 16.i.2020, 17.i.2020 (gen. prep. RE-4060b), 21.i.2020, 21.i.2020 (gen.prep.RE-4095), 22.i.2020, 25.i.2020, 26.i.2020, 04.ii.2020, 06.ii.2020, 15.ii.2020, 22.ii.2020, 19.iii.2020 (same locality) in Naturalis, Netherlands. male: 16.i.2020 (gen. prep. RE-4049), 17.i.2020 (2 specimens, gen. prep.RE-4060a and RE-4060c), 17.i.2020, 19.i.2020 (gen. prep. Re-4100), 21.i.2020, 22.i.2020, 25.i.2020, 27.i.2020, 04.ii.2020, 14.ii.2020, 20.ii.2020, 27.ii.2020, 09.iv.2020 (2pcs), 04.v.2020 (same locality) in Naturalis, Netherlands.

One male, 14.xii.2017 (gen. prep. RE-3446), 1 female, 02.ii.2020 and two undetermined sex from 10.i.2020 and 13.ii.2020 in collection M. Bippus.

Distribution: Réunion (TL). Likely to be an introduced species.

Eccopsis incultana (Walker, 1863)

1 male specimen, gen. prep. Mru-134, in Mauritius. Another specimen from Madagascar, Andasibe, 29.xi.2016.

Also common in Réunion.

Distribution: throughout continental Africa, including Madagascar, Mauritius, Réunion and Seychelles.

Plate 04:

- 22. - *Cryptophlebia peltastica*, adult
- 23. - *Cryptophlebia peltastica*, male genitalia
- 24. - *Epichoristodes leucocymba*, adult
- 25. - *Epichoristodes leucocymba*, male genitalia

- 26. - *Grapholita siderocosma*, adult
- 27. - *Grapholita siderocosma*, male genitalia
- 28. - *Leguminivora anthracotis*, adult
- 29. - *Leguminivora anthracotis*, male genitalia
right: Réunion, left: Mauritius

Plate 05:

- 30. - *Lobesia semosa*, adult
- 31. - *Lobesia semosa*, male genitalia
- 32. - *Panegyra cosmophora*, adult
- 33. - *Panegyra cosmophora*, adult

- 34. - *Panegyra cosmophora*, male genitalia
- 35. - *Strepsicrates penechra*, male genitalia
- 36. - *Strepsicrates penechra*, adult
- 37. - *Tetramoera isogramma*, male genitalia

Leif Aarvik (2004; p.89) had reported this species from Rodrigues island that was erroneously attributed as belonging to Chile (as Manuel Rodriguez Island). Though the specimen was collected in the Mascarenes island of Rodrigues, belonging to the Republic of Mauritius. There are other species that were described by Meyrick (1924) from Rodrigues bearing labels by the same collectors and dates (H.P. Thomasset & H.J. Snell Coll. in viii.-xi.1918). For instance, the Choreutidae *Simaethis turilega* Meyrick, 1924 bears this label. The holotype of *S. turilega* and its label are also illustrated on the website of Jadranka Rota: <http://choreutidae.myspecies.info/taxonomy/term/108/media>

Epichoristodes leucocymba (Meyrick, 1912) - Figs. 24-25.

Wingspan: 16mm.

One male specimen was collected in Madagascar, Andasibe, alt.945m, 18°56'51"S/48°25'4", 24.xi.-03.xii.2016.

Distribution: Madagascar (TL).

Grapholita siderocosma Diakonoff, 1978 - Figs. 26-27.

Wingspan: 10mm.

A common species in Réunion that appears to be rather washed. The male is easily distinctive by its long valvae that rear out of its genitalia. Though the females can be mistaken as washed examples of other species.

Distribution: Ethiopia and Réunion (TL).

Leguminivora anthracotis (Meyrick, 1913) - Figs. 28-29.

Wingspan: 9.5-10.5mm

One male on 04.x.2016, gen. prep. RE-2870 (Fig.29, left), was raised from larvae found on *Pithecellobium dulce* (Roxb.) Benth. (Fabaceae) in Réunion, La Possession, alt.100m.

Two male specimens were also collected in Mauritius, Flic-en-Flac, 11.vi.2016 and Blackriver, 06.-10.vi.2016 (gen. prep. Mru-064, Fig.29, right).

Another male specimen, wingspan 10.5mm, was found in Madagascar, Andasibe, 01.xii.2016 (gen. prep. MG-067).

Host plant: *Pithecellobium dulce* (Roxb.) Benth. (Fabaceae).

Distribution: Nigeria, South Africa (Razowski & Wojtusiak, 2012; Razowski, 2015), new for Madagascar, Mauritius and Réunion.

Lobesia semosa Diakonoff, 1992 - Figs. 30-31.

Wingspan: 9.5-10mm.

5 male specimens were collected in Andasibe, Madagascar, alt.945m, 18°56'51"S/48°25'4", between 24.xi.2016-03.xii.2016.

Distribution: Madagascar (TL).

Panegyra cosmophora Diakonoff, 1960 - Figs. 32.-34.

Wingspan 18mm.

One male, collected in Madagascar, Andasibe, alt.945m, 18°56'51"S/48°25'4" on 30.xi.2016, gen. prep. MG-027 (Fig.34).

Distribution: Madagascar (TL).

Strepsicrates penechra (Diakonoff, 1989) - Figs. 35-36.

Wingspan: 13mm. 3 male specimens were bred from *Psidium guajava* L. (Myrtaceae) in Réunion, La Possession, alt.550m, xi.2014 and 24.i.2015. At light also in 07.ii.2017, 28.iv.2018, 27.ii.2020 (Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m).

Host plant: *Psidium guajava* L. (Myrtaceae).

Distribution: Madagascar (TL) & Réunion.

Tetramoera isogramma (Meyrick, 1908) - Fig. 37.

One male, 03.viii.2018 (gen.prep. RE-3589, Fig.37) from Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m.

Distribution: Congo, Ethiopia, South Africa, Sri Lanka, new for Réunion.

Tetramoera schistaceana (Snellen, 1891) - Fig. 164.

One female (gen.prep.Mru-006; Fig.164) in Mauritius, Mahébourg, 13.vi.2016.

Thaumatotibia rassembi nov.spec. - Figs. 38-40.

Description: Wingspan: 18mm. Head, palpa and antennae ochreous-brownish, short, less than half. Forewings brownish, a little darkened near base. Hindwings: ochreous-brownish.

38.

39.

40.

41.

42.

43.

Plate 06: Tortricidae

38 & 39. - *Thaumatotibia rassembi*, adult

40. - *Thaumatotibia rassembi*, female genitalia

41. - *Thaumatotibia rochata*, female genitalia

42 & 43. - *Thaumatotibia rochata*, HT, adult

Plate 07: Choreutidae

- 44. - *Anthophila emplecta*, adult
- 45. - *Anthophila emplecta*, male genitalia
- 46. - *Brenthia leptocosma*, adult
- 47. - *Brenthia leptocosma*, male genitalia

- 48. - *Tebenna cornua*, adult
- 49. - *Tebenna cornua*, male genitalia
- 50. - *Tebenna cornua*, larvae
- 51. - *Tebenna cornua*, adult
- 52. - *Tebenna cornua*, pupae

Female genitalia (Fig.40): Two signa: one slender curved horn at base, moderately surrounded by little darkened patch, a second signa longer than first, in the middle of bursae.

Holotype: 1 female, 10.xii.2017, Réunion, La Possession, 400m, 20°55'37"S/55°21'45"E; leg. M. Bippus, gen.prep.RE-3442 in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108625.

Paratype: 1 female, 21.ii.2017, same locality, gen. prep. RE-3053, in personal collection Bippus.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Thaumatotibia rochata nov.spec. - Figs. 41-43.

Description: Wingspan: 21 mm. Head, palpa and antennae: dark greyish. Antennae short, less than half. Forewings: dark greyish, irregularly mixed with blackish. At 2/3 a dull, beige cell-spot in cell.

Hindwings: greyish.

Female genitalia (Fig.41): Ostium widened, broad ductus bursae, two large signa in triangular shape in ovular bursae.

Holotype: 1 female, 09.i.2020, Réunion, La Possession, alt. 400m; 20°55'37"S/55°21'45"E, leg. M. Bippus, gen. prep. RE-4048 in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108626.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Etymology: Named in honour of Mr. Jacques Rochat, Réunion.

Choreutidae:

Anthophila emplecta (Turner, 1942) new comb. - Figs. 44-45.

Orig. comb.: *Choreutis emplecta* Turner, 1942

Wingspan: 11mm. Two males were captured in Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m, 20°55'37"S/55°21'45"E on 21.i.2020 (gen. prep. RE-4080) and 11.iv.2020.

This species seems to exist also in Papua New Guinea but the specimens are not illustrated (www.boldsystems.org).

Distribution: Australia, Papua New Guinea and Réunion (new record).

Brenthia leptocosma Meyrick, 1916 - Figs. 46-47.

Wingspan: 9mm-10mm. This species was bred ex-larvae found on *Ehretia cymosa* (Thonn.) and *Cordia africana* Lam. (Boraginaceae) from November to June (in Réunion). Particularly on the second plant, *Cordia africana*, it is very common. In May-early June I found as many as 50 specimens on *Cordia africana*. On the first host-plant (*Ehretia cymosa*) there seem to be only single specimens. Both hostplants are introduced in the Mascarenes and this species is likely to be found also in continental Africa.

2 specimens were also collected in Mauritius at light in Blackriver, 08.-10.vi.2016.

Host plants: *Ehretia cymosa* (Thonn.) and *Cordia africana* Lam. (Boraginaceae).

Distribution: Mauritius (TL) & Réunion.

Tebenna cornua nov.spec. - Figs. 48-52. Fig.166.

Description: Wingspan: 10mm. Antennae annealed, simple, half of forewing length. Base of forewing and thorax dark yellow with silvery stripes, forewings brownish, irregularly mottled with darker brownish, speckled with silvery and white cells. At tornus darker brownish. Hindwings brownish. The larvae is light greenish.

Male genitalia (Fig.49): Tegumen absent. Valvae with two digits, the second a bit longer than the first, V-shaped vinculum. Aedeagus very impressive, longer than genitalia (120%), with cornuti in the medial section.

Holotype: male, 28.iv.2015, Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m (e.l. *Tithonia diversifolia*), RE-1781D, in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108627.

Paratypes: 4 male & 1 female (Fig.166), 28.iv.2015 (e.l. *Tithonia diversifolia*), 20.v.2015 (abdomen lost, e.l. *Acanthospermum hispidum*) and 12.ix.2015 (e.l. *Tithonia diversifolia*).

Etymology: Named in the honour of Dr. Séverine Cornu, Le Port. Her skills made this publication possible.

Host plants: *Acanthospermum hispidum* D.C. and *Tithonia diversifolia* (Hemsl.) A. Gray (Asteraceae). Both hostplants are introduced in Réunion.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Plate 08:

53. - *Alucita priona*, adult

54. - *Alucita priona*, female genitalia

55. - *Alucita priona*, larvae

56. - *Alucitia priona*, male genitalia

57. - *Megalonycta kissa*, adult

58. - *Megalonycta kissa*, male genitalia

Alucitidae:

Alucita priona nov.spec. - Figs. 53-56.

Description: Wingspan: 15-16mm, forewing length: 6.5-7.5mm.

Head and abdomen beige-ochreous scattered brownish, palpaе sharply angled, scattered with brownish. Antennae annealed, simple, little above half. Wings alternating brownish with beige-yellowish, shortly interrupted by a fine whitish streak.

Male genitalia (Fig.56): Tegumen long and dilated, half rounded. Gnathos moderate, terminally widened. Weakly sclerotized & short valve. Very long aedeagus of the length of the entire genitalia.

Female genitalia (Fig.54): Broad U-shaped ostium, moderate ductus bursae, oval bursae, no signa.

Larvae (Fig. 55): The larvae is pinkish and feeds inside the young seeds.

Holotype: male, 19.x.2016, Réunion, La Possession, geom. coordinates 20°55'37"S/55°19'56.5"E, alt.5m, e.l. *Barleria prionitis*, leg. M. Bippus, gen. prep. RE-2895d, in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108628.

Paratypes: 7 specimens of both sex, 5 specimens (e.l. *Barleria prionitis*), Réunion, La Possession, alt.5m, 20°55'37"S/55°19'56.5"E, 15.-23.x.2016; 2 specimens at light, 27.ix.2016 and 05.i.2017, Réunion, La Possession, 400m in Naturalis Biodiversity Center.

Host plant: *Barleria prionitis* L. (Acanthaceae). The host-plant is introduced in Réunion.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Euteliidae:

Atacira mima (Prout A. E., 1925)

4 specimens were taken in Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m on 21.x.2017 (male & female; gen. prep. RE-3402 & RE-3404), 27.xii.2017 and 03.ix.2018.

There is also a specimen collected at Aldabra Atoll, Ile Picard Settlement, 22.iii.1986 by D. Adamski in the collections of the Smithsonian Institution.

Distribution: Eritrea, Oman, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, Tanzania, Yemen. New for Réunion and Seychelles (Aldabra).

Chlumetia borbonica Guillermet, 1992

Larvae of this species was found in Madagascar, Andasibe, 30.xi.2016 on *Eucalyptus robusta* Sm. (Myrtaceae).

Host plants: *Syzygium cumini* (L.) Skeels and *Eucalyptus robusta* Sm. (Myrtaceae).

Distribution: Réunion (TL) and Madagascar.

Noctuidae:

Amyna acuta Berio, 1959

syn.nov.: *Amyna incertalis* (Guillermet, 1992) [orig. comb.: *Illatia incertalis*]

Berio (1959) described *Amyna acuta* illustrating its male genitalia. Orhant (2003) illustrated the male of *Amyna incertalis* (Guillermet, 1992), while Guillermet confused its male genitalia with *Amyna octo* (Guénée, 1852). These are identical and the species are synonyms.

Distribution: Madagascar (TL) and Réunion.

Athetis ignava (Guenée, 1852)

2 specimens were raised from larvae found on *Acacia mearnsii* De Wild. (Fabaceae) on 29.xii.2015 in Réunion, La Montagne, alt.750m.

Hostplant: *Acacia mearnsii* De Wild. (Fabaceae).

Argyrogramma signata (Fabricius, 1792)

One specimen was raised on *Commelina benghalensis* L. (Commelinaceae) on 10.ix.2016. Does not seem to feed frequently on this plant.

Host plant: *Commelina benghalensis* L. (Commelinaceae).

Chrysodeixis chalcites (Esper, 1798)

One specimen was raised on *Tetradenia riparia* (Hochst.) Codd. (Lamiaceae) on 17.v.2020, 4 specimens on *Ipomoea nil* (L.) Roth (Convolvulaceae) on 06./10./14.ix.2020, 2 specimens on *Impatiens flaccida* Arn (Balsaminaceae) and 1 specimen on *Solanum americanum* Mill. (Solanaceae).

Plate 09: Gelechiidae

59. - *Anarsia citromitra*, adult

60. - *Anarsia citromitra*, male genitalia (aedeagus in-situ)

61. - *Anarsia dodonaea*, adult, HT, female.

62. - *Anarsia dodonaea*, male genitalia (aedeagus in-situ)

63. - *Anarsia tremata*, adult, male

64. - *Anarsia tremata*, male genitalia, right: aedeagus

65. - *Anarsia vinsonella*, adult

66. - *Anarsia vinsonella*, male genitalia (aedeagus in-situ)

Host plants: polyphagous, incl. *Tetradenia riparia* (Hochst.) Codd. (Lamiaceae), *Ipomoea nil* (L.) Roth (Convolvulaceae), *Impatiens flaccida* Arn (Balsaminaceae) and *Solanum americanum* Mill. (Solanaceae).

Megalonycta kissa nov. spec. - Figs. 57-58. Fig.165.

A recent publication with an illustration of the genitalia of *Megalonycta mediiovittata* (Rothschild, 1924) by Ádám Kiss (Kiss, 2017) from Madagascar revealed that this species was misidentified in Réunion.

Although the imago is very similar to *Megalonycta mediiovittata* there is an important difference in genitalia, notably its aedeagus, and the new species needs description.

Description:

Wingspan: 35 mm, wing length: 15mm. (one specimen smaller: wingspan: 28mm, wing length: 12mm).

Antennae about half of forewing length. Greyish, spotted irregularly with blackish. One larger blackish field at the middle of forewing at costa, an elongated forewing in field at base up to 1/4, another irregularly shaped, larger spot at 3/4, at 2/3rd from costa. An irregular cross-line near apex.

Male genitalia: Long, solid uncus with curved apex, valvae not scarified, elongated oval, saccus rounded. Massive aedeagus, as long as valvae, with cornuti.

Holotype: male, 28.iv.2018, Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m, RE-3552, in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No. 1108639.

Paratypes: 9 males & 1 female (Fig. 165): 10.xi.2013, 03.iv.2014, 19.x.2016 (gen. prep. RE-1080), 03.xi.2016, 13.xii.2016, 20./21./22.i.2020, 26.ii.2020. Female: 06.i.2020 (gen. prep. RE-4039, Fig.165) in Naturalis Biodiversity Center. All specimens were taken in Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m.

Etymology: Dedicated to Mr. Ádám Kiss from Hungary.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Gelechiidae:

Anarsia citromitra Meyrick, 1921 - Figs. 59-60; 69.

Wingspan: 9.5-10.5mm

Head, palpa and forewings greyish, irregularly scattered with dark cells. A blackish spot on the middle of costa.

Anarsia citromitra is probably the most common *Anarsia* species on the Mascarenes islands.

In Mauritius I collected 7 specimens in Flic-en-Flac, alt.10-15m between 10.-13.vi.2016 and 11 specimens in Blackriver, alt. 20m. 2 males and 2 females from Mauritius were dissected.

On the neighbouring island of Réunion I have collected even more than 50 specimens, with probably still some 20-30 supplementary specimens in my freezer.

12 specimens were raised from larvae on flowers of *Mimosa pudica* L. (e.l.16.xi.2015, 15.ii.2016, 17.xii.2016) that I collected in Réunion, La Possession, alt.550m) and 18 specimens from the inflorescence of *Pithecellobium dulce* (Roxb.) Benth. (e.l. 23.ix.2016, 30.ix.2016, 16.x.2016, 13.xi.2016) that grew in an altitude of 100m.

Specimens taken at light in Réunion, La Possession, alt. 400m were recorded on: 18.xii.2015, 18.viii.2016, 20.viii.2016, 31.viii.2016, 01.ix.2016, 25.ix.2016, 28.ix.2016, 25.x.2016, 09.xi.2016, 25.xi.2016, 06.vi.2017, 22.iv.2018 and 09.i.2019.

Specimens of both sex and from both host plants as well as additional specimens from light had been dissected.

Recorded on wings in the months of: i, ii, iv, viii, ix, x, xi, xii.

Host plants: *Mimosa pudica* L. and *Pithecellobium dulce* (Roxb.) Benth. (Fabaceae).

Distribution: Mozambique (TL), Kenya, Malawi, Namibia, South Africa, Zimbabwe (Agassiz & Bidzilya, 2016), recorded new for Mauritius and Réunion.

Anarsia dodonaea nov.spec. - Figs. 61-62, 67-68, 74.

Description: Wingspan: 10-13.5mm. Head and abdomen light greyish-beige colouration, mottled with fuscous. Forewings: Light greyish-beige colouration, at 1/3 of costa a minute, short streak followed by two larger strikes at 1/2 of costa. Middle of the forewings marked by 3 interrupted, larger stripes, two interrupted stripes at dorsum, the 2nd only indicated. Hindwings light greyish-beige.

Male genitalia: Tegumen narrow, dilating, at uncus inwardly in-curved with a small hook-like gnathos. Asymmetric, broad valvae, with a small zone of raised scales at apex. Right valvae with a long curved appendage. Aedeagus: slim, long and curved.

Female genitalia: with a triangular signa.

Holotype: male, 05.xi.2015 (gen. prep. RE-2221), Réunion, La Possession, alt.565m, 20°55'25"S/55°22'45"E in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108629.

Paratypes: female, 08.x.2015 (gen. prep. RE-2178), 27.x.2015 (female) and 28.xi.2015 (male, RE-2559 wing preparation, Wingspan: 10mm) in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Netherlands.

Plate 10: Gelechiidae

67. - *Anarsia dodonaea*, wing venations

68. - *Anarsia dodonaea*, larvae

69. - *Anarsia citromitra*, larvae

70. - *Anarsia tremata*, female genitalia

71. - *Anarsia tremata*, wing venations

72. - *Anarsia tremata*, larvae

73. - *Anarsia tremata*, detail bursae

74. - *Anarsia dodonaea*, female genitalia

75.

76.

77.

78.

79.

80.

81.

82.

Plate 11: Gelechiidae

75. - *Aristotelia bicovis*, adult

76. - *Aristotelia bicovis*, adult

77. - *Aristotelia bicovis*, male genitalia

78. - *Aristotelia bicovis*, female genitalia

79. - *Aristotelia bicovis*, detail bursae

80. - *Dactylethrella tetrametra*, adult

81. - *Dactylethrella tetrametra*, male genitalia

82. - *Dactylethrella tetrametra*, male genitalia

Host plant: *Dodonaea viscosa* Jacq. (Sapindaceae). All types were raised from larvae.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Anarsia tremata nov.spec. - Figs. 63-64, 70-73.

Description: Wingspan: 11-13mm. Head, palpa, thorax and forewings light brownish-grey. Forewings lightly scattered with a few darker brownish cells.

Male genitalia (Fig.64): Tegumen broad and rounded, long gnathos. Asymmetric valvae, right valvae dilated with a digit form continuation and a long spine. Left valvae with 3 lobes: a digit form lobe, with an annexed broader lobe of half the length, continuing in a long spine, and a third lobe, dilated a base, narrowing at middle.

Aedeagus short, rounded with hook-shaped appendix.

Female genitalia (Fig.70, 73): with an undefined darker zone in the upper half of bursae; without signa.

Parasites: *Eriborus pallipes* (Brullé, 1846) (Ichneumonidae) (identification: Pascal Rousse, France).

Holotype: female, 12.vi.2015, Réunion, La Possession alt.400m, e.l. *Trema orientalis* #423a, in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108630.

Paratypes: 16 specimens of both sex, 25.ii.2015, 21.v.2015, 30.v.2015, 31.v.2015, 08.vi.2015, 16.vi.2015, 20.vi.2015, 26.vi.2015, 12.vii.2015, 22.vii.2015, 16.vii.2015, 18.viii.2015, 27.viii.2015 and 23.ix.2015. All paratypes had been raised e.l. *Trema orientalis* in Réunion, La Possession, alt.400 and 550m.

Host plant: *Trema orientalis* (L.) Blume (Ulmaceae). This species of tree was introduced in Réunion.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Anarsia vinsonella Viette, 1957 - Figs. 65-66.

Wingspan: 12.0 mm-13.0mm.

5 male were collected in Mauritius, Blackriver, 06.-10.vi.2016. Furthermore in Réunion, Sainte-Marie, 06.xii.2015 and La Possession, alt.400m, 11./13.ix.2018.

Distribution: Réunion (TL) and Mauritius.

Aristotelia bicomis nov.spec. - Figs. 75-79.

Description: Wingspan: 10.5mm, wing length: 4.5mm. Palpa fuscous, head greyish with fuscous. Antennae fuscous, 3/4 forewing lengths, simple, annealed. Forewings greyish scattered with irregular dark fuscous fields, bordered by dark-ochreous, at 1/5 of dorsum fuscous, 2 fields of a larger, triangular fuscous spot, first from 1/3 costa until 1/2 costa reaching dorsum, second at 3/4 to 4/5 almost reaching dorsum, followed by a neat fuscous streak in cell and a larger fuscous dot at apex.

Similar in forewing pattern to *Aristotelia comis* Meyrick, 1913 from South Africa but smaller in size (10.5mm against 12-15mm for *A. comis*). Both species distinguish notably by the shape of the signa in female.

Male genitalia: Tegumen broad at base, uncus rounded, longue gnathos. Symmetrical valvae and pointed aedeagus, broader at base.

Female genitalia: long ductus bursae, widening at bursae, oval bursae with a rectangular signa at bottom.

Holotype: male, 20.iv.2015 (gen.prep.RE-1748), in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108631.

Paratypes: 17 specimens, both sex dated: 11.v.2015 (female, gen. prep. RE-1816), 10.xi.2015, 27.iv.2016 (male, gen. prep. RE-2619), 11.v.2016, 25.vii.2016 (male, gen. prep. RE-2718), 12.ii.2018, 05.i.2020, 18.i.2020, 10.ii.2020, 15.ii.2020, 25.ii.2020, 03.iii.2020, 26.iii.2020, 31.iii.2020, 07.iv.2020, 04.v.2020 and 22.v.2020 in Naturalis Biodiversity Center.

Months: i, ii, iii, iv, v, vii, xi.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Dactylethrella tetrametra (Meyrick, 1913)- Figs. 80-81.

Redescription: Wingspan: 09mm. Head, body and forewings creamish-beige. On the forewings 5 minute spots on costa up to 3/4. Some 7 dark spots distributed irregularly in the fields.

Male genitalia: rounded uncus, valvae spade-like shaped and pointed, saccus by 2 projections. Aedeagus curved with pointed apex, dilated at base.

One male, 10.ii.2018, Réunion, Ste. Suzanne, alt.700m, 20°58'23"S/55°33'58"E, gen. prep. 8505 (Fig.81).

Distribution: South Africa (TL) & Réunion.

Bilobata subsecivella (Zeller, 1852) - Figs. 82-84.

Wingspan: 10mm

Examined: 1 male specimen, Mauritius, Mahébourg, alt.20m, 24.iv.2017.

Plate 12: Gelechiidae

- 83. - *Bilobata subsecivella*, adult
- 84. - *Bilobata subsecivella*, male genitalia
- 85. - *Dichomeris acuminata*, adult
- 86. - *Dichomeris acuminata*, male genitalia

- 87. - *Dichomeris andasibea*, adult
- 88. - *Dichomeris andasibea*, male genitalia
- 89. - *Dichomeris hortulana*, adult
- 90. - *Dichomeris hortulana*, male genitalia

91.

92.

93.

94.

95.

96.

97.

98.

Plate 13: Gelechiidae

91. - *Faristenia tamarinda*, adult

92. - *Faristenia tamarinda*, male genitalia

93. - *Faristenia tamarinda*, female genitalia

94. - *Faristenia tamarinda*, female genitalia

95. - *Helcystogramma convolvuli*, adult

96. - *Helcystogramma convolvuli*, male genitalia

97. - *Helcystogramma convolvuli*, female genitalia

98. - *Helcystogramma convolvuli*, larvae

This species had to be identified by the male genitalia provided by Philpott (1928, a+b) from New Zealand as *Stomopteryx columbina* Philpott, 1928.

The NHM name index (Beccaloni *et al.*, 2003) lists *Stomopteryx columbina* Philpott, 1928 as a junior synonym of *Bilobata (Stomopteryx) subsecivella* (Zeller, 1852) but unfortunately I could not find any publication on this synonymy nor other publications illustrating its genitalia, except the original publication by Philpott.

The genus *Bilobata* Vari in Vari & Kroon, 1986 is a replacement name for *Biloba* Janse, 1954 (preocc. Stach, 1951). Type species: *Gelechia subsecivella* Zeller, 1852.

ICRISAT (International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics) report 1986 (p.55) mentions a publication by Fearkin (1973): "*Aproaerema modicella* (Deventer, 1904) is also listed as a pest in Indonesia, under the earlier name of *Stomopteryx subsecivella*". I have not seen the publication of Fearkin and do not know if he illustrated that species or listed it as a junior synonym or not. There have been dozens of publications on *Aproaerema modicella* (Deventer, 1904) particularly by Crop Protection Agencies but nobody seems to have illustrated its genitalia. If the information provided by Fearkin (1973) is correct, not only these two species will need to be placed into synonymy but also the genus *Biloba* Janse, 1954 and its replacement name *Bilobata* Vari, 1986 will become a junior synonym of *Aproaerema* Durrant, 1897. Furthermore *Aproaerema modicella* (Deventer, 1904) would become a junior synonym of *Aproaerema subsecivella* (Zeller, 1852).

Brachmia septella (Zeller, 1852) - not illustrated.

This species was recorded for the first time from Mayotte where it was found by J. Rochat (pers. comm. J. Rochat, 2017).

Distribution: Gambia, Malawi, Sierra Leone, South Africa and Tanzania. New for Mayotte.

Dichomeris acuminata (Staudinger, 1876) - Fig. 85-86.

Wingspan: 12.5 mm.

One male on 11.iv.2020 in Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m.

Dichomeris andasibea nov. spec. - Figs. 87-88.

Description: Wingspan: 12.5 mm. Antennae 2/3rd forewing length. Head and Forewings uni, light beige-ochreous. Hindwings light beige-ochreous.

Male genitalia: Clubbed valvae, gnathos widened at apex, saccus very wide. Aedeagus broad, long and pointed, with a long cornuti.

Holotype: male, 29.xi.2016, Madagascar, Andasibe, alt.945m, geometrical coordinates 18°56'51"S/48°25'4", gen. prep. MG-018, in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108634.

Distribution: Madagascar (TL).

Dichomeris hortulana (Meyrick, 1918) - Figs. 89-90.

Orig. comb.: *Trichotaphe hortulana*, TL: South Africa

Syn. nov.: *Cymotricha tetraschema* Meyrick, 1931, TL: India (Gates, 1969a; Vol. VI, plate 266, Figs.2-2b)

Syn. nov.: *Dichomeris ceponoma* Meyrick, 1918, TL: India (Gates, 1969b; Vol. VII, plate 08, Figs. 3-3b)

Wingspan: 11mm

One male specimen, wingspan 11mm, in Mauritius, Blackriver, alt.55m, 12.vi.2016 (gen.prep.Mru-078). This species was also found in Mayotte during 2017 by J. Rochat (comm. pers. 2017).

Distribution: India, South Africa, Seychelles, Mauritius and Mayotte (new records; pers. comm. J. Rochat, 2017).

Remarks: This species was illustrated by Gates (1969a,b). He had already noticed the synonymy between *Cymotricha tetraschema* and *Dichomeris ceponoma* (1969b) but it seems to have been ignored by the scientific community.

Janse (1954) illustrated *Dichomeris hortulana (Trichotaphe)* on Plate CLXXXI though his image of the adult moth does not show the particular markings of the wings as his image was printed in black and white. I am therefore very grateful to Mr. James Lawrence & Mr. Peter Webb (South Africa) for providing an image of the holotype of *Trichotaphe hortulana*. These species are shown to be synonyms.

Faristenia tamarinda nov. spec. - Figs. 91-95; 114.

Description: Wingspan: 10.5mm. Antennae simple, fine, 2/3 forewing length, fuscous and ringed. Palpi fuscous mixed with beige-whitish. Head & abdomen greyish with some few darker, greyish specks. Forewings: shaded greyish, an irregular, transverse of irregularly shaped blackish spots at 2/5, a larger blackish spot at 2/3 in field, followed by a blackish costal mark at 4/5. Hindwings: greyish.

Male genitalia (Fig.96): Uncus rounded, small gnathos hook, asymmetrical valvae, right valvae waved, left valvae largely bulged in its middle. Short, pointed aedeagus, dilated at its base and a small, hooked tip.

Female genitalia (Figs.97-98): Long, twisted ductus bursae. Oval bursae with one, roundish signa.

Plate 14: Gelechiidae

- 99. - *Helcystogramma malagasy*, HT, adult
- 100. - *Helcystogramma malagasy*, male genitalia
- 101. - *Sitotroga psacasta* (Meyrick, 1908)
- 102. - *Sitotroga psacasta*, male genitalia

- 103. - *Sitotroga psacasta*, female genitalia
- 104. - *Sitotroga psacasta*, wing venations
- 105. - *Stegasta variana*, adult
- 106. - *Stegasta variana*, male genitalia

Holotype: male, 17.i.2020, Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108638.

Paratypes: 17.ix.2013, 12.iii.2015 (e.l. *Trema orientalis*), 17.iii.2015 (e.l. *Tamarindus indica*), 22.iii.2015 (e.l. *Tamarindus indica*), 13.iv.2015 (e.l. *Tamarindus indica*), 13.ix.2017, 13.ii.2016, 19.ii.2018, 09.i.2020, 15.i.2020, 17.i.2020, 18.i.2020, 20.i.2020 (2x), 21.i.2020 (3x), 22.i.2020, 14.ii.2020 in Naturalis Biodiversity Center.

Host plants: *Tamarindus indica* L. (Fabaceae) and *Trema orientalis* (L.) Blume (Cannabaceae).

Distribution: Réunion (TL) and Seychelles (Praslin). Certainly a species with a larger distribution than presently known.

Observation: I illustrated this species already in Bippus (2016a) from Praslin, Seychelles as *Gelechiidae* sp.01 (Bippus, 2016a; Figs. 98-101). It is probably an introduced species but seems to be without description.

Helcystogramma convolvuli (Walsingham, 1908) - Figs. 96-99.

Wingspan: 12mm.

Dates of collection (Réunion): 08.xii.2013, 16.v.2014, 11.iii.2020; 6 specimen e.l. *Ipomoea cairica* on 14.xii.2014, 21.xi.2015 and 23.iv.2016.

Host plants: In Réunion its larvae are very abundant on *Ipomoea cairica* (L.) Sweet, though single specimens feed also on *Ipomoea alba* L. (Convolvulaceae). In Mauritius I also found its larvae also on *Ipomoea alba* (09.vi.2016).

Distribution: Asia, Africa, Oceania, Middle East, Caribbean and Florida

Helcystogramma malagasy nov.spec. Figs. 99-100.

Description: Wingspan 11mm. Antennae simple. Head, abdomen and wings entirely dirty brownish, with a fine indication of a dark-brownish spot in cell at 1/3 and 3/5. Hindwings: light brownish-grey.

Male genitalia: Uncus rounded, tegumen dilated in middle, gnathos long, simple. Saccus pointed. Valvae almost straight, rounded at apex. Short, pointed aedeagus, dilated at its base.

Holotype: male, 24.xi.-03.xii.2016, Madagascar, Andasibe, alt.945m, 18°56'51"S/48°25'4", gen. prep. MG-038, in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108635.

Distribution: Madagascar.

Idiophantis valeriae Guillermet, 2010 - Figs. 172-173.

5 specimens of both sex were raised from fruits of *Syzygium cymosum* (Lam.) DC. (Myrtaceae) by Séb. Albert in Réunion, St. Philippe, 15.-25.ii.2018 (J. Rochat, pers.comm.2018). One female also in Réunion, Ste. Marie, 05.xii.2015.

Host plant: *Syzygium cymosum* (Lam.) DC. (Myrtaceae).

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Sitotroga psacasta (Meyrick, 1908) - Figs. 101-104.

Wingspan: 13mm.

Specimens examined: 25.iv.2015 (Réunion, St. Denis, Colorado); 17.iv.2016, 26.iv.2016 (male, gen. prep. RE-2608), 09.xii.2017, 05./08./11.i.2018, 2 specimens on 22.iv.2018 and 04.iv.2020 (all in Réunion, La Possession, 400m).

Recorded on wings in the months of: i, iv, xii.

Distribution: Southern Europe, Namibia, South Africa, Zimbabwe, Solomon Islands (Bradley, 1961), new for Réunion.

Stegasta variana Meyrick, 1904 - Figs. 105-106.

Wingspan: 10mm

One male on 04.01.2020, Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m.

Distribution: China, India, Congo, Eritrea, Kenya, Seychelles, South Africa, Zimbabwe, new for Réunion.

Thiotricha tenuis (Walsingham, 1891) - Figs. 107-109.

Wingspan: 10mm

One male in Mauritius (Fig.107-108), Flic-en-Flac, 10.-12.vi.2016, 4 specimens in Réunion, La Possession, 400m, 04./05.i.2020 and 7 specimens on 21.i.2020.

This species is variable in wing markings. My specimens from Réunion are much less marked than the excellently marked specimen from Mauritius (Fig.107).

Host plant: *Morinda citrifolia* L. (Rubiaceae) in the Seychelles (Gerlach & Matyot, 2006).

Distribution: Gambia, Seychelles, South Africa, recorded new for Mauritius and Réunion.

107.

108.

109.

110.

111.

112.

113.

114.

Plate 15:

107. - *Thiotricha tenuis*, adult

108. - *Thiotricha tenuis*, male genitalia

109. - *Thiotricha tenuis*, female genitalia

110. - *Lateantenna inana*, adult

111. - *Lateantenna inana*, male genitalia

112. - *Lateantenna inana*, female genitalia

113. - *Lateantenna inana*, wing venations

114. - *Faristenia tamarinda*, wing venations

115.

116.

117.

1 mm

118.

119.

120.

121.

122.

Plate 16: Tineidae

115. - *Agnathosia nana*, adult

116. - *Agnathosia nana*, male genitalia

117. - *Agnathosia nana*, wing venations

118. - *Eudarcia oceanica*, wing venations

119. - *Amphixystis guttata*, adult

120. - *Amphixystis guttata*, male genitalia

121. - *Amphixystis patelia*, adult

122. - *Amphixystis patelia*, male genitalia

Blastobasidae:

Lateantenna inana (Butler, 1881) - Figs. 110-113.

Wing length: 5.5mm, Wingspan: 12mm

9 specimens were collected at light in Réunion, La Possession, alt.400 m on the following dates: 17.xi.2015, 13.xii.2015 (female, gen. prep. RE-1571), 24.i.2017 (male, gen.prep.RE-3022), 17.xi.2017, 26.i.2018, 02.ii.2018 (wing prep. RE-3496), 15.v.2018 (male, gen. prep. RE-3546, Fig.111), 13.x.2019 and 19.iv.2020.

Recorded on wings in the month of: i, ii, iv, v, x, xi, xii

Wing venations (Fig.113): Zimmerman (1979) illustrated a supplementary vein on the hindwing from base to dorsum.

I believe that this is correct but my specimen's hindwing was damaged in this area.

Host plants: Garden beans (*Phaseolus* sp. (L.) Mill (Fabaceae)), coffee berries (*Coffea* sp. L. - Rubiaceae), dead sugar cane (*Saccharum officinarum* L. - Poaceae), *Dioscorea* (yam - Dioscoreaceae), *Allium sativum* L. (Garlic - Amaryllidaceae) and *Eugenia uniflora* L. (Myrtaceae) (Zimmerman, 1978; Clarke, 1986).

Its host-plant in Reunion remains unknown but there is a *Eugenia uniflora* bush growing at a distance of 15 meters from the site of collection.

Distribution: Oahu, Hawaii (Type locality), India, New Britain (Zimmerman, 1979) and French Polynesia (Marqueses) (Clarke, 1986). New to Réunion (new record and also the first record from an African country). Zimmerman (1979) suggested that this is a widely distributed species that had been dispersed by man. Apparently he is right.

Remarks: Many thanks to Dr. David Adamski (Smithsonian, USA) for his help on identification of this species.

Tineidae:

Agnathosia nana nov. spec. - Figs. 115-117.

Description: Wingspan: variable in size, between 8-15mm. Most specimens have a wingspan between 11-14 mm.

Antennae 2/3 of forewing lengths. Front tufted dirty whitish, thorax whitish with greyish cells.

Forewings light greyish-white, on costa near base a short blackish streak, a blackish dot just behind in cell, 2 interrupted transverse lines, first at 1/3, second at half only indicated, a 3rd transverse line at 5/6th of forewing only indicated.

Hindwings light greyish-white.

Male genitalia (Fig.116): Weakly sclerotized tegumen, gnathos absent, doubled structured valvae, one with digit-form, rounded apex, the other with pointed apex. Pointed saccus. Short, stout aedeagus, pointed apex with cornuti.

Holotype: male, 17.i.2015, gen. prep. RE-1458 (Fig. 116), Réunion, La Possession, alt. 400m in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Netherlands, RMNH. No.1283507.

Paratypes: Both sex, dated: 01./11.xii.2014, 19./27./29.i.2015, 16./19./22..ii.2015, 24.ii.2015 (2x), 02.iii.2015, 14./21.iv.2015, 22.vi.2015, 14.iii.2020, 21.iii.2020, 31.iii.2020 in Naturalis Biodiversity Center.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Amphixystis anchiala (Meyrick, 1909) - Fig.196.

1 male in Madagascar, Andasibe, alt. 945m, 18°56'51"S/48°25'4", 24.xi.-03.xii.2016.

Distribution: Madagascar, Nigeria and South Africa

Amphixystis fragosa (Meyrick, 1910)

This is the most common *Amphixystis* species in Réunion island. It flies all year in low and medium altitudes.

I collected also 2 specimens in Mauritius (TL), Flic-en- Flac, 11.vi.2016.

Possibly *Amphixystis cymataula* (Meyrick, 1926) from Zimbabwe is a junior synonym but the quality of images that are provided for this species is too poor.

Distribution: Mauritius (TL) and Réunion.

Amphixystis fricata (Meyrick, 1911) - Figs. 170-171.

1 worn (?) male specimen in Madagascar, Andasibe, alt. 945m, 18°56'51"S/48°25'4", 24.xi.-03.xii.2016.

Distribution: Seychelles (Mahé, Silhouette & Aride) and new for Madagascar.

Amphixystis guttata nov.spec. - Figs. 119-120.

Description: Wingspan: 11mm. Head, front and thorax beige-brownish, antennae greyish in length of forewing.

Forewings brownish, first quarter of costa with brownish strigulae, from 1/4 to apex a broader dark-brownish streak interrupted by whitish streaks. First 1/5 of forewing uniformly brownish, with few darker cells. Followed by a series of dark-brownish spots and a dark-brownish streak in cell. At apex an blackish strigulae surrounded by light-brownish.

Male genitalia (Fig.120): Short, bilobed valvae, inner apex pointed. Saccus very long and pointed. Very long aedeagus, ending in a rolled tip.

Plate 17:

- 123. - *Amphixystis patelia*, female genitalia
- 124. - *Eudarcia oceanica*, female genitalia
- 125. - *Eudarcia oceanica*, adult
- 126. - *Eudarcia oceanica*, male genitalia

- 127. - *Erehtias nigrocaputis*, HT, adult
- 128. - *Erehtias nigrocaputis*, HT, male genitalia
- 129. - *Tonza toga*, HT, adult
- 130. - *Tonza toga*, male genitalia

Holotype: male, 07.vii.2017, Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m, in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108640.

Paratypes: male: 15.xii.2017, 21.i.2018, 27.ii.2018, 28.ii.2018 and 07.iv.2018 in Naturalis Biodiversity Center.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Amphixystis patelia nov. spec. - Figs. 121-123.

Description: Wingspan: 8'5mm-9.5mm. Palpi greyish-beige with dark fuscous, frons blackish-fuscous, Antennae dark brownish-fuscous, in length of forewing.

Upperside: Forewings and shoulders are dark-greyish-fuscous, with a beige strigulae at 4/5 shortly behind costa, a second strigulae at dorsum at 2/3. Underside of forewing dark fuscous-grey, hindwings greyish. Underside of abdomen brownish-beige, sprinkled with fuscous.

Male genitalia (Fig.122): Short bilobed valvae, outer large and rounded apex, the inner small and pointed apex. Long aedeagus, pointed.

Female genitalia (Fig.123): long ductus bursae, a U-shaped thickening at base of bursae (detail in Fig.123)

Holotype: male, 10.ii.2018, Réunion, Ste. Suzanne, alt. 700m (gen. prep. RE-3504), in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108641.

Paratypes: 2 female, 10.ii.2018, Ste. Suzanne, 700m (gen. prep. RE-3510) and 12.i.2018, Réunion, La Possession, 400m in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, 3 male, 12.i.2018, 08.iv.2018 and 21.iii.2020 (abdomen glued), Réunion, La Possession, 400m in Naturalis Biodiversity Center.

1 female, 06.iv.2018, La Possession, 400m (abdomen damaged) in collection Bippus.

Etymology: Dedicated to Mr. Haroun Patel, St. André, Réunion.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Amphixystis serrata (Meyrick, 1914)

Syn.nov.: *Amphixystis maillardella* (Viette, 1957) [Orig. comb. *Oinophila maillardella*]

Wingspan: 9.5mm-10mm.

These species are corresponding in genitalia and in imago. Therefore they are synonyms.

Distribution: Kenya, Malawi, Mauritius (de Prins & de Prins, 2019) and Réunion.

Erechtias nigrocaputis nov. spec. - Figs. 127-128.

Description: Wingspan: 7.5-9mm. Head and scalp black, Antennae beige with brownish, simple. Palpae, thorax and abdomen cream-beige with a few scattered darker cells. Forewings cream-beige, costa dotted with blackish a little above half, at half near costa a prominent, large blackish spot, a smaller blackish streak shortly before apex.

Underside brownish scattered with beige cells. Hindwings: light cream-beige.

Male genitalia: Simple tegumen, gnathos absent, valvae costa straight, dorsum rounded with a pointed process. Saccus long and spiniform. Aedeagus long and simple, straight.

Holotype: male (Figs. 127-128), 18.i.2017, La Possession, alt. 400m, gen. prep. RE-3007, geographical coordinates: 20°55'37"S/ 55°21'45"E, in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108637.

Paratypes: all females: 22.xii.2015, Ste. Suzanne, alt. 700m; 10.ii.2017, Ste. Suzanne, alt.700m; 17.ii.2017, La Possession, alt.400m and 21.xii.2017, La Possession, alt. 400m, in Naturalis Biodiversity Center.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Eudarcia oceanica nov. spec. - Fig. 118 (wing venations); Figs. 124-126.

Description: Wingspan: 5.8-6.3mm. Antennae simple, greyish, head greyish tufted, forewings whitish-greyish, irregularly sprinkled with blackish cells. Hindwings: light greyish.

There is an important variability in density of the black cells on the forewings. Most specimens are whitish-grey, scattered with blackish over 40-50% (Fig.125) without a standard pattern.

Male genitalia (Fig.126): Uncus bifid, valvae almost as long as uncus high, valvae with a round cavitation. Slim, simple aedeagus, without cornuti.

Female genitalia (Fig.124): Without a clear structure, appears to be a simple loop, without a clearly defined bursae.

Holotype: male, 17.ii.2016, (gen. prep. RE-2444, Réunion, La Possession, alt. 400m in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Netherlands, RMNH.No.1283508.

Paratypes: 23 specimens of both sex dated 15.i.2016, 18.ii.2016, 17.iii.2016 (3x), 25.iv.2016, 11.x.2016 (2x), 18.xii.2017, 25.xii.2018, 14.i.2018, 14.ii.2018, 07.iv.2018, 21.i.2020, 25.i.2020, 27.i.2020 (2x), 04.ii.2020, 15.ii.2020 (2x), 21.ii.2020, 02.iii.2020 in Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Netherlands.

Two specimens were also collected in Mauritius, Blackriver, 06./10.vi.2016. One male dissected, gen. prep. Mru-135.

Distribution: Réunion (TL) and Mauritius.

Plate 18:

- 131. - *Megalorrhipida monsa*, adult
- 132. - *Megalorrhipida monsa*, male genitalia
- 133. - *Megalorrhipida monsa*, female genitalia
- 134. - *Megalorrhipida monsa*, larvae
- 135. - *Megalorrhipida monsa*, underside abdomen

- 136. - *Prays armynoti*, male
- 137. - *Prays armynoti*, female
- 138. - *Prays armynoti*, male genitalia
- 139. - *Prays armynoti*, female genitalia

Opogona transversata Bippus, 2016 - Fig. 174.

Supplementary specimens were collected (Réunion, La Possession, 400m):

1 female on 15.v.2018, 6 specimens on 14.ii.2020 (one male, gen. prep. RE-4111, Fig. 174), 1 female on 28.ii.2020, 1 male on 05.iii.2020 and 1 male on 15.iii.2020.

I still would like to illustrate its male genitalia (Fig. 174) and attribute a vernacular name: Yellow-vested moth (English), Gelbwestenmotte (German) and Teigne gilet jaune (French). Personally I find vernacular names rather ridiculous but governmental agencies love to use them.

Some additional specimens will be deposited in the Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Netherlands.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Tonzidae:

Tonza toga nov. spec. - Figs. 129-130.

Description: Wingspan: 16mm. Head, thorax and abdomen whitish, Antennae above light, simple. Palpi and base of antennae tinged light straw yellowish. The eyes appear blackish at the dead specimen though they would have been greyish on the living lepidopteran.

Forelegs brownish with straw-yellow femorae, remaining legs straw-yellowish, tibia of the last pair ringed blackish.

Forewings are white, bordered broadly pale straw-yellowish along costa. A light-brown streak, irregularly dotted by dark-brown scales crossing the wing in its middle from base to tornus, continuing narrowly along outer margin to apex. A larger, elongated brown dot at 2/3. 3 smaller dark-brown at 4/5th. Cilia white, tinged brownish between apex and tornus. Hindwings whitish, tinged a little straw yellowish near outer margin at apex. Cilia white.

Male genitalia (Fig.130): Valvae slim, rounded at end, with 2 projections at inner side. One near base, the second at 1/3. Bifurcated uncus on a moderately scarified tegumen, broad saccus with a fine and long projection. Aedeagus long and slim, without cornuti, approx. 1.2mm of length.

Holotype: 1 male, 18.i.2017, Réunion, La Possession, Ravine à Malheur, alt. 400m, Geographical coordinates: 20°55'37"S/55°21'45"E (gen. prep. RE-3012) in Naturalis, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108633.

J. Rochat (pers. comm. 2017) had observed this species also at Plaine des Palmistes, Réunion on 01.xii.2011.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Etymology: By its colouration this species remembers to the ancient Roman "toga praetexta" but as I prefer short species names "toga" seems to be a good option.

Pterophoridae:

Exelastis phlyctaenias (Meyrick, 1911) - Figs. 167, 177.

One female specimen was recorded in Mauritius, Blackriver, 10.vi.2016, gen. prep. Mru-067 (Fig.167; new record).

This is also a common species in Réunion.

Hellinsia imerinae (Bigot, 1964) n. comb. [Pterophorus]

Junior synonym: *Oidaematophorus mineti* Gibeaux, 1994 syn. nov

Forewing length: 11mm, wingspan 23-24mm.

2 pupae and 2 caterpillars were collected on *Vernonia appendiculata* Less. (Asteraceae) in Parque Botanique et Zoologique de Tsimbazaza, Antananarivo, Madagascar (18°55'48"S/47°31'34"E) from which were raised 4 specimens (male & female) of *Hellinsia imerinae* in xii.2016. Its female genitalia corresponds to *Oidaematophorus mineti* Gibeaux, 1994 syn. nov. that was described from a female holotype.

I am aware that *Hellinsia imerinae* was already put into synonymy with *Picardia orchatias* (Meyrick, 1908). Though no genitalia images of *P.orchatias* are presently available therefore I stick to *Hellinsia imerinae* which had its genitalia illustrated (Gibeaux, 1994).

Host plant: *Vernonia appendiculata* Less. (Asteraceae).

Distribution: Madagascar (TL).

Remarks: I would like to thank Mr. Romer Rabarijaona (Fianarantsoa) for his help in identification of the host plant and also Mr. Christian Gibeaux (France) for providing one issue of his 1994 publication to me.

Hellinsia madecasseus (Bigot, 1964)

Specimens were raised from larvae on 30.x./01.xi.2014, 10.i.2015, 14.ii.2015, 22.iii.2015, 24.iv.2015, 13.vi.2017 and 12.viii.2017 (all in Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m) on *Acanthospermum hispidum* D.C. and *Tithonia diversifolia* (Hemsl.) A. Gray. Seems to be more abundant on *Tithonia diversifolia* than on *Acanthospermum hispidum*.

Host plants: *Acanthospermum hispidum* D.C. and *Tithonia diversifolia* (Hemsl.) A. Gray (Asteraceae).

Plate 19: Yponomeutidae

- 140. - *Kessleria gibeauxia*, adult
- 141. - *Kessleria gibeauxia*, male genitalia
- 142. - *Kessleria gibeauxia*, in-situ
- 143. - *Xyrosaris canusa*, in-situ

- 144. - *Xyrosaris canusa*, adult
- 145. - *Xyrosaris canusa*, female genitalia
- 146. - *Gibeauxiella reliqua*, adult
- 147. - *Gibeauxiella reliqua*, male genitalia

Megalorhipida monsa nov. spec. - Figs. 131-135.

Description:

Wingspan: 10.5-11mm. Antennae simple, annulated. Abdomen, body and wings uniformly brownish, at 4/5 and 5/6 of forewing an indication of a whitish-transversal line. Underside of wings uniformly brownish. Underside abdomen & legs: whitish, densely speckled with fuscous, abdomen whitish ringed fuscous (Fig. 135).

Larvae (Fig. 124): The larvae feed on sticky secretions on the underside of young leaves of *Dombeya ciliata* Cordem.. Mostly they were found near the centre of the leaves. Also adults can be found sitting during daytime on the undersides of young leaves of *Dombeya ciliata*.

Male genitalia: tegumen weak, clubbed valvae, straight aedeagus.

Female genitalia: a S-shaped, scarified ductus bursae, ovoid bursae without signa.

Holotype: male, 14.ii.2016, Réunion, La Montagne, alt. 900m, e.l. *Dombeya ciliata*, leg. Maik Bippus, numbered: RE-2420. In Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Netherlands, RMNH No.1108642.

Paratypes: 15 specimens of both sex, collected e.l. *Dombeya ciliata* Cordem. (Sterculiaceae) or as pupae/adults at daytime on *Dombeya ciliata*, in Naturalis, Netherlands (14 of these specimens from Réunion, La Montagne, alt.900m, one specimen from Réunion, St.Paul (Maido), alt. 1670m.).

Dates of paratypes: 09.iv.2015, 12.iv.2015, 28.iv.2015, 04.ii.2016, 06.ii.2016, 19.ii.2016 (2x), 27.ii.2016, 13.iii.2016 (2x), 16.iii.2016, 03.iv.2016 (3x) and 09.iv.2016.

Host-plant: *Dombeya ciliata* Cordem. (Sterculiaceae).

Etymology: derived from mons = mountain, or La Montagne (French).

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Platytilia fulva Bigot, 1964

2 male, wingspan 16mm, in Madagascar, Andasibe, 02./03.xii.2016.

Sphenarches anisodactylus (Walker, 1864)

The larvae of this species was found very abundantly feeding on flowers of *Cynorkis purpurascens* Thouars. (Orchidaceae). More than 25 specimens were bred on 15.-25.ii.2016 (Réunion, La Montagne, alt. 900m) on this plant. At light also recorded in Mauritius, Bambous, 11.vi.2016.

Stenoptilodes taprobanes (Felder & Rogenhofer, 1875) - Fig. 168.

One female was bred from flowers of *Antirrhinum majus* L. (Plantaginaceae) on 28.x.2016 (Réunion, La Possession, alt. 400m). This species of plant had been recorded already by Zimmerman (1978) from Hawaii.

Another female (Fig. 168, gen. prep. MG-009) was collected at light in Madagascar, Andasibe, 30.xi.2016.

Praydidae:

Prays armynoti nov. spec. - Figs. 136-141.

Description: Wingspan: 11mm. This species is variable in adult morphology. The holotype can be described as being: antennae half of forewing length, simple and stout, greyish. Shoulders greyish with whitish, abdomen greyish. Forewings greyish, with a larger whitish patch at dorsum near shoulder. Some smaller whitish dots at costa above 1/2 and some whitish dots at submarginal termen. Hindwings: greyish.

One specimen from the same larval lot shows to be entirely dark greyish, with minute lighter greyish spot at 4/5 of costa and 2/3 dorsum, and also 2 female specimens that I raised earlier in 2016 on the same hostplant are entirely greyish. I believe therefore that this species is variable in adult morphology.

Male genitalia: valvae long and spiniform, auxiliary valvae moderately rectangular, uncus angulated, broad saccus, aedeagus moderately curved, one minute cornuti.

Female genitalia: one large signa in bursae.

Holotype: 03.xi.2017, male, Réunion, Grand Galet/Col Blanc, 21°18'39"S/55°38'30"S, alt. 700m, e.l. *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. (Rutaceae), leg. J.Armynot (gen.prep.RE-3460b), in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, RMNH No.1283505.

Paratypes: 3 females, same collection data & collector and 1 female, La Montagne, alt. 900m, RE-2536b, e.l. *Toddalia asiatica*, 27.ii.2016, leg. M. Bippus, in Naturalis Biodiversity Center.

1 female, in private collection Bippus, same data as holotype, gen. prep. RE-3460e.

Host plant: *Toddalia asiatica* (L.) Lam. (Rutaceae).

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Etymology: Dedicated to the finder of this species, Mr. Jean Armynot, France.

Yponomeutidae:

Kessleria gibeauxia nov.spec. - Figs. 140-142.

Description: Wingspan: 10mm. Head & palpaes beige mixed with ochreous-brownish, antennae almost as long as forewings (85-90%). Forewings ochreous-brownish mixed with greyish, a small blackish spot on dorsum at half, a second small blackish spot on 4/5th shortly before dorsum.

Male genitalia: Broad valvae, digit-form saccus with rounded apex. Very long (approx 1.4mm) and slim aedeagus, straight, with cornuti at apex. Two coremata on the eighth abdominal segment.

Holotype: male, 25.iv.2015, St. Denis (Colorado), alt.700m, 20°54'35"S/55°25'22" E, gen. prep. RE-1773, in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Netherlands, RMNH No.1283504.

Paratypes: 3 specimens (male) from Takamaka, 09.i.2016 and 1 male (gen. prep. RE-4382), Sainte-Suzanne, 700m on 10.ii.2018 in Naturalis Biodiversity Center.

1 additional specimen from the same place/date was moisture damaged and is retained in my personal collection.

On 25.i.2014 and 04.i.2020 I also observed this species in La Possession, alt. 400m but both specimens escaped.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Etymology: Named in honour of Mr. Christian Gibeaux. Also for thanking him for having sent me a copy of his publication from 1994 on Pterophoridae.

Swammerdamia villiersi Gibeaux, 1984 - Figs.148-149.

1 female in Madagascar, Andasibe, 30.xi.2016. Seems to be a common species in Andasibe. I collected 3 specimens during my stay at Andasibe.

Distribution: Madagascar (TL).

Xyrosaris canusa nov.spec. - Figs. 143-145.

Description: Wingspan: 15mm. Head and palpaes greyish, mixed with a few darker greyish-blackish scales.

Forewings greyish, a few darker greyish cells along costa, two small blackish cell-spots, one at 2/5th and the second at 2/3rd in cell. On the paratype a small, dark greyish-blackish zone at dorsum at half.

Female genitalia (Fig.145): ductus bursae 3x as long as bursae diameter, roundish bursae with one signa.

Holotype: female, 02.ii.2020, Réunion, La Possession, alt. 400m, in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Netherlands, RMNH1283503.

Paratype: male, 15.i.2017 (abdomen lost), same locality, in Naturalis Biodiversity Center.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Cosmopterigidae:

Anatrachyntis simplex (Walsingham, 1891) - Figs. 150-153.

Wingspan: 9.5-10.0mm.

In Réunion the larvae of this species can be found in huge quantities on *Typha domingensis* Pers. (Typhaceae) (in cattails). There are up to 20-40 larvae in a cattail.

Host plant: *Typha domingensis* Pers. (Typhaceae) (Fig. 152).

Anatrachyntis rileyi (Walshingham, 1882) - Figs. 154-155.

Wingspan: 9-11mm.

4 specimens were found in Mauritius, Bambous, 12.vi.2016 (gen. prep. Mru-080) and Mahébourg, 24.iv.2017 (male & female, gen. prep. Mru-130 and Mru-131).

Distribution: Antilles, Hawaii, South America, Australia, new for Mauritius and also first record from an Africa country.

Calicotis attiei (Guillermet, 2011) new.comb. [orig. comb. *Stathmopoda attiei* Guillermet, 2011]

Syn.nov.: *Calicotis cuspidata* Guan & Li, 2015 (TL: China).

Wingspan: 9 mm.

From genitalia and habitus this species belongs to the genus *Calicotis* Meyrick, 1889 new. comb..

This species had been re-described as *Calicotis cuspidata* Guan & Li, 2015 from China though I expect it to have a much wider distribution.

For its genitalia I refer to Guan & Li (2015) or its original publication. Having dissected more than 10 males it shows to absorb very badly colourants. I cannot figure it as well as Guan & Li (2015) did.

Calicotis attiei was bred from 3 different species of introduced ferns, including *Phymatosorus scolopendria* (Burm.f.) Pic. (Polypodiaceae). It feeds on the spores and can be found in huge quantities.

Some 12-15 specimen bred from larvae had been added to the collections of Naturalis Biodiversity Center in 2016.

Plate 20:

- 148. - *Swammerdamia villiersi*, adult
- 149. - *Swammerdamia villiersi*, female genitalia
- 150. - *Anatrachyntis simplex*, adult
- 151. - *Anatrachyntis simplex*, male genitalia

- 152. - *Typha domingensis* (host-plant)
- 153. - *Anatrachyntis simplex*, larvae
- 154. - *Anatrachyntis rileyi*, adult
- 155. - *Anatrachyntis rileyi*, male genitalia

156.

157.

158.

159.

160.

161.

162.

163.

Plate 21:

- 156. - *Pyroderces spix*, adult
- 157. - *Pyroderces spix*, adult
- 158. - *Pyroderces spix*, female genitalia
- 159. - *Pyroderces spix*, male genitalia

- 160. - *Batrachedra rainha*, adult
- 161. - *Batrachedra rainha*, adult
- 162. - *Batrachedra rainha*, larvae
- 163. - *Batrachedra rainha*, male genitalia

Host plants: polyphagous on ferns' spores, including *Phymatosorus scolopendria* (Burm.f.) Pic. (Polypodiaceae).

Distribution : Réunion (TL) and China.

Remarks: I have to thank Mr. Sjaak Kusters for his hint to look for larvae on fern spores; I found it the same day in my garden.

Gibeauxiella reliqua (Gibeaux, 1986) - Figs.146-147.

Wingspan: 9.5 mm. 5 specimens at Madagascar, Andasibe, 24.xi.-03.xii.2016, gen. prep. MG-014 (male).

This find disturbs me a little: this species was described from France but it seems to be a rather common species in Madagascar, in a completely different habitat. I wonder if the type specimen was correctly labelled? Mr. Gibeaux was working also on Malagasy Lepidoptera at the time of description.

Distribution: France (?) and Madagascar.

Remarks: I wish to thank Mr. Sergej Sinev & Mr. Sjaak Koster for help & documentation.

Pyroderces spix nov.spec. - Figs.156-159.

Description: Wingspan: 10mm. Antennae about 3/4, head & palpaie whitish, eyes red. Forewings brownish, with a white stripe of 1/3 of forewing width along dorsum from base to apex.

2 blackish spots at 1/4 and 1/2, about 1/3 from dorsum. 2 smaller blackish spots shortly before half and at 3/4 at 1/3 from costa. Cilia greyish, hindwings greyish.

Male genitalia (Fig. 159): Doubled, asymmetric uncus, saccus absent, rectangular valvae, with two auxiliary valvae.

Female genitalia (Fig. 158): ductus bursae fine, in length of diameter of bursae. Bursae round, without visible signa.

Holotype: male, 29.vii.2017, Réunion, La Possession, alt.400m in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Netherlands, RMNH 1108632.

Paratypes: 09.vi.2018 (female), Réunion, La Possession, alt. 400m at Naturalis Biodiversity Center, 08.x.2016, 20.i.2018, 21.i.2018 in my collection.

Distribution: Réunion (TL).

Batrachedridae:

Batrachedra cf.arenosella (Walker, 1864) - Figs. 175-176.

Wingspan: 10mm. 4 specimens were collected in Mauritius, Blackriver on 11.vi.2016 and Mahébourg (Garden of National History Museum), alt. 20m, on 13.vi.2016. 1 male and female dissected (gen. prep. Mru-027 & Mru-028). Also a common species in Réunion. The Mauritian specimen had a longer aedeagus than illustrated by Guillermet (2011) from Réunion.

Batrachedra rainha nov.spec. - Figs. 160-163.

Description: Wingspan 11mm. Palpaie black annealed, head ochreous brownish, tuff dirty beige, forewings ochreous-brownish scattered with blackish scales, more densely along costa and dorsum. One blackish mark in cell at 1/3.

Male genitalia (Fig. 163): Large, spade like uncus, narrow at base. Elongated, bifurcated valvae. One valvae long & narrow, with setae on apex, the other one short, pointed and dilated in the middle. Long and narrow aedeagus.

Holotype: male, 03.vii.2016, gen. prep. RE-2686, Réunion, La Possession, alt.200m, e.l. *Roystonea* (?) *regia*, in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Netherlands, RMNH 1283506.

Paratype: female, 04.vii.2016, gen. prep. RE-2735, same collection data, in collection M. Bippus.

Hostplant: *Roystonea* (?) *regia* (Kunth) O.F. Cook (Arecaceae).

Some doubts on the host plant persist: there are two introduced *Roystonea* species in Réunion. I believe its host plant is *Roystonea regia* but do not know the exact differences between the species.

Distribution: Réunion (TL) - introduced.

Images of the species that are not illustrated in this publication will be put into the disposition of De Prins & De Prins (2019) www.afromoths.net.

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Plate 22:

- 164. - *Tetramoera schistaceana*, female genitalia
- 165. - *Megalonocyta kissa*, female genitalia
- 166. - *Tebenna cornua*, female genitalia
- 167. - *Exelastis phlyctaenias*, female genitalia
- 168. - *Stenoptilodes taprobanes*, female genitalia
- 169. - *Amphixystis anchiala*, adult
- 170. - *Amphixystis fricata*, adult

- 171. - *Amphixystis fricata*, male genitalia
- 172. - *Idiophantis valeriae*, adult
- 173. - *Idiophantis valeriae*, male genitalia (aed.in-situ)
- 174. - *Opogona transversata*, male genitalia
- 175. - *Batrachedra arenosella*, male genitalia (Mauritius)
- 176. - *Batrachedra arenosella*, female (Mauritius)
- 177. - *Exelastis phlyctaenias*, male genitalia

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